

Sharing Digital Sequence Information

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Study for the European Commission

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1 Executive Summary

This paper addresses the sharing of digital sequence information. Digital sequence information is a placeholder term for genetic sequence data in international policy debates under the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity and its Nagoya Protocol, the Plant Treaty of the Food and Agriculture Organisation, the draft treaty on marine biodiversity under UNCLOS, the World Health Organisation and related policy processes.

This paper follows on from a research paper prepared for the European Commission in February 2020 entitled *Digital Sequence Information - Technical Aspects* (Oldham 2020). The earlier paper used a Sustainable Social Ecological Systems (SES) approach pioneered by economist Elinor Ostrom for the analysis of the governance of common pool resources to explore the options that might exist to address digital sequence information under the CBD and related processes (Ostrom 2009; Hess and Ostrom 2006). The analysis in that paper identified two key issues:

1. There is an urgent need to generate monetary benefits for investments in biodiversity;
2. The biodiversity and life science infrastructure that makes digital sequence information openly available for wider use is under pressure from the explosion in sequence data and user demand but lacks stable and sustainable sources of funding.

In response, the earlier paper argued that options existed to address both of these issues by recognising two features of the modern digital economy. The first is that the digital economy is constructed around copyright based open source and Creative Commons licences that allow creators to set basic terms and conditions for sharing and collaborating on creative works such as publications, images, software and data. These licences creatively exploit the possibilities of copyright law and have increasingly been extended to biodiversity data including for over 2 billion species occurrence records at the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

The second feature of the digital economy is that the dramatic growth of digital data over the course of the last decade has led to new approaches to the storage and processing of data and new and highly profitable business models in the form of cloud computing. In essence “the cloud” involves remote storage and processing of data and is encountered by most people in the form of storage of photos on subscription platforms such as Google Photos or Apple iCloud. However, these services are part of a wider and rapidly growing multi-billion dollar industry that focuses on the provision of a wide range of infrastructure and software services for which users pay by the second, the minute and the hour.

This paper ties these two outcomes of the earlier analysis together to propose that it may be possible to construct a cross-instrument approach to digital sequence information that would generate revenue for investment in biodiversity and the biodiversity and life science infrastructure.

The essence of this proposal is as follows:

1. Participating parties would agree a set of principles focusing on the promotion of open access and open science in addressing digital sequence information. The principles could draw on the recommendations in the 2021 *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* and *OECD Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data* (EASD);
2. Drawing on the experience of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) as an intergovernmental network involving developed and developing countries, participating parties would adopt a small set of standard open licences for digital sequence information. Participating parties would require users to deposit licenced sequences in participating databases;
3. Digital sequence information would remain openly accessible free of charge;
4. Participating databases and service providers would charge users low level fees for the use of the infrastructure and services based on experience with cloud service pricing models (e.g. subscriptions, “pay as you go”);
5. Participating parties would receive fees that would be held nationally/regionally in a national/regional fund as part of a *distributed global biodiversity fund*;
6. Participating parties would, over time, introduce additional revenue generation measures on the national/regional level that may include *inter alia*: a bio-based product levy; a micro-levy (e.g. on reagents/sequencing machines); royalty fees linked to patent filings or other revenue generation measures.
7. A portion of revenue generated would support the sustainability of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure and a portion would be committed for investments in biodiversity;
8. Participating parties would establish a *shared roadmap* to set out priorities for investments in biodiversity at the required level for successful implementation (e.g. local, national, regional, international). The shared roadmap would support implementation of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework;
9. Participating parties would make disbursements for investment in accordance with the shared roadmap in partnership with other participating parties. Disbursements would be made and accounted for through existing agencies at the appropriate level. Priority in partnerships would be given to partnerships with developing country participants and indigenous peoples and local communities at the forefront of the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity;
10. Key participants in the implementation of the proposal outlined above include: the private sector, as both service providers and users; research funding bodies, in identifying and coordinating research priorities under the shared roadmap; technical assistance agencies and non-governmental organisations in facilitating partnerships and administration of disbursements, and; indigenous peoples and local communities as the principal guardians of biodiversity.
11. No new legal instrument is anticipated under this proposal. Participating parties under instruments and processes participating in the above system would establish cost-effective measures for the establishment of the shared roadmap, experience sharing, reporting and periodic updating of the shared roadmap and other measures.

This paper argues that any revenue generating measures on digital sequence information should form part of a flexible framework consisting of multiple revenue generation options (Oldham 2020). Revenue generation models should then be modelled and evaluated for inclusion within the wider framework and could be tested by participating Parties in a set of pilots. This is a more flexible approach to the construction of a benefit-sharing mechanism than has historically been the case under environmental instruments. The challenges involved in agreeing on a flexible approach with multiple revenue generation elements in a negotiation should probably not be underestimated. Nevertheless, this approach would avoid the pitfalls experienced in the past of opting for a single untested approach to benefit-sharing.

In debates on digital sequence information, the necessity of the openness of digital sequence information without responsibility or obligation has been emphasised by some in the scientific community and the private sector. However, this emphasis on openness is relatively recent and can be traced to sharing practices that emerged during the Human Genome Project and its Bermuda Principles that emphasise placing sequence data into the public domain (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018). Following the completion of the Human Genome Project, anonymous, open and unrestricted access to sequence data, that we might call the public domain by any other name, has become established policy of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC).

Advocacy for a single solution to data sharing as a global norm for sequence data disguises the significant and enduring tensions that existed at the time the Bermuda Principles were agreed. These tensions are manifest in the launch in 2008 of GISAID as a platform for sharing influenza and coronavirus sequences. GISAID uses its terms and conditions as an open licence that requires recognition of contributions and best efforts to promote collaborations. The popularity of this approach with researchers from both developing and developed countries has become apparent during the COVID-19 pandemic. GISAID is the single most popular platform for sharing COVID-19 sequence data (Maxmen 2021b). Debates on the merits of different approaches to data sharing during the COVID-19 pandemic were played out in the pages of *Nature* and other scientific journals. All participants in these debates appear to be committed to the pursuit of open science. The question that emerges is how data sharing may best be pursued while recognising the diverse interests of the communities involved.

We argue that the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), established by governments in 2001, provides a more suitable model for identifying a way forward on sharing digital sequence information than the INSDC or GISAID models. GBIF is an international network that is funded and governed by governments from developed and developing countries and actively engages with scientists, amateur naturalists and citizen scientists around the world. As a global network GBIF provides open access to over 2 billion species occurrence records including metadata linked to sequence records.

GBIF has sought to balance the needs and interests of data providers and users in a different way to the INSDC and GISAID. As the network grew GBIF was confronted by the existence of hundreds of different terms and conditions for its species occurrence records. The confusion this created was not in the interests of its data publishers or users. In 2013 GBIF initiated two rounds of public consultation to debate the

introduction of a set of standard Creative Commons licences. This led to agreement by the governing body in 2014 to use three standard Creative Commons licences across taxonomic data submitted to GBIF. The three Creative Commons licences are: any use permitted provided that the source is attributed (CC-BY); use provided there is attribution and the data is used for non-commercial purposes (CC-BY-NC), and; a waiver of rights to the public domain (CC0). The licences were successfully implemented across GBIF data without significant issues in 2016.

In our view, the open and transparent consultation process employed by GBIF serves as a very useful model for debates on DSI under the CBD and other instruments. Critically, GBIF's experience reveals the importance of pragmatic compromise in recognising and balancing the rights and interests of diverse data providers working with a range of different business models in both developed and developing countries. The smooth implementation of standard open licences across over 2 billion records, including metadata for sequence records from the INSDC, provides a valuable example of what can be achieved by collaboration between developing and developed country partners in identifying suitable ways to share data.

Debates on open access commonly emphasise that publications and data should be both open access and free of charge for the user. This ignores the considerable costs of open access to taxpayers and funding bodies from a business model that requires authors to pay large Article Processing Charges (APCs) to publishing companies. These charges have become a focus of coordinated action by major funding agencies participating in cOAlition S and its Plan S.¹ Coordination between funding agencies around a shared set of principles or plan in the case of the Human Genome Project and more recently cOAlition S and its Plan S has proven to be very powerful in effecting change. Consideration of the costs of open access publications also reveals the significant attention required when introducing change in relation to the costs and wider impacts of fees. For this reason, as in the previous work, we emphasise the importance of modelling potential options on dsi.

A common feature of international policy debates is that specific sectors will seek to establish themselves as exceptions to any proposed policy measures. In debates on digital sequence information it is reasonable to expect that this behaviour will also manifest itself. For example, we might expect that some members of the non-commercial research sector may seek to exempt themselves from any proposed measures on the grounds that it will affect research. However, as recognition of the global biodiversity crisis deepens we might reasonably assert that the time for exceptions is well and truly over. Put bluntly, biodiversity is not free and has to be paid for (Oldham 2020). In accordance with this observation, this paper takes the position that no one is exempt. Everyone, in accordance with their means, must contribute to investments in biodiversity.

If we accept that no one is exempt, the challenge in the case of digital sequence information is to create revenue generation options that do not impose a disproportionate or intolerable burden on any individual participant or sector. To succeed, any measures on revenue generation must be considered to be broadly fair,

¹ See: <https://www.coalition-s.org/>

reasonable and proportionate and directed towards purposes that enjoy broad consensus by the communities involved. The proposal in this paper seeks to achieve this by relying on the power of revenue generation *at scale* across millions of users and tens of thousands of organisations and companies in countries around the world. The proposal focuses on the use of computer cloud based pricing models to charge users fees for the use of the infrastructure that provides access to dsi.

The paper presents an initial experiment to model potential revenue based on the subscription charges for consumer cloud storage such as Google Photos or Apple iCloud to illustrate the potential of this approach. If we assume that there are a low level of 2.8 million users of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure per year who pay 10 cents a day or US\$24 dollars a year, assuming 240 working days a year, the potential yearly revenue would be a modest US\$68 million a year. However, if we take a high estimate of 500 million global users potential revenue rises to US\$12 billion a year. Calculated at a higher level of US\$1 a day or US\$240 per user per year that figure rises to US\$688 million for 2.8 million users and US\$120 billion for 500 million users respectively.

This simple experiment demonstrates that potential revenue from charges against the use of the dsi infrastructure depends on the number of users and the price point for any fees. It also allows us to start asking questions about the willingness to pay of individual users of dsi at levels such as US\$24 or US\$240 per year. We argue that the willingness of users to pay would be heavily dependent on a shared commitment to the purposes for which the fees are charged.

If implemented at scale the cost of revenue generation for biodiversity may be barely noticeable, or regarded as readily tolerable, by the affected communities of users of digital sequence information. The promise of this approach is that it will successfully embed a financial return to biodiversity into policy measures and serve as an example for other processes (Dasgupta 2021).

We argue that the introduction of revenue generation measures will involve a shift towards a *social enterprise* model for the emerging global biodiversity and life science infrastructure. This is very different from the existing donor model and has significant implications for the design of a proposed “global fund.” We argue that the requirement for revenue generation will best be implemented and managed by participating parties on a national level.² We also argue that disbursements from the fund could most efficiently be handled through existing national technical assistance agencies, regional organisations, UN agencies, the GEF and NGOs in accordance with the level of investment required (e.g. national, regional, international). Investments in biodiversity would be made against a mutually agreed *shared roadmap* established between participating parties linked to implementing the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. As such, we argue for a *distributed global biodiversity fund* consisting of a set of national funds with regional and global components. Partnerships between participating parties could be request based and linked to the priorities agreed as part of the shared roadmap.

² We use the expression ‘participating parties’ throughout this paper to refer to governments across the different instruments and processes addressing dsi who choose to participate in the proposed system.

As we will see, considerable work remains in modelling, evaluating and discussing potential revenue generation measures for biodiversity in potential policy measures on digital sequence information. We also anticipate a need for further discussion of the idea of a distributed global biodiversity fund provided in this paper. As an aid to the reader in reflecting on the proposal developed in this paper a 'version zero' draft of the proposal in CBD style language is attached as an Annex.

Finally, the authors would emphasise that we regard the proposals in this paper as converging in various ways with work being conducted in parallel by teams led by Elisa Morgera, notably in connection with a proposed multilateral platform on benefit-sharing, Amber Scholz and Jens Freitag on engagement with the scientific community, the International Indigenous Forum on Biodiversity (IIFB) and Jane Anderson and Maui Hudson in exploring potential options such as biocultural labels for sequence data. The global dialogues series coordinated by the ABS Initiative in collaboration with the CBD Secretariat, with support from South Africa and Norway, are increasingly revealing convergences between Parties to these debates. While many uncertainties and difficulties remain this provides reason for hope that constructive solutions will be found on digital sequence information. This paper is a contribution to that process.

2 Introduction

This paper forms part of work on options to address digital sequence information under the Convention on Biological Diversity and related instruments and processes. The paper consists of three parts:

1. Key findings to date and issues for further exploration (this paper);
2. An annex written in the form of an outline CBD style text proposal to begin exploring what a proposal might look like;
3. An annex table containing an example of one experimental approach to calculating potential cloud computing based revenue from dsi.

This paper is not intended to be a general introduction to digital sequence information and assumes that the reader is already familiar with these debates across the multiple instruments and processes that are considering dsi. The paper is also not concerned with matters of definition or legal interpretation, but does seek to highlight elements of the wider economic and policy context that have either not previously been considered or fully explored in these debates.

The central tension in debates on digital sequence information can be said to be between advocates of open access to digital sequence information and advocates for greater controls over dsi to secure benefit sharing for states based in their sovereign rights over natural resources. This tension is reflected in widely different positions on subjects such as the need to ‘track and trace’ DNA molecules from countries of origin into commercial products or the need for some form of multilateral benefit-sharing mechanism or fund. It is widely recognised that delegations are presently far apart on these and other subjects although areas of convergence are now starting to emerge through the global dialogue process. This poses a challenge for the adoption of the Post 2020 Biodiversity Framework and wider international cooperation on the environment across multiple instruments and processes.

This paper takes a step back from the intricacies of the debate on digital sequence information to explore the broader context in the pursuit of potential solutions and alternative ways of approaching the issues. The focus of this paper is on understanding data sharing and approaches to openness and how these might be linked with approaches to generating monetary investments for biodiversity.

As a starting point this paper is grounded in the principle that biodiversity is not free and must be paid for (Oldham 2020). It assumes that everyone, proportionate to their means, must contribute something. The recently released *The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review* commissioned by the UK argues that conventional approaches to economics have failed to recognise that human economies are embedded in nature and to incorporate biodiversity as natural capital in economic models (Dasgupta 2021). Future approaches must therefore adopt an *embedded approach* that recognises and incorporates biodiversity as a set of natural assets (Dasgupta 2021). In our view this applies to any future measures on digital sequence information.

To date, debates on digital sequence information (genetic sequence data, genomes etc.) have not considered the nature of these resources as a type of asset (Swanson 1995; Vogel 1994; Muller 2015). Approaching digital sequence information as a type of asset allows us to examine the nature of the asset and how value can be realised from this

type of asset. Analysis of this type reveals that in contrast with other types of asset a distinctive feature of genomes is that value can only be realised where the asset is compared and contrasted with assets of the same or a similar type. In short, the value of a genome is realised by sharing the asset and combining it with other assets of the same type.

This is significant for debates on digital sequence information. First, it allows us to understand the importance that the scientific and private sectors place on open access to digital sequence information. It also helps explain the emphasis on sharing and the exponential growth of sequence data in pursuit of new insights and the realisation of value, as the recent pandemic reveals. Second, it assists us in appreciating that approaches to digital sequence information predicated on the assertion of some form of hard control are doomed to fail. Treating this form of asset as a type of gold is to misunderstand the nature of the asset and will prevent the effective realisation of its value. In this situation everyone will lose.

Approaching digital sequence information as an asset also helps us to identify potential solutions. From this perspective what is required is a means through which sovereign states - along with indigenous peoples and local communities - as the holders of rights in relation to assets of this type, can share these assets and realise value in conditions where their contributions are recognised. As sovereigns, we would expect that the providers of the asset would be willing to set basic terms and conditions for the use of the asset but will logically seek to avoid conditions that prevent the realisation of the value of the asset. However, the willingness of sovereigns to engage in sharing requires trust that the basic terms and conditions they set will be respected and that they will receive a share of the value generated from these contributions. Because of the scale required for the realisation of the value of this type of asset it is not logical to expect a direct relationship between the sharing of an asset and benefits. It is logical to expect an *indirect share* of the value generated and this value should be quantifiable and measurable as an element in a trusted system. This suggests the need for some form of vessel, container or mechanism that will capture a portion of value that can be returned for purposes mutually agreed between those sharing the asset. This container or mechanism would need to be constructed in a way that most efficiently allows for the effective disbursement of the value generated to participating parties and could be centralised, decentralised or take a mixed form. The purposes of the container should, in our view, be directed to the investments necessary for the maintenance of the underlying class of assets (biodiversity).

Following this line of reasoning this paper explores options for the practical implementation of such an approach. The paper is organised around overlapping themes rather than distinct sections. We begin by providing a brief background on previous work leading to the present paper.

The main body of the paper focuses on exploring the dimensions of open access. This analysis begins by examining the history of open access in genomics and focuses on how the adoption of the Bermuda Principles during the Human Genome Project transformed the nature of data sharing in the emerging field of genomics. The public domain model for sharing sequence data that emerged from the human genome project has come under challenge over the last decade from the alternative sharing model represented by GISAID.

We then turn to analysis of the rise of the open access movement for scientific publications and scientific data. This involves a description of the definitions of open access followed by analysis of the economic factors involved in the rise of open access publications and the impact of these factors on funding policies, notably under cOAlition S and its Plan S.

Open licences have emerged as a central feature of the modern knowledge economy. The use of open licences is particularly marked in the case of software, scientific research and taxonomic data.³ In the case of scientific research open licences are providing important policy levers in effecting change for funding bodies under cOAlition S and Plan S. In reviewing these developments we argue that existing debates on monitoring and ‘track and trace’ could be constructively reframed to focus on the implementation of the FAIR principles that data be *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable* (FAIR) (Wilkinson et al. 2016). These principles are now widely supported by governments and inform scientific and data policies in Europe and the European Union. In response to the growth of digital data and growing requirements for the governance of data, indigenous peoples and local community organisations and researchers have developed a complementary set of principles called the CARE principles linked to biocultural labels for digital data that merit further discussion and exploration in the context of debates on digital sequence information (Carroll et al. 2020; Anderson and Hudson 2020; Liggins, Hudson, and Anderson 2021).

The Reusable element of the FAIR Principles is directly linked to licences, which set out the terms and conditions of reuse. To date, empirical analysis of trends in the use of licences has been limited. We examine trends in the use of open licences based on data from three cases:

- a) trends in the use of open licences in the software community;
- b) trends in the use of licences for scientific publications;
- c) the application of licences to over 2 billion taxonomic occurrence records at GBIF including the metadata for sequence records.

This analysis reveals that from a European and wider policy perspective, standard licences are a condition for the realisation of the *Reusable* element of the FAIR principles as reflected in EU Directive 2019/1024 on open data, the Horizon 2020 and the new Horizon Europe funding programmes, and the scientific policies of countries such as the United States. Analysis of trends in the use of different types of standard licences demonstrates that where given a choice providers will typically opt for the most liberal licences. Detailed discussion of GBIF’s experience in the introduction of licences provides many valuable insights of relevance to the potential introduction of licences for digital sequence information. GBIF’s experience reveals the importance of recognition and promotion of legal certainty enabled by licences and a pragmatic willingness to give data providers a limited range of choices when making data available for wider use.

³ See for example the Open Definition for open source licences from the Open Knowledge Foundation <https://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>

The diverse strands of open access movements are now converging around the concept of *open science*. On the international level this is reflected in the recent adoption of the *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* as an expression of international consensus between member states on the definition of open science and approaches to open science. The UNESCO recommendation is complemented in important ways by the more specialised *OECD Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data (EASD)* adopted in October 2021. We propose that taken together the two recommendations could prove very useful in identifying important principles for framing the approach to dsi under the CBD and related instruments and useful guidance on practical approaches to implementation.

The paper then moves into a discussion of the economics of information and exploration of the history of the concept of bounded openness. This provides the basis for examination of the rise of *cloud computing* in relation to digital sequence information. Cloud computing involves the use of remote computer infrastructure and services for which fees are normally charged. The analysis reveals that the scale of the transition in policies to promote cloud computing in the United States and Europe has not yet been appreciated in discussions on digital sequence information. The transition to cloud computing in the United States, Europe and beyond will involve a mixed model of partnerships between public and private actors directed towards promoting science at scale while seeking to reduce costs by creating a competitive digital marketplace. This has major, if presently rather opaque, implications for digital sequence information and the publicly funded life science infrastructure that supports it because it implies a transformation in business models.

The key feature of this emerging marketplace is that data itself will be accessible free of charge and will be FAIR compliant but users will pay for storage, processing and data movement (egress) services by the second, minute and hour. These services will be offered by a mix of public and private sector providers. In the case of publicly funded researchers in the United States partnerships with private sector service providers have already been established for services for the Sequence Read Archive (SRA). The situation in Europe is somewhat less clear in the early stages of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) but EU Directive 2019/1024 as well as Horizon 2020 and the new Horizon Europe all suggest to the authors that the costs of cloud services will be reimbursable expenses for researchers. Based on pilots in the United States, the preferred business model for this emerging 'data commons' appears to be a cloud credits system where users (researchers) purchase cloud services at discounted rates through intermediary providers. Commercial users of cloud services for digital sequence information will continue to pay at commercial rates.

We then present an initial experiment to explore whether and how value could be returned to biodiversity by obtaining a portion of cloud service expenditures as a return to biodiversity for investments in maintenance of the asset. Using flat rate pricing models for consumer cloud storage (Google Photos etc.) as a basic guide, the analysis suggests that the return to biodiversity could be significant in the context of growth in the number of users and sequence data and services. However, existing data on the number and characteristics of users can only be described as poor and modelling of potential revenue is highly dependent on the assumptions and constraints that are applied (such as what sequence data is included). This is followed by a brief analysis of emerging efforts by researchers to model the costs of cloud services in genomics

charged at variable rates (e.g. per service). The paper recommends that efforts to model potential revenue for biodiversity from cloud services could proceed by identifying a standardised set of common workflows in genomics that can be run on cloud services. The recent addition of over 1.3 billion GBIF species occurrence records to the Microsoft Planetary Computer may also prove to be very useful for modelling purposes. Engagement with commercial cloud service providers is also recommended to better understand the feasibility and options that may exist for this approach.

A number of potential options for revenue generation have been advanced for digital sequence information including benefit-sharing at the point of commercialisation, royalties linked to patents, biodiversity bonds, biodiversity tokens, a micro-levy, membership fees, subscriptions, blockchain and others (see generally: Vogel 1994; Muller 2015; Morgera, Switzer, and Geelhoed 2020; Oldham 2020; Scholz et al. 2020). This paper argues that, drawing on the experience of the Plant Treaty, the assessment of the feasibility of revenue generation options should involve modelling exercises to project potential revenue and costs as part of a framework approach (see below). This would allow parties to make informed evidence based decisions about the strengths and weaknesses of different approaches in moving forward. Given that other parties may view such an approach as a delay, the inclusion of the “cold start” fund in the framework is recommended to create conditions of confidence. Further considerations regarding the possible form of a mechanism, and the possibility of a decentralised approach, are discussed in the paper.

The paper concludes with an outline of a distributed global biodiversity fund as a contribution to further discussion on the appropriate design of a potential global fund.

3 Background

The paper is based on two assumptions about potential outcomes of debates on digital sequence information:

1. That digital sequence information should remain open access;
2. That quantifiable monetary benefits should be generated for investments in biodiversity.

The 2020 research paper *Digital Sequence Information - Technical Aspects* adopted a Sustainable Social Ecological Systems approach (SES) to the analysis of options to address digital sequence information. The paper adopted the position that biodiversity is not a free good and must be paid for. On that basis any measures on digital sequence information should return tangible and measurable value to biodiversity. The paper argued that three main options existed to address the requirement of open access and quantitative benefits:

1. The use of a set of simple standardised licences for digital sequence information modelled on experience with open source software and creative commons licences. The licences would set out basic terms of use and improve transparency and certainty for providers and users of DSI. In recognition that some Parties to the Nagoya Protocol may choose to apply PIC and MAT to DSI, licences would also need to cover these possibilities;
2. Generating revenue for investment in biodiversity by reconceptualising the life science infrastructure as a form of social enterprise. This would involve introducing cloud computing pricing models for use of the life science infrastructure such as ‘pay as you go’ style subscription charges based on use. An agreed portion of revenue generated would be allocated to ensuring the sustainability of the infrastructure and a portion for investments in biodiversity;
3. The paper argued that the concept of benefit-sharing could be reframed to focus on the promotion of investments in biodiversity. Using the concept of an Earth Investment Fund as a device the paper argued for a cross-instrument framework for investment led by the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) consisting of multiple revenue generating elements that would mix existing and new money. To address issues of scale in global systems the elaboration and implementation of revenue generating elements would be phased and supported by evidence and lessons learned from pilot ‘flagship’ experiments. The framework would remain open to new elements to adapt to changes in science and technology over time (e.g. biodiversity tokens or similar schemes). To create conditions of trust between Parties in implementing such a framework, Parties would make initial financial commitments to a “Cold Start” investment element as a statement of collective intent.⁴ In contrast with existing approaches focusing on a *centralised fund* the paper suggested a *distributed* approach that could involve international, regional and national elements. In the author’s view a distributed approach grounded in action on the national/regional level is more likely to be cost effective and efficient.

⁴ The cold start problem refers to a problem in artificial intelligence where insufficient initial material is available to train a new model to make reliable predictions. The problem can only be overcome by independently generating sufficient initial data to feed into and train the model.

This paper focuses on advancing research on feasibility and costs and benefits of the first two options by examining:

1. Practical experiences in the use of standardised commons and open source licences and their potential application to digital sequence information.
2. Conducting initial experiments to explore and model the costs and benefits of charges for use of the infrastructure with cloud based fees.

We then pull together these strands into an outline for a distributed global biodiversity fund and present a draft “version zero” proposal for a cross-instrument system in the Annex as a basis for possible further discussion.

We begin by examining the history of open access in genomics and the impact and debates around the Bermuda Principles in framing data sharing in genomics.

4 Open Access

4.1 Open Access & Genomics

Figure 1: John Sulston's First Draft of the Bermuda Principles 1996. Courtesy of Richard Myers. <https://dukespace.lib.duke.edu/dspace/handle/10161/7721>

In the discussions on digital sequence information it is easy to gain the impression that open access to sequence data is normal, natural and has a long history in scientific practice. In reality, open sharing of sequence data is relatively recent and has a contested history. This history focuses on the Human Genome Project and the 1996 Bermuda Principles. The Bermuda Principles were agreed at a meeting held in Bermuda in February 1996 and attended by the major centres involved in the Human Genome Project and funding bodies such as the Wellcome Trust, the US NIH and Department of Energy and the European Commission among others. The white board image presented in Figure 1 above of the first draft of these principles enshrined a set of basic principles that have had a major impact on data sharing in genomics.

The principles presented above involve a combination of radical and contested departures from standard scientific practice in data sharing through an emphasis on daily sharing of genomics data and immediate release of finished sequences to public databases. Standard scientific practice prior to these principles was to share data on publication and was often accompanied by significant delays (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018). The second feature of the Bermuda Principles is that sequences should be freely available for both research and development, a framing that refers to non-

commercial and commercial use, with the addition that sequence data should be placed in the public domain. This principle represents a departure from standard practice where genetic data would be kept private in order to allow for analysis, the identification of value and the filing of patents. The balloon that inserts reference to the public domain in Sulston's first draft of the Bermuda Principles is explicitly directed towards placing what would come to be called primary sequence data outside the realm of patents. Finally, and critically, the principles urge funding agencies to promote these data sharing policies.

The Bermuda Principles were later described as “community spirit, with teeth” (Marshall 2001). As we will now see, the spirit enshrined in the principles emerged from a very specific community while the teeth were provided by a combination of threats of exclusion from the Human Genome Project and the policies of funding agencies that required or strongly encouraged compliance with the principles. This provides important insights and lessons for potential measures on digital sequence information. As we will see, the impact of the Bermuda Principles has been far reaching. However, as genomics has expanded a more complex landscape of database access agreements, open and closed access tiers, and delays in release of data to accommodate publication and commercial interests have emerged (Contreras 2011). We discuss these tensions in connection with the INSDC and GISAID below.

The history of data sharing under the Human Genome Project has been extensively explored, in part as a result of the competition between the publicly funded genome project and the privately funded commercial effort led by Craig Venter and Celera. We rely here mainly on the work of Jones et al. 2018 (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018) and Contreras 2011 (Contreras 2011) while *The Gene Wars* by Robert Cook-Deegan is required background reading in understanding the early history of genomics and the human genome project (Cook-Deegan 1994). More recent work by Stephen Hilgartner in *Reordering Life: Knowledge and Control in the Genomics Revolution* provides very valuable analysis of the transformations in data sharing and the governance of scientific knowledge production during the genomics revolution (Hilgartner 2017). Moving beyond the history of the Human Genome Project, Sabina Leonelli provides a sophisticated analysis of the transition to data centrism in biology precipitated by the rise of genomics in *Data-Centric Biology: A Philosophical Study* (Leonelli 2016, 2020).

The principle of daily sharing of data and its public release to what are now INSDC databases, can be traced to the data sharing practices that emerged in the Laboratory of Molecular Biology (LMB) at Cambridge University. In the 1960s and 1970s Sydney Brenner and John Sulston led the early mapping of the nematode worm (*Caenorhabditis elegans*) for which they would subsequently share a Nobel Prize (Sulston and Brenner 1974). In contrast with practices elsewhere, the sharing of data prior to publication became an increasing norm in the *C. elegans* community. By the early 1990s that community encompassed a network of around 150 laboratories in the US, Europe and Japan (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018). Sharing within the *C. elegans* community was conducted through personal contacts and paper, notably newsletters, and increasingly replaced by digital data sharing with the shift from generating physical maps of genes to sequencing (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018).

The establishment of the Sanger Centre (now the Wellcome Sanger Institute) in 1992 under the leadership of John Sulston cemented this approach to data sharing. Jane Rogers, who managed 17 sequencing groups at the Sanger Centre in the 1990s, reported in 2012 that for Sulston rapid sharing of data was regarded as “... a continuation of the hippie culture of freedom” (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018, 22). Cultural practices around sharing genetic data among the *C. elegans* community became the model that was, depending on one’s point of view, agreed or imposed in the Bermuda Principles.

As we will see in more detail in other examples below, the policies of funding organisations have important impacts on scientific practices. The Human Genome Project was formally started in 1990 under grants from the US NIH and DOE. As Stephen Hilgartner has reported, the two major funding bodies for the HGP were the NIH and the Wellcome Trust in the UK who provided nearly 90% of the funding (Hilgartner 2017 cited in Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018). In late 1992, and following earlier work in 1991, the DOE-NIH subcommittee for the project adopted a policy requiring the sharing and public deposit of genome data after a six month period as a condition of support (Human Genome Program 1993).

However, Sulston and collaborators, notably Robert Waterson, would increasingly push for daily or immediate data sharing. At the 1996 Bermuda meeting, Sulston and Waterson tabled a proposal for the immediate release of data (for 1kb contigs as used in the *C. elegans* community) that was subsequently presented, along with the other principles highlighted above, as the consensus outcome of the conference. As Jones et al. 2018 highlight, this consensus could best be described as a “measured consensus” with some participants expressing outrage at these conditions, and it must be noted that some laboratories, even supporters of the Bermuda Principles, never achieved immediate data release in practice (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018).

There were two main objections to immediate data sharing. The first substantive objection related to the quality of the data that would be released. Specifically, participants expressed discomfort at the prospect of “baring their soul on a nightly basis” that would reveal errors to the wider community and possibly lead to colleagues working on bad data (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018, 39). As such, for some participants it was important to be able to make the necessary quality control checks and corrections. A compromise subsequently emerged around the distinction between requirements for unfinished and finished sequences with the nightly releases characterised as prereleases (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018).

A number of researchers involved in the project were reportedly furious about this apparent consensus. Maynard Olson, a leading figure in the Human Genome Project and pioneer of research in yeast genomics, was a supporter of open access but declared that “I do not like manifestos and ‘unanimous’ pronouncements on highly technical issues. Most people are simply being rail-roaded under these circumstances, in response to an unwise conversion of a technical issue into a moral one” (cited in Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018, 41). A dispute on the Bermuda Principles involving Mark Adams and Craig Venter subsequently broke out in the pages of *Science*. Adams and Venter were concerned not with the release of sequence data as such but with the broad brush nature of the requirement that the Bermuda Principles introduced.

“We believe there are substantial reasons why scientists should be cautious about using or releasing data and results that have been neither peer-reviewed nor extensively self-reviewed. Although we do not object to the policy of nightly data release adopted by some genome centers, we do object to having these terms applied across the board to all labs involved in genome research.” (Adams and Venter 1996, 534, see also Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018).

The concerns expressed in this article are mainly focused on quality control in relation to the release of unfinished sequence alongside finished sequences with peer reviewed publications leading to a loss of control over the quality of data and what they presciently described as a “deluge” of information. Instead they proposed that for sequencing projects that could not be completed in a 12 to 18 month period, sequence data should be released to the wider community immediately if they had passed quality control checks and had been annotated (Adams and Venter 1996, 536).

In equally prescient remarks in light of the later emergence of GISAID, the two authors argue that:

“We are concerned that raw or finished sequence data release without accompanying scientific publications will become the new end point of some groups’ contributions to genomics. This could happen intentionally or inadvertently.” (Adams and Venter 1996, 535).

Adams and Venter also express an objection to “... the notion that it is somehow inappropriate for the scientific teams that generate sequence information to extract scientific value from their data before releasing these data to others” (Adams and Venter 1996, 534). With the benefit of hindsight we might be tempted to detect here the later tensions that existed between the public HGP project and the private initiative led by Venter that focused on patents and the commercial potential of sequencing human genome data. Specifically, the emphasis on placing genome data into the public domain that emerges in the Bermuda Principles is a clear and unambiguous response to the controversies over the patenting of DNA that raged in the 1990s and into the early part of the 21st Century (Cook-Deegan 1994). Viewed from this perspective, the immediate release of sequence data was linked to a desire to prevent the patenting of what came to be called primary genomic sequences. This should not be interpreted as opposition to commercial research and patent activity *per se* - as reflected in the final version of the principles which aim “to encourage research and development and to maximize the benefit to society.”

The adoption of the Bermuda Principles, along with later refinements as the HGP progressed, had the important consequence of establishing a set of norms that continue to reverberate in the genomics community with respect to data release and the public domain. In particular, the Wellcome Trust formally adopted the principles as a condition of their grants for the HGP in 1996 and then extended this to all model organism projects under the HGP in 1998. In short, willingness to comply with the Bermuda Principles became a precondition for funding. In the United States the situation was complicated by the existence of the 1980 Bayh-Dole Act that mandates the pursuit of patent protection arising from federally funded research. However, a version of the Principles were incorporated into NIH funding guidance for HGP projects with the warning that “NIH is concerned that patent applications on large blocks of primary

genomic DNA sequence could have a chilling effect on the development of future inventions.” and would be monitoring researchers activity (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018, 53). As a consequence, researchers were put on notice that their funding would be at risk in the absence of compliance.

Outside the United States and the UK other Human Genome Project participants experienced difficulties with implementation of the Bermuda Principles, notably in Germany and Japan. In Germany the policy of the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) originally focused on maintaining privileged access to sequence data to encourage industry participation. However, this approach was dropped for the Human Genome Project following what in effect amounted to a threat of exclusion from the HGP (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018). A similar situation emerged in Japan where some researchers appeared to be complying while others were not, leading to delays in data release that were measured in months and resulted in a warning letter from the HGP leaders. The outcome was a “fuzzy approach” to implementation (Jones, Ankeny, and Cook-Deegan 2018). In France the relatively young French National Sequencing Center (Genoscope) created in 1996, appears to have adhered as best it could, more as a matter of practice than formal policy, and was mainly involved with the Rice Genome Project, sequencing of the puffer fish and the rat genome. As such, the young centre can be said to have responded to the Bermuda Principles by simply incorporating them into their emerging daily routine.

The important point that emerges here is that the Bermuda Principles had teeth in the form of a combination of the threat of public scientific opprobrium, the threat of exclusion from a prestigious project and the formal policies of funding agencies. Increasingly, these once radical policies became part of routine scientific practice and as such came to be considered as *normal*, *the best* and for some powerful actors *the only* approach to data sharing in genomics.

The data sharing policies introduced by the Bermuda Principles were subsequently expanded to other areas of genomics and related fields such as proteomics (the analysis of the protein complement of an organism). Following the completion of the Human Genome Project, the Wellcome Trust organised a Meeting in Fort Lauderdale in January 2003 with 40 participants from a range of organisations including funding agencies, sequencing centres and journals that produced what is now known as the Fort Lauderdale Agreement (Contreras 2011).

The Fort Lauderdale Agreement explicitly extended the Bermuda Principles to other types of genomics projects outside the human genome for what it called Community Resource Projects (CRPs) consisting of “a research project specifically devised and implemented to create a set of data, reagents or other material whose primary utility will be as a resource for the broad scientific community” (cited in Contreras 2011). The Fort Lauderdale Agreement states that:

- “The meeting attendees enthusiastically reaffirmed the 1996 Bermuda Principles, which expressly called for rapid release to the public international DNA sequence databases (GenBank, EMBL, and DDBJ) of sequence assemblies of 2kb or greater by large-scale sequencing efforts and recommended that that agreement be extended to apply to all sequence data, including both the raw traces submitted to the Trace Repositories at NCBI and Ensembl and whole genome shotgun assemblies.

- The attendees recommended that the principle of rapid pre-publication release should apply to other types of data from other large-scale production centers specifically established as ‘community resource projects.’”

Once again, the policies of funding agencies are an important target. The Fort Lauderdale Agreement called upon funding agencies to:

“A.2. require, as a condition of funding, free and unrestricted data release from community resource projects to appropriate central and searchable public databases, and vigorously ensure that this occurs.”

As Jorge Contreras has noted, these policies were rapidly adopted by some of the funding agencies and major sequencing centres (Contreras 2011). As Contreras explores in detail, other projects such as the International HapMap project, to create the haplotype map of the human genome, adopted policies based on the Fort Lauderdale Agreement. Later initiatives such as the Genetic Association Information Network (GAIN) for Genome Wide Association Studies adopted immediate release policies with data deposited in the Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP). However, it is notable that a number of later developments involving human genetic data start to bifurcate the data into public and private access. Under these approaches aggregated data is made publicly accessible while the controlled portion of the data, that may include confidential information, requires permission (Contreras 2011). These arrangements are often accompanied by a requirement for users to sign separate data access agreements (Contreras 2011). Reflecting the concerns expressed by Adams and Venter highlighted above a significant number of policies require data deposit as soon as possible after quality control has been performed.

As Contreras 2011 has argued: “The influence of the Bermuda/Ft. Lauderdale Principles has been lasting and pervasive.” However, subsequent developments, notably in human genomics, have been characterised by growing complexity as the rights of a range of different actors, data providers, data users and others are recognised amid the demands of publication and commercial interests. For our purposes, the history of the Bermuda Principles is revealing both in terms of its impact in normalising data sharing that prioritises the public domain and the lessons that can be learned for dsi debates. We can summarise the key factors behind the success of the Bermuda Principles as follows:

- a) Changes in community practices among a small group who subsequently extended those practices to a wider network (the *C. elegans* community) and then to other research communities (the human genome and model organisms);
- b) The adoption of policies by funding agencies to promote specific practices (data sharing);
- c) The use of peer pressure and the possibility of withdrawal of funding to promote compliance combined with a degree of pragmatic toleration of non-compliance to accommodate different circumstances;
- d) The extension of practices that were adopted for human genome data to other areas of dsi research;

- e) The adoption of this data sharing policy by the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) with limited, if any, apparent public discussion outside its International Advisory Committee (Brunak et al. 2002).

We can now appreciate that what has become the single dominant model for data sharing in genomics is in fact relatively new and was highly contested at the time. As we will now see, the tensions that existed at the time of the Human Genome Project and the adoption of the Bermuda Principles have endured and arguably deepened as efforts have been made to extend this model to a global norm. We now turn to exploration of the policies of the INSDC and the tensions that have emerged around data sharing in connection with GISAID.

4.2 Open Access & the Public Domain

The history of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) consisting of GenBank in the United States, the European Nucleotide Authority (ENA) and the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ) is closely tied up with the history of the Human Genome Project and the Bermuda Principles.

We have seen in the preceding discussion that the triumph of a particular model of data sharing enshrined in the Bermuda Principles is set against a complex background involving scientific competition, intense tensions between public and commercial interests and international cooperation in the pursuit of the landmark sequencing of the human genome and other organisms. It is against this background that INSDC policy needs to be considered.

In 2002 the INSDC published its policy in *Science* (Brunak et al. 2002). This is reproduced below in full from the INSDC website.⁵

1. The INSD has a uniform policy of free and unrestricted access to all of the data records their databases contain. Scientists worldwide can access these records to plan experiments or publish any analysis or critique. Appropriate credit is given by citing the original submission, following the practices of scientists utilizing published scientific literature.
2. The INSD will not attach statements to records that restrict access to the data, limit the use of the information in these records, or prohibit certain types of publications based on these records. Specifically, no use restrictions or licensing requirements will be included in any sequence data records, and no restrictions or licensing fees will be placed on the redistribution or use of the database by any party.
3. All database records submitted to the INSD will remain permanently accessible as part of the scientific record. Corrections of errors and update of the records by authors are welcome and erroneous records may be removed from the next database release, but all will remain permanently accessible by accession number.

⁵ Source: <https://www.insdc.org/policy.html>

4. Submitters are advised that the information displayed on the Web sites maintained by the INSD is fully disclosed to the public. It is the responsibility of the submitters to ascertain that they have the right to submit the data.
5. Beyond limited editorial control and some internal integrity checks (for example, proper use of INSD formats and translation of coding regions specified in CDS entries are verified), the quality and accuracy of the record are the responsibility of the submitting author, not of the database. The databases will work with submitters and users of the database to achieve the best quality resource possible.

In considering these provisions we can immediately detect the legacy of the Bermuda Principles in the emphasis on free and unrestricted access in paragraph 1. Paragraph 2 on restrictions of access or use of data can be said to reflect a solution to the underlying tensions between public and commercial interests that were revealed during the competition to sequence the human genome. These tensions do not simply involve considerations around patents but also data access agreements and copyright.

By way of example, in 2002 Syngenta completed the sequencing of the rice genome (Goff et al. 2002; Oldham 2004). Through its then subsidiary at the Torrey Mesa Research Institute (now closed) the company released the sequence on CD under non-commercial and commercial terms in material transfer agreements (Oldham 2004). The following is an excerpt from these terms.

“The PROVIDER retains all right, title and interest in and to the MATERIAL, including any MATERIAL contained or incorporated in MODIFICATIONS. The MATERIAL, both the primary sequence assembly and the representation thereof, is a copyrighted work of Torrey Mesa Research Institute.”⁶

At the same time, the company also submitted patent applications relating to aspects of the rice genome which resulted in an international campaign led by the ETC Group (Oldham 2004). However, the company subsequently dropped these agreements and contributed its sequence to the public International Rice Genome Sequencing Project which, in line with the Bermuda Principles, made its data publicly available.

This example serves to illustrate the underlying complexity of the background that informs the second provision in the INSDC policy. In particular, organisations involved in sequencing with commercial interests, a category that includes universities, can be said to have been engaged in a process of working out business models and figuring out the appropriate balance between private interest against public release of data.

For the INSDC as an entity, it appears reasonable to argue that amid intense commercial interest, the databases would have been confronted by a complex morass of competing, conflicting and confusing licenses and claims to rights that would have severely constrained its efforts to make sequence data publicly available for wider use. As we will see in detail below, some years later a set of new tools have become available to help solve these types of problems in the modern knowledge economy.

⁶ The agreements remain accessible through the Internet Archive for the Torrey Mesa Research Institute in a Summary of Terms and a Free Public Access Agreement and MTA for commercial entities at <https://bit.ly/3iX6fmF>

The fourth provision of the INSDC policy can be linked to the second in so far that it asserts that it is the responsibility of the submitters to ensure that they have the right to submit the data.

The third and fifth provisions of the INSDC policy can be linked back to the concerns relating to quality control that were expressed by Adams and Venter (among others) about the release of primary sequence data.

INSDC policy can be said to skate over a second issue that is implicit in the second and the fourth provision in relation to rights. That is, who owns the data and has the right to submit it? An answer to this question is provided in regular, normally annual, updates on the INSDC that are published in *Nucleic Acids Research*. A succinct summary of the position on this question as well as the position on the second provision is provided in the 2020 update.

“INSDC policy does not impose upon intellectual property rights. Publication of deposited sequences can be delayed until their journal publication, during which only journal editors and reviewers can access the information. Updates are accepted only from the original data providers so that appropriate recognition or credit can be traced. Thus, INSDC has been long recognized as the reliable framework for sustainably maintaining NSD and associated metadata throughout the scientific community. The framework became a model for the Open Access movement for academic literature (<https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org>), and was also the template of the FAIR principle for promoting Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data (<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>)” (Arita, Karsch-Mizrachi, and Cochrane 2020).

“The INSDC supports deposition and distribution of data from publicly funded science, but does not claim the ownership of data. Data ownership is retained by the submitter. Although deposited data may be reformatted by the INSDC, original data providers retain rights to update records. Intellectual property rights are managed through patents and other measures independently from the INSDC although patented sequences are deposited within the INSDC by national or regional patent offices. The fundamental data-sharing policy of the INSDC was published in 2002 by our advisory board: free and unrestricted access to all of the data records, without use restrictions, licensing requirements, or fees on the distribution or use by any party. Another important principle is that data be permanently accessible as part of the scientific record including all updates. The same policy was adopted as the Bermuda Principles for the Human Genome Project in 1996, and as the Fort Lauderdale Agreement for genome sequencing data in 2003. The policy should not be misinterpreted as open access, where use restriction may apply depending on the licensing terms. The policy was reaffirmed by the advisory board in 2016” (Arita, Karsch-Mizrachi, and Cochrane 2020, references removed).

In considering these statements we can make two main observations. The first of these is that data submitters or providers are assumed to be the owner of the sequence data. The second is the argument that INSDC has served as a model for the open access movement. However, as we move into the second section we observe the relevance of

the Bermuda Principles and Fort Lauderdale Agreement accompanied by an apparent attempt to distance INSDC policy from the concept of open access and its use of licences. This is a new development in the regular updates that may, in our view, reflect two developments in the wider policy landscape for sequence data. The first of these is an emerging discussion on options for open standardised licences in the background debates on digital sequence information under the CBD. However, of greater immediate significance is the tension that has emerged between the INSDC and GISAID in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

4.3 INSDC & GISAID

In the opening to this paper we observed that arguments for anonymous, open and unrestricted access to sequence data as advocated in INSDC policy could be characterised as *the public domain by any other name*. That the term public domain appears in the Bermuda Principles, but does not appear in INSDC policy, may reflect recognition that the public domain is a complicated legal concept when applied across multiple jurisdictions around the world. As we will now see, while INSDC policy may not use the term public domain it may readily be interpreted as a policy that pursues that goal for data submitted to its databases.

GISAID is a platform that was launched in 2008 as a platform for the open access sharing of influenza viruses and was “Created as an alternative to the public domain sharing model.”⁷ GISAID is hosted by Germany and has received support from a variety of European and US funding bodies. In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic GISAID emerged as the leading platform for the sharing of SARS-CoV-2 sequence data (Maxmen 2021a).

GISAID is a direct response to concerns about access and benefit-sharing that arose in the context of the avian influenza virus A subtype H5N1 (commonly called bird flu) outbreak in 2004. In a well documented case, Indonesia stopped sending samples to the WHO global influenza network in 2007. In 2008 an article focusing on the pursuit of mutual trust, transparency and equity in sharing virus data co-authored by the then Indonesian Minister of Health argued that:

“Disease affected countries, which are usually developing countries, provide information and share biological specimens/virus with the WHO system; then pharmaceutical industries of developed countries obtain free access to this information and specimens, produce and patent the products (diagnostics, vaccines, therapeutics or other technologies), and sell them back to the developing countries at unaffordable prices. Although it is general knowledge that this practice has been going on for a long time for other major communicable diseases –not just for avian influenza – the fear of potential pandemic influenza has magnified this gap. Moreover, in Indonesia’s opinion, what has been emphasised by the current global system is merely the responsibilities of developing countries, leaving a big hole in the rights of these nations...” (Endang R Sedyaningsih 2008)

⁷ Source: <https://www.gisaid.org/about-us/history/>

At the launch of GISAID Indonesia agreed to submit its samples and data through the new GISAID platform.⁸ GISAID describes its origins as follows:

“In January 2006, when mainstream media first took notice of human fatalities caused by the deadly bird flu, public access to the latest genetic sequences of highly pathogenic avian influenza e.g. H5N1 was limited and often restricted due to the hesitancy by affected countries to share their information through traditional public domain archives such as EMBL, DDBJ and GenBank.

Public Domain archives, where access and use of data takes place anonymously, neither offered any protection of the owners’ intellectual property rights to the data, or any other valuable incentive to incentivize the sharing of data, such as transparency on the use of data or effective mechanisms that would ensure the acknowledgement of the owners of the virus and recognition of the submitters of the data. Another hurdle responsible for the lack of rapidly sharing influenza data was in part due to the concern of scientists that they were often not credited for their contribution of data, and to no lesser extent, their worry of being ‘scooped’ by those publishing a manuscript first, without their consent.”⁹

Stefan Elbe and Gemma Buckland-Merrett provide a valuable interview based history of GISAID for readers seeking to understand the history of GISAID (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017). The key innovation in addressing the concerns of developing countries was the use of the GISAID terms and conditions as a licence following expert input from legal specialists in licensing in other fields under the leadership of Peter Bogner who had experience in media and licensing (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017). A second important development was a requirement for user registration and validation. We address user registration first.

In considering registration issues it is important to make a distinction between two categories: registration of users and registration of data providers.

INSDC databases do not require registration for users of the public web interface or access to the downloadable archive (FTP archive). As such, users can remain anonymous. As we discuss later in the paper, this appears to be one reason it is difficult to arrive at accurate figures on the number of users of the public interface. INSDC data is also available through a web service which provides programmatic access to its data. NCBI web service tools (Entrez) can be used in a limited way to access data without registration. However, regular users will register with NCBI in order to obtain an access token that authenticates them when using the service. This provides unrestricted access to NCBI data at scale. Requirements for user authentication when using web services (Application Programming Interfaces or APIs) are very widely used as they help prevent malicious attacks and can assist with solving problems because users can be contacted.¹⁰

⁸ Source: <https://www.gisaid.org/references/gisaid-in-the-news/associated-press-2008-05-16/>

⁹ Source: <https://www.gisaid.org/about-us/history/>

¹⁰ As far as we can ascertain the EMBL-EBI webservice (API) does not involve authentication.

The second aspect of registration is when submitting sequence data. EMBL-EBI, NCBI and DDBJ all require registration for those submitting data.¹¹ Important reasons for requiring user accounts for submission will include security, contacting submitters on data curation and reporting. In the main sequence databases, such as GenBank, the details of those submitting such as submitter names and organisation do not appear. However, this data does appear in databases such as BioSamples and BioProjects which focus on metadata linked to sequence data (Oldham 2020).

These technical details are important because while it is true that it is possible to access INSDC databases anonymously, it is also the case that registration exists as a requirement for those who will be submitting data and advantageous for those making regular programmatic use of web services. It is important to highlight that registration is routine practice for most electronic data services and cannot sensibly be characterised as a burden or obstacle to data access. We make this point in the context of the debate on registration that emerged in the CBD public forum on dsi in April 2021.¹²

GISAID requires all users to register and authenticate with its services using their official email and institutional address. The authors were able to register with GISAID without any problems. At the time of registration, GISAID users are required to signal agreement with what are described as the terms of use in a database access agreement (DDA) that is also described as a licence.

The second, and substantive, innovation at GISAID is the licence set out in the terms of use in a database access agreement. The full GISAID access agreement is available at <<https://platform.epicov.org/epi3/frontend#1e543f>>. We will confine ourselves to its key features.

The database access agreement contains two articles. Article 1 requires users to be bound by the access agreement. Article 2 is framed as a licence that grants the user:

“...a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free, non-transferable and revocable license to access and use the GISAID EpiFlu™ Database and Data solely in accordance with this Agreement in all its terms. Without limiting the foregoing, your access to and use of the GISAID EpiFlu™ Database and Data is subject to the following terms and conditions...”

The clauses under Article 2 set out core provisions including that:

- Users grant a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free, and irrevocable license to the data to other users without transferring any other rights or ownership interests in the data;
- A standard clause to not duplicate the database or allow access through other portals except where authorised by GISAID.

¹¹ a) EMBL-EBI: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/sra/#home> b) NCBI: https://account.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?back_url=https%3A//submit.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/subs/genome/ c) DDBJ: https://ddbj.nig.ac.jp/D-way/login_form

¹² See: <https://www.cbd.int/dsi-gr/forum.shtml?threadid=2045> . The concern that arose about registration that emerged in the discussion is what other purposes registration data might be used for.

In a key departure GISAID then introduces requirements relating to attribution and co-authorship and collaborations:

“Art 2. c. Acknowledgement, co-authorship. You may use Data to author, co-author or publish results obtained from your analyses of relevant Data, provided that any such published results acknowledge, as the original source of the Data, the laboratory where the clinical specimen(s) and/or virus isolate(s) were first obtained (**“Originating Laboratory”**) and if applicable, the laboratory where Data have been generated from the isolate(s) and/or specimen(s) received and submitted to the GISAID EpiFlu™ Database. (**“Submitting Laboratory”**). Originating Laboratory and Submitting Laboratory may be in the same country, or in a different country and should be identified by geographic location and address. The listing of any Originating Laboratory or Submitting Laboratory does in no way imply that You, an Authorized User, or any other entity has relinquished its ownership rights, in cases where such rights might exist.”

Art 2. e. Collaboration. You agree to make best efforts to collaborate with representatives of the Originating Laboratory responsible for obtaining the specimen(s) and involve them in such analyses and further research using such Data.

Art 2.g. Intellectual Property. You acknowledge and agree that:

- i. It is your sole responsibility to obtain any additional authorization or license as may be necessary for your use of the Data.
- ii. You agree not to offer or impose any terms on the Data that alter or restrict either the terms of this Agreement or the rights of Authorized Users granted hereunder. Subject only to any pre-existing third party rights on the Data, You acknowledge and agree that all Data will be freely shared among and used by all other Authorized Users.
- iii. You understand that Authorized Users intend to use the Data provided by You for research purposes and/or for the development, testing and dissemination of interventions such as vaccines, diagnostics and therapeutics.”

The remaining provisions of the licence relating to termination, dispute settlement etc. do not appear to be novel. However, we would emphasise that the full agreement merits consideration by legal experts.

In considering these provisions, it is striking that they seek to address some of the criticisms that were originally levelled at the Bermuda Principles, notably that research teams risked being scooped by other research teams using their own data or that teams could in effect be reduced to data providers (Adams and Venter 1996). The GISAID acknowledgement (attribution) provisions seek to address this type of problem. Article 2(e) goes further by requiring “best efforts” in collaboration with originating laboratories. The use of the phrase best efforts has a specific meaning in contract law to the effect that the parties to a contract will do whatever is necessary. However, we would note that the use of this term may vary across legal systems and its interpretation requires legal expertise in terms of the nature of the obligation created in contract law in specific jurisdictions.

In connection with the intellectual property provisions in the GISAID licence, we will see below that one issue with the use of Creative Commons licences is the interpretation of the meaning of non-commercial use. Article 2.g.iii of the GISAID licence avoids this issue by making it explicit that authorised users will use the data for the development of vaccines, diagnostics and therapeutics. For discussions on digital sequence information and benefit-sharing it is equally notable that the licence does not seek to enforce benefit sharing. However, in 2013 the platform was able to mediate tensions that arose between Chinese researchers and Novartis and the J. Craig Venter Institute that was working to develop a new H7N9 vaccine to the reported satisfaction of all parties (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017). In our view, this suggests that the promotion of best efforts, as a contractual obligation, can also have teeth in encouraging conformity with expected community standards. Equally, the availability of a trusted mediator appears to be important for platforms and may complement arguments advanced by Morgera and collaborators (Morgera, Switzer, and Geelhoed 2020).

GISAID has risen to prominence in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. A news article in *Nature* in April 2021 reported that: “More than 1.2 million coronavirus genome sequences from 172 countries and territories” have been shared through GISAID and goes on to explain that: “Several databases for genome sequences exist, but GISAID is by far the most popular for SARS-CoV-2” (Maxmen 2021a). As of October 2021 GISAID contained over 4.1 million SARS-CoV-2 whole genomes.¹³ As this makes clear, an open access resource governed under a licence has succeeded in mobilising data sharing on a critical global issue. In particular, GISAID has succeeded in mobilising data sharing by researchers from developing countries with particularly strong contributions from Africa and Asia (Maxmen 2021a). We would also mention, in light of the discussion below, that nothing in the GISAID licence prevents researchers from submitting to INSDC databases in parallel with GISAID. The main question that arises here is whether incentives exist for researchers to submit to INSDC given the degree of security offered by GISAID.

However, GISAID has not been without controversy. In January 2021 an open letter entitled *Support data sharing for COVID-19* was published on the COVID-19 Data Portal.¹⁴ calling for the removal of “barriers that restrain effective data sharing.” The letter argued that “As much research and healthcare data as possible need to be taken out of silos and stored into an open, connected and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) environment to prepare our healthcare systems for future pandemics, and to unleash the fast flow of research advances into clinical use for the benefit of society.” To achieve this the letter argued that the research community should:

- “Submit raw SARS-CoV-2 data to the databases of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC)
- Submit consensus/assembled SARS-CoV-2 data to the databases of the INSDC

¹³ Source: GISAID Analysis Update 2021-10-26.

¹⁴ Source: <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/support-data-sharing-covid19>

- Provide information relating to the sequenced isolate or sample as part of the sequence submission; a minimum of time and place of isolation/sampling and an isolate/sample identifier should be provided to maximise the value of the sequences
- In cases where scientists have already established submissions to other databases, these submissions should continue in parallel to the INSDC submissions.”

To date the letter has been signed by a reported 778 scientists, 99% of whom are based in Europe, the US and Canada (Maxmen 2021b). This was followed in February 2021 by a news item in *Nature* entitled *Scientists call for fully open sharing of coronavirus genome data* (Noorden 2021). In this news item, Rolf Apweiler, co-director of the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), argued that because GISAID does not allow the public resharing of data, this was “hampering efforts to understand the coronavirus and the rapid rise of new variants” (Noorden 2021). However, from another perspective the article noted that this could be described as a ‘feature not a flaw’ (Noorden 2021). That is, the GISAID approach provides researchers with security to share data that they might otherwise choose not to share if the only available option is *de facto* surrender of their interests to the public domain.

This theme was picked up in a news item in *Nature* in May 2021 entitled *Why some researchers oppose unrestricted sharing of coronavirus genome data* which focused on how researchers from developing countries in particular are pushing back against calls for unrestricted sharing. A key issue that emerged here is *the lack of recognition* of work by developing country researchers that could be regarded simply as raw material for researchers elsewhere. This is then tied to the issue of access to vaccines:

“Imagine Africans working so hard to contribute to a database that’s used to make or update vaccines, and then we don’t get access to the vaccines,”
(Christian Happi, African Centre of Excellence for Genomics of Infectious Diseases in Nigeria cited in Maxmen 2021b)

Looking beyond the major issue of equity in access to vaccines, a key issue that emerges is the negative impacts of unrestricted sharing on the careers of researchers in developing countries who, as with researchers everywhere, depend on publications and the ability to attract funding to advance their careers. Historical precedent also plays a role here. Thus, as the *Nature* news item highlights, during the 2014-2016 Ebola outbreak in Guinea, a senior scientist discovered that all Ebola samples were being shipped out of the country where they became the focus of research by others while Guinea continues to lack sequencing capacity (Maxmen 2021b). Responses on this issue have also given rise to allegations in the public press that “a neocolonial mentality has long permeated the scientific community” (Maxmen 2021b). This exposes a key weakness for public domain models because these models are predicated on abstract promises of benefits in return, in effect, for surrendering any rights or interest in data. In the process, data providers lose any opportunity to be involved in discussions on the forms that such benefits might take and who gets to receive those benefits in circumstances where others are able to receive credit and other more material benefits. From this perspective it is not surprising that researchers may decide that the public domain model has little to offer them and may indeed be contrary to their best interests.

In closing this discussion we can observe a growing tension between organisations and researchers who advocate anonymous unrestricted free access to genetic sequence data and initiatives that seek to use licensing terms to promote particular forms of sharing and collaborations between diverse scientific communities around the world. That is, to promote particular forms of social and economic relations around the key issues of addressing influenza and coronavirus outbreaks. Advocates of open access (as anonymous, unrestricted free access) commonly argue that licence or other provisions will restrict or limit sharing and thus limit scientific research. However, this fails to recognise that researchers are generally not obliged to share their data except where they are submitting for publication where validation is required. The attempt to impose a set of principles that were established in specific circumstances as *de facto global norms* fails to recognise the realities of life for these wider communities and risks preventing the sharing of data on urgent issues such as the emergence of new COVID-19 variants. This is not an argument against public domain models, but rather suggests that a single model is unlikely to recognise and serve the interests of diverse communities.

Finally, this example also highlights the importance of the use of terms in this debate among advocates of open access. For some participants in this debate ‘open’ refers in practical effect, but not terminology, to the surrender of any rights or interests over sequence data to the public domain as originally formulated in the Bermuda Principles. In contrast, for other advocates of open access the use of license terms and conditions creates the foundation for sharing. This latter approach is closer to the open source movement in software development discussed below. GISAID has chosen to adopt an approach that is open to anyone who is willing to accept its terms and conditions and in effect has created a single closed or bounded commons based on its licence provisions. As we will see below, in other situations organisations such as GBIF have chosen to use a small set of licences in response to the diverse needs and interests of their communities. In short, to provide data providers with a set of mutually agreed choices on how to make their data available in a way that works for the diverse members of their communities in an “open commons” approach.

This section has explored the history of data sharing and open access in the field of genomics. As this has revealed, there are significant tensions between those who otherwise have a shared and often passionate commitment to open science. In practice, these tensions reflect the diversity of interests within the scientific community. This diversity is also reflected in the *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* that offers the following definition in Article 6:

“6. For the purpose of this Recommendation, **open science** is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.” (Document 41/C22)

The preceding discussion suggests that there is a considerable danger in assuming that existing arrangements constitute a form of *agreed settlement* on the sharing of digital sequence information. The challenge for Parties and member states of the various instruments and processes that are debating dsi is recognising the strengths and weaknesses of existing data sharing models and constructing a settlement that recognises and accommodates the range of different interests.

The history of data sharing in genomics is one of a series of movements that form part of what can be described as a drive to openness in multiple fields. In the following sections we pull together inter-related strands to identify the key milestones, tools, trends and issues involved in this drive to openness. This in turn allows us to turn to the main features of emerging international recommendations on open science and data sharing and their implications for debates on digital sequence information.

4.4 The Rise of Open Access

In this section we discuss the rise of the open access movement and the main milestones in the definition of open access. The history of open access can be said to involve three main strands arising from genomics, software and scholarly publications that have mutually informed each other in various ways (Suber 2012). The key milestones can be briefly summarised as follows:

- The rise of free software (freeware) in the 1980s and the subsequent creation of a free software movement in 1983 oriented around the General Public Licence (GPL) for the GNU operating system and Free Software Foundation (1985). The GPL creatively exploited the flexibilities of copyright law to require modifications of software source code to share modifications on exactly the same terms (share alike);
- The rise of the open source software movement from 1998 onwards in response to the perceived limitations of the share alike model, the creation of the non-profit Open Source Initiative and subsequent development of a suite of open source licences that must meet the criteria set out in the Open Source Definition.¹⁵ The first list of licences meeting the definition was published in 1999;¹⁶
- The Bermuda Principles (1996) and the Fort Lauderdale Agreement (2003) focusing originally on the human genome and subsequently expanded to other organisms (see above);
- The emergence of self-archiving of preprints of scientific publications in the early 1990s and formalisation of definitions of open access through:
 - The Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002) and the Budapest Declaration (2003);

¹⁵ Source: The Open Source Definition. <https://opensource.org/osd>

¹⁶ The original list of approved licences is available at: <http://web.archive.org/web/20000815055529/http://www.opensource.org/licenses/>

- The Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing (2003);
- The Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities (2003);
- The creation of the non-profit Creative Commons (2001) with support from the Center for the Public Domain followed by the release of a set of copyright based licences in December 2002;
- The increasing adoption of open access and open data policies by funding bodies including coordination and formalisation through the creation of an alliance of funding agencies led by the European Commission and European Research Council called cOAlition S in 2018 and implementation of the Plan S roadmap to require open licensing and drive down costs;
- Adoption of EU Directive 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information and the incorporation of requirements for open access, including reimbursement of costs, in a pilot phase of the Horizon 2020 research programme and as a formal requirement of the new Horizon Europe programme;
- The adoption in October 2021 of the *OECD Recommendation of the Council on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data* (OECD 2021);
- The growing convergence of multiple strands of open access policy and practice around the concept of open science with the *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*, adopted in November 2021, representing the present apex of international policy development on open science.

As we discuss below, the rise of the open access and open source movements is widely seen as a response to the increased strengthening of intellectual property rights or ‘enclosures’ from the 1990s onwards across multiple fields (Boyle 2003; May 2015). In practical terms the key innovations behind open access have their origins with the free and open source software movement (FOSS). The free and open source software movement was the first area of science and innovation to recognise and exploit the possibilities of copyright law to introduce a range of highly successful ‘open’ licences that power the modern information economy. Developments in software subsequently informed the expansion of the use of copyright based ‘open’ licencing models to scientific publications and data, notably through the Creative Commons suite of licences. We will focus here on open access and scientific publications.

4.4.1 *Scientific Publications and Open Access*

Scientific publication has historically been organised around books, letters and the journals published by scholarly societies and universities. In the 20th Century, journals became the dominant means of scholarly communication in many disciplines. After the Second World War, the rights to the journals created by scholarly societies were increasingly acquired by commercial companies (Bergstrom et al. 2014; Stuart, Ben, and Michelle 2014). By the 1990s, journal articles produced by commercial publishers accounted for around 40% of journal outputs in the United States (Tenopir and King 1997; Larivière, Haustein, and Mongeon 2015).

A key feature of the increasing commercial share of journal publications was a practice whereby authors published articles free of charge but assigned copyright over their work to the journal or journal owners. The owners of journals typically then charged institutions and individuals subscription fees for print editions of journals. From the mid-1990s onwards, scholarly publication increasingly became digitised with the pdf (portable document format) as the main format for dissemination. The rise of electronic formats reduced costs for publishing houses but also gave rise to new revenue streams such as the ability to ‘rent’ digital articles to readers for set periods (such as 24 hours) in return for a fee.

It is important to appreciate the scale of commercial influence in scientific publishing. By the mid-2000s, five publishing companies accounted for 50% of journal publications rising to 53% in 2013 with three publishing houses accounting for 47% of papers (Larivière, Haustein, and Mongeon 2015). The growing consolidation of the share of papers by a small number of companies in this period arose primarily from a combination of the creation of new journals and the acquisition of journal titles (Larivière, Haustein, and Mongeon 2015).

The rise of what came to be called the open access movement is a response to the consequences of growing market dominance for the costs of access to scientific knowledge in two areas: the cost for individual access and, in particular, the growing cost of institutional journal subscriptions. We consider these costs in the next section.

The history of the rise of the open access movement in scientific publications can be traced in various ways. However, there is widespread agreement that the creation of the arXiv preprint server in 1991 at Los Alamos, for papers in Physics was a key development (Warner 2001).¹⁷ ArXiv became a primary example of a model known as “self archiving” whereby researchers deposit a copy of a pre-peer review version of paper. Rapid access to the latest research, whether peer reviewed or not, is particularly important in some disciplines such as Physics. ArXiv subsequently expanded coverage to mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical engineering and systems science, and economics. At the time of writing, arXiv provides access to over 1.8 million papers free of charge. The arXiv approach was later expanded to biology through bioRxiv and the social sciences through the SocArXiv preprint services. The bioRxiv service is particularly popular in biology and contains over 115,000 freely accessible preprints. BioRxiv became an important venue for the rapid dissemination of preprints on Covid-19 during the pandemic.

As with open source software and the Open Source Definition, a second important development involved mobilisations around the *definition* of open access. Three events are significant here.

The Budapest Open Access Initiative in 2002 produced the *Budapest Declaration* which defined open access to the scientific literature as follows:

“By ‘open access’ to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass

¹⁷ See: <https://arxiv.org/>

them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. The only constraint on reproduction and distribution, and the only role for copyright in this domain, should be to give authors control over the integrity of their work and the right to be properly acknowledged and cited.”¹⁸

The *Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing*, arising from a meeting held at the Howard Hughes Medical Institute in April 2003, added the following provisions to the definition of open access.

“An Open Access Publication is one that meets the following two conditions:

The author(s) and copyright holder(s) grant(s) to all users a free, irrevocable, worldwide, perpetual right of access to, and a license to copy, use, distribute, transmit and display the work publicly and to make and distribute derivative works, in any digital medium for any responsible purpose, subject to proper attribution of authorship, as well as the right to make small numbers of printed copies for their personal use.

A complete version of the work and all supplemental materials, including a copy of the permission as stated above, in a suitable standard electronic format is deposited immediately upon initial publication in at least one online repository that is supported by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency, or other well-established organization that seeks to enable open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability, and long-term archiving (for the biomedical sciences, PubMed Central is such a repository).

Notes:

1. Open access is a property of individual works, not necessarily journals or publishers
2. Community standards, rather than copyright law, will continue to provide the mechanism for enforcement of proper attribution and responsible use of the published work, as they do now.”

This was followed in October 2003 by the *Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities*. The Berlin Declaration sharpened the emerging definitions provided above.

“Open access contributions must satisfy two conditions: The author(s) and right holder(s) of such contributions grant(s) to all users a free, irrevocable, worldwide, right of access to, and a license to copy, use, distribute, transmit and display the work publicly and to make and distribute derivative works, in any digital medium for any responsible purpose, subject to proper attribution of authorship (community standards, will continue to provide the mechanism for enforcement of proper attribution and responsible use of the published work, as they do now), as well as the right to make small numbers of printed copies for their personal use.

¹⁸ Source: The Budapest Open Access Initiative <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>

A complete version of the work and all supplemental materials, including a copy of the permission as stated above, in an appropriate standard electronic format is deposited (and thus published) in at least one online repository using suitable technical standards (such as the Open Archive definitions) that is supported and maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency, or other well-established organization that seeks to enable open access, unrestricted distribution, inter operability, and long-term archiving.”

From this we can observe that the essential conditions of open access are:

- Publications are accessible free of charge to users;
- A licence (also described as “the permission”);
- Attribution;
- The complete copy is made available, including supplementary material and the permission (licence).

In considering these developments, the ability to provide an easy to understand definition of the subject matter has proven to be an important element in mobilising support around the idea of open access.

The concept of open access has subsequently been extended to movements for open data and open science. While there is no single agreed definition of open data, one summary of open data is as follows:

“Open means **anyone** can **freely access, use, modify, and share** for **any purpose** (subject, at most, to requirements that preserve provenance and openness).”¹⁹

This summary is supported by a more detailed definition, modelled on the Open Source Definition for software. The open data definition was developed by the Open Knowledge Foundation, an NGO established in Cambridge in 2004, that serves as the host for what it calls the Open Definition 2.1 (first circulated in 2005).²⁰ We would note that definitions of what open data should, or shouldn’t be, cannot be described as settled and may be open to competing understandings. Arriving at a definition of openness that enjoys a broad consensus in a particular domain can be said to be an important component in the success or failure of movements towards openness.

Wider policy developments on open access and the concept of open science will be considered in more detail below. However, the role of funding agencies has been critical in the promotion of open access. In the United States in 2004 the National Institutes of Health adopted the NIH Public Access policy that requires all researchers funded by NIH to make peer reviewed versions of publications available in the PubMed Central database within 12 months of publication. Within the EU and other European countries, the promotion of open access has been adopted by many funding bodies while in 2019

¹⁹ Source: Open Knowledge Foundation, Open Definition <https://opendefinition.org/>

²⁰ Source: Open Knowledge Foundation, Open Definition <https://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>

the EU adopted the Open Data Directive (EU Directive 2019/1024) based on earlier work on public sector information initiated in 2003.

In debates on open access and definitional exercises it is commonly argued that research publications or data should be made freely accessible to users. This can easily disguise the significant costs behind open access. A key driver in the promotion of open access on the policy level has been increasing attention to the costs associated with commercial journal subscriptions and the Article Processing Charge models that have come to dominate open access business models over the last decade. We now turn to the costs of open access.

4.5 The Costs of Open Access

In debates on digital sequence information, the scientific community has repeatedly and consistently emphasised the importance of open access to dsi. Many countries around the world, including the European Union, now formally require or support open access to scientific publications. In the Horizon Europe research programme, following initial pilots under Horizon 2020, open access now extends to the promotion of open data. In the context of the dramatic growth of digital data and the rise of the digital economy, many countries and the European Union now formally mandate or support the FAIR Principles that data be *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)* (Wilkinson et al. 2016).²¹

As we have seen above, the emphasis in existing debates on open access can readily give rise to the impression that open access is somehow a longstanding, normal or natural state of affairs in science. We might also gain the impression that open access and free are synonyms. As we will now see, the ‘free’ in the promotion of open access relates to free access for users and disguises the reality that open access is not free of cost. At the same time, open access for scientific publications is not free of obligations but is normally enabled by terms and conditions set out in licences.

In connection with cost, the open access movement arose in response to a model of scientific publication where authors transferred copyright to journal publishers as a condition of publication. In the late 20th Century, consolidation of ownership of scientific journals in what has been called an “oligopoly” led to escalating costs of journal subscription charges for universities and funding bodies as well as the phenomenon of “pay per view” for individual scientific publications (Larivière, Haustein, and Mongeon 2015). This is widely regarded as having created a perverse situation in which researchers and the public are expected to pay to access work that was funded by taxpayers at levels far above the marginal cost of production to publishers.

The open access response to this problem was a change of business model for scientific publications. Under the new model, exemplified by the Public Library of Science (PLOS), the author pays the cost of scientific publication (e.g. US\$1350) in the form of an Article Processing Charge (APC) and makes the publication openly available under a copyright

²¹ See: The Fair Principles <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

based Creative Commons or similar publisher licence.²² As of early 2021, just over 109 million journal articles were listed in the Lens non-profit open access database. Of these, 30.1 million were open access under some form of licence.²³ In the field of biology, a total of 10 million journal articles were recorded between 1950 to February 2021 with over 3.9 million classified as open access.²⁴ This is also the field where the bulk of research publications linked to sequences will be located. From this perspective, open access publication can be regarded as a major and growing success.

A 2018 review of the Article Processing Charges (APCs) across over 14 thousand journals revealed that charges are highly skewed (e.g. from zero to US\$5000 in high prestige journals) (Morrison 2018). The most frequently occurring charge (mode) was US\$1,780 per article with the mid-point (median) charge at US\$750 per article. If extrapolated across millions of open access publications it can be readily appreciated that the sums involved are likely to amount to billions of dollars. For example, in crude terms, at the mid-point cost of US\$750 the nearly 3.9 million open access Biology articles mentioned above would cost US\$2.9 billion rising to US\$6.9 billion for the most frequent charge of US\$1,780.

Real world expenditure on these charges is increasingly being compiled by individual funding bodies and research institutions and made publicly available for analysis through the Open APC Initiative at Bielefeld University in Germany.²⁵ The total recorded expenditure for APC payments between 2005 and October 2021, reported by 326 institutions for 139,134 open access articles, was 233.6 million Euro. This represents only a very partial view of total global expenditure on publication charges for open access publications. Figure 2 displays a summary of expenditure for 2020 for ten organisations contributing to the Open APC Initiative.

²² PLOS is a pioneer of open access scientific publications and will waive the author publication charge on request.

²³ For the latest data from the Lens follow this link <https://bit.ly/3x6tno3>

²⁴ For the latest data follow this link: <https://bit.ly/3Dp00z9> . Note that this refers to publications listed in Microsoft Academic Graph under Biology as the field of study.

²⁵ Source: Open APC Initiative: Datasets on fee-based Open Access publishing, Bielefeld University Library <https://github.com/openapc>

Institution	Total (euro)	Articles	Mean	Standard deviation
Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	1,880,307	832	2,260	1,152
Qatar National Library	1,730,063	885	1,955	825
INSERM	1,728,098	761	2,271	962
FWF - Austrian Science Fund	1,302,069	682	1,909	794
Karolinska Institutet	1,144,115	496	2,307	945
Lund University	1,039,324	559	1,859	743
Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin	983,030	553	1,778	428
Uppsala University	724,626	349	2,076	1,097
University of Debrecen	701,723	334	2,101	964
Magdeburg U	673,877	335	2,012	603

Figure 2: Open APC Charges 2020

The costs of open access publications are generally met through block grants from funding bodies to institutions, as part of individual research grants, or directly by the researcher. The promotion of open access and reimbursement of publication costs was introduced into the European Horizon 2020 programme and has been enhanced in the new European Horizon Europe programme (2021-2027).²⁶ In the context of the promotion of open data, the costs of deposit of data with repositories is now a reimbursable cost. As this suggests, established means exist for reimbursing research costs associated with open access. As we will see in the case of cloud computing, this increasingly extends to meeting costs either directly in research grants or using cloud credits or vouchers.

Data on open access publications is relevant to debates on digital sequence information for two reasons. First, it reveals that the emphasis on “free” disguises the economic reality of a business model that relies on willingness to pay publication costs charges that, in the digital era, are likely to be far beyond the cost of production. In recognition of the lack of transparency around these pricing practices, in 2018 a coalition of major funding bodies including the European Commission and the European Research Council

²⁶ A fact sheet on Horizon Europe support for Open Science prepared by the European Commission is available at <https://bit.ly/3zR5t1x>.

created Coalition S and a plan known as Plan S.²⁷ Plan S contains a set of commitments to open access that national funding bodies agree to implement within set time periods. For example, funding bodies have committed to only funding publications in truly open access journals, requiring that publications are FAIR and that APC pricing is transparent in relation to costs.

Coalition S is an example of coordinated action across multiple funding bodies to effect change organised around a shared plan.²⁸ Funding bodies participating in Plan S also extend beyond national funding bodies and include the World Health Organization, the Special Programme for Research and Training in Tropical Diseases (TDR) operated by UNICEF, UNDP, the World Bank and WHO, and private funders such as the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.²⁹

Coalition S and Plan S are significant for debates on the potential form and elements of a benefit-sharing mechanism for dsi because this initiative suggests that in reality a great deal could be achieved through the promotion of coordination between funding agencies around a common agreed roadmap with clear requirements without creating new institutions (Oldham 2020; Oldham et al. 2014).

Second, digital sequence information is an important subset of scientific knowledge production. The open access movement was originally directed towards tackling the negative impacts of a subscription based “paywall” model on research budgets and its wider impacts on science, society and the economy. The open access movement, led by funding bodies, was then obliged to start tackling the widely varying costs of the author Article Processing Charge (APC) model that was introduced by publishers as an alternative. This suggests that, as far as possible, it will be important to model the potential costs and benefits of any measures proposed for digital sequence information. Specifically, rather than adopting an approach that enshrines options in stone, or its black letter legal equivalent, it will be important to create a framework that is flexible enough to permit experimentation and evidence based testing of innovative approaches to the generation of revenue to return to biodiversity (Oldham 2020). We return to this point in the conclusion.

²⁷ Source: Coalition S <https://www.coalition-s.org/>

²⁸ Plan S Price and Service Transparency Frameworks: <https://www.coalition-s.org/price-and-service-transparency-frameworks/>

²⁹ For information on funding bodies participating in Coalitions S see: <https://www.coalition-s.org/organisations/>

4.6 Open Access & Licences

Open access scientific publications are predicated on the use of licences setting out the terms and conditions of use. This approach is increasingly being extended to scientific data as part of the implementation of the FAIR principles.

The most widely used licences for scientific publications are copyright based Creative Commons licences <<https://creativecommons.org/>>. These consist of a set of interoperable licences setting out conditions of use. The most widely used of these licences are:

- By Attribution (CC-BY). Any use permitted including commercial use provided that attribution is provided;
- Non-commercial (CC-BY-NC). Any non-commercial use is permitted subject to attribution. Non-commercial “means not primarily intended for or directed towards commercial advantage or monetary compensation” (CC-BY-NC International version 4.0);
- Share Alike (CC-BY-SA). The user must share any modifications on the same terms as the original work. This is a “copyleft” licence;
- No Derivative Works (ND). Used in combination with the above to specify that no derivative works may be created (not compatible with Share Alike);
- Public Domain (CC0). An explicit waiver of the rights conferred by copyright and commitment of a work to the public domain. Technically this is not a licence but is listed with CC licences.

The non-profit Creative Commons organisation has estimated that over 1.6 billion items are now covered by the licences (and this is likely to be conservative). In the field of software a set of distinct open source licences that meet the Open Source Definition are also widely used. These include the highly permissive MIT licence, the permissive Apache 2 licence and a set of share-alike licences in the General Public Licence (GPL) family of licences.

In order to improve understanding of the implications of the potential application of standard licences to digital sequence information we examined:

1. The licences associated with 30 million open access journal articles and 3.5 million open access scientific publications for Biology;
2. The adoption of Creative Commons licences by the Global Biodiversity Facility from 2016 onwards and their application to what is now over 2 billion taxonomic occurrence records including over 7 million records linked to genetic sequences;
3. Open source software licences in use on the popular GitHub open source software development platform.

Our aim in examining this data was to address the following questions:

1. What licences have proved to be the most popular over time?
2. What processes have been used to introduce licences within a community (e.g. GBIF)?

3. What insights can be gained for the possible adoption of licences for digital sequence information?

For the sake of brevity we summarise the main findings below rather than presenting a detailed account for each of the three case studies.

4.6.1 Trends in the Use of Open Licences

In order to answer the question “What licences have proved to be the most popular over time?” we will present the available data for each of the three domains: open source software, scientific publications and taxonomic data.

4.6.1.1 Open Source Software

In the case of open source software licences the highly permissive MIT licence was the most popular licence listed on the popular online software development platform GitHub.³⁰ Figure 3 displays overall counts of the top licences for GitHub repositories for the period 2010 to 2020 (a repository is where software code is shared).³¹

licence	total
MIT	6,256,741
GNU General Public License family	1,838,461
Apache license 2.0	1,510,522
GNU General Public License v3.0	1,426,353
GNU General Public License v2.0	412,105
BSD 3-clause "New" or "Revised" license	203,275
The Unlicense	162,168
GNU Lesser General Public License family	120,352
GNU Affero General Public License v3.0	111,969
Creative Commons license family	96,862

Figure 3: Top Licences in Use Across GitHub Software Repositories

Figure 4 shows trends over time for the top three licences for software on GitHub consisting of the MIT licence, the GPL family and the Apache 2 licence.

³⁰ MIT Licence: <https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>

³¹ Source code available in Oldham, P 2021 GitHub Licence Data. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6557388

Figure 4: Trends for Popular Licences for Software Repositories on GitHub

Figure 4 reveals what proves to be a major trend in the use of licences across the spectrum of software, publications and taxonomic data. That is, the most liberal licences are typically the most popular. In other cases, communities that are familiar with a specific licence, such as the share alike General Public Licence (GPL family), will stay with that licence where it meets their purposes.

The use of licences for open source software is more mature than the other examples discussed below. One insight from open source software licences is that communities can form around the use of specific licences for software, notably software with ‘share alike’ provisions. A second insight, discussed in more detail below, is that new entrants into software development appear to be highly likely to copy the behaviour of existing users and may prefer licences with the simplest terms. While speculative in the absence of survey data, we suspect that this helps explain the rapid growth of the MIT licence. The MIT licence consists of a licence and a statement that the software is provided without warranty or liability. The licence element is as follows.

“Permission is hereby granted, free of charge, to any person obtaining a copy of this software and associated documentation files (the ‘Software’), to deal in the Software without restriction, including without limitation the rights to use, copy, modify, merge, publish, distribute, sublicense, and/or sell copies of the

Software, and to permit persons to whom the Software is furnished to do so, subject to the following conditions:

The above copyright notice and this permission notice shall be included in all copies or substantial portions of the Software.”³²

A third insight in the case of data on licences on the GitHub platform is that licences are designed for specific purposes. Thus, it is widely recognised that Creative Commons licences are not designed for software. While software developers are at liberty to use Creative Commons licences, in our experience the presence of these licences on GitHub in Figure 3 is more likely to reflect the growing use of the platform for the publication of blogs, websites, electronic books and other materials that are not software.

Finally, as discussed in earlier work, the key reason that the use of licences has been actively promoted on the GitHub platform is because adding a clear licence to a repository sends a signal to users on the terms and conditions of use of code (Oldham 2020). In the absence of a licence a sensible user will assume that all rights remain reserved under copyright and they will not include unlicensed libraries or code in their own products or services. This is particularly important for companies who may be exposed to legal claims for breach of copyright. Companies will typically check the licences of libraries they propose to use in products (known as dependencies) as part of their due diligence procedures.

4.6.1.2 Scientific Publications

The history of open access publications can be divided into two main phases. The first phase involved the designation of the types of open access publication by colour as part of the implementation of the Budapest Open Access Initiative:

- Gold: Published in an open access journal indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ);
- Green: A free copy is available in an open access repository with paid access on a publishers site;
- Hybrid: Free under an open licence in a paid access journal;
- Bronze: Free to read on a publishers site but lacks a clearly identifiable licence (Piwowar et al. 2018).

In the second and overlapping phase, the terms and conditions of access to publications have increasingly been clarified using Creative Commons licences (Gomez-Diaz and Recio 2020). The key factor behind this transition is that colours describe the type of repository rather than the permitted uses of an article. For example, while a publication listed on a “bronze” site may be free for a user to read this does not extend to any other use right, such as copying the publication or data mining. Licences have become increasingly important in clarifying these rights.

To date, most quantitative analysis has focused on mapping trends using the colour scheme for open access publications rather than the use of licences (Piwowar et al.

³² Source: Open Source Initiative, The MIT License: <https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>

2018). To address this issue we used the Lens database of over 239 million scientific publications, including licences, to extract available data on licences using the Lens Application Programming Interface (API) (Oldham and Kindness 2021a). Across 31 million open access journal articles we discovered that in all cases, and by a very considerable margin, the most widely used licences were the most liberal, with 5.6 million articles under CC-BY. To narrow the focus to subjects closer to digital sequence information, we retrieved 3.5 million open access journal articles in the field of Biology published between 1990 and 2020. Figure 5 displays trends in the use of licences for 1.9 million open access Biology journal articles with a licence between 1990 and 2020.

Figure 5: Licence Trends for Journal Articles in Biology (Top 5)

In considering Figure 5 it is clear that the most liberal form of licence (CC-BY or attribution only) is the most popular in Biology followed by CC-BY-NC-ND (non-commercial, no derivative works) and CC-BY-NC (non-commercial). As discussed in connection with the provisions of Plan S below, we strongly suspect, but cannot presently confirm, that the prominence of the non-commercial and no-derivative works licence reflects a requirement by commercial publishing houses to use this very restrictive licence for the final peer-reviewed versions of articles.³³

What is important in this data is that the use of licences is a strong and growing feature of publications that include digital sequence information. The data presented above reveals that it is increasingly straightforward to automate the retrieval of licence data in

³³ The Elsevier sharing policy requires the use of the CC-BY-NC-ND licence for accepted manuscripts, see <https://www.elsevier.com/about/policies/sharing>. We would also observe that one feature of open access publications is the presence of multiple versions of a work under a licence. Thus, an author may publish a pre-print (pre peer review version) under one licence (e.g. CC-BY) while the post peer review version may appear under another licence (e.g. CC-BY-NC-ND). Multi-licensed work is a smaller subset of the data and is not included above pending further research (Oldham and Kindness 2021a).

order to develop indicators to inform policy deliberations. As we will see below in connection with Plan S, the visibility of licence data makes it possible to target policy measures to discourage particular types of behaviour in the pursuit of policy objectives.

4.6.1.3 Taxonomic Data (GBIF)

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is an international network created by governments to provide open access to taxonomic data on a global level. As we will discuss in more detail below, in 2016 GBIF transitioned from the use of hundreds of terms and conditions set by publishers to the use of three Creative Commons licences. Figure 6 displays a summary of licences for species occurrence records at GBIF in September 2021 across what was then over 1.8 billion species occurrence records (Oldham and Kindness 2021b).

license	records
CC0	239,680,175
CC-BY	1,334,930,003
CC-BY-NC	320,841,138
Total	1,895,451,316

Figure 6: GBIF Occurrence Records by CC Licence Type

Figure 6 reveals that at the present time the dominant licence is CC-BY for attribution (any use) followed by Non-commercial use. Figure 7 displays cumulative trends for the licences for species occurrence records across GBIF data.

Figure 7: Overall Occurrence Records by Licence Type

In considering trends in species occurrence records at GBIF it is important to emphasise that these vary between kingdoms and by classes of organism (e.g. birds of class Aves).

Figure 8 breaks out the cumulative counts by individual kingdom. Note that because each set contains very different quantities of records, they each have their own y axis values.

Figure 8: GBIF Occurrence Records by Kingdom and Licence Type

In considering Figure 8 we can see an important distinction between the animals data, where the use of CC-BY is dominant and the data for Plants where the data is more evenly distributed between attribution only (CC-BY), non-commercial (CC-BY-NC) and the public domain waiver (CC0). This type of analysis could as necessary be conducted on lower levels such as the genus or species level or filtered by country records.

The important point here is that it is possible to filter licence data in a wide variety of ways and to develop indicators. On the GBIF website it is now a trivial matter to search for occurrences at different levels and different geographic locations and filter the data by the licence type before downloading it. This is illustrated in Figure 9 for Baobab where a significant number of the records (939) have been contributed by amateur naturalists or citizen scientists through the iNaturalist network (see below).

Figure 9: *Adansonia digitata* (Baobab) records by licence type

More recently, and building on earlier work by the European Nucleotide Authority (ENA), the INSDC now publishes a number of metadata datasets linked to sequences through GBIF. The datasets are made available under a CC-BY (attribution) licence.³⁴

On a wider level, the availability of standard open licences also makes it possible to make data available for large scale analysis. For example, in May 2021 GBIF made nearly 1.3 billion species occurrence records that are under CC-BY or CC0 licences available on the Microsoft Planetary Computer data catalogue as we can see in Figure 10 (GBIF 2021).

³⁴ See for example, the dataset containing metadata for +4 million sequence records not associated with environmental sample identifiers published on the 9th of September 2021 at: <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d8cd16ba-bb74-4420-821e-083f2bac17c2>.

Figure 10: Access to GBIF Data in the Cloud on the Microsoft Planetary Computer

The availability of openly licenced data on the cloud means that researchers are now able to use large scale cloud based computing to analyse GBIF data on a global level. As we will see later in the paper, while GBIF makes this data available free of charge, users of cloud services will pay for the use of this infrastructure.

4.6.2 Discussion

In approaching the discussion of the data presented above we will focus on identifying common elements across the three domains. In particular, we will highlight the issues raised by participants in the GBIF public consultation exercises held in 2013 and 2014 that led to the adoption of Creative Commons licences (GBIF 2013, 2014). The important point here is that by focusing on discussions around the use of licences in these fields it becomes possible to start making predictions about issues that are likely to arise if licences are applied to digital sequence information.

The findings presented above across the three domains are significant because they demonstrate that when given the opportunity, users will generally choose the least restrictive licences in making creative works, software or data (GBIF) available. However, our review of the data and debates around licences reveals five wider issues that are likely to merit further consideration in considering the use of licenses:

- Defining Non-Commercial Use;

- The Impact of Share Alike;
- The Public Domain;
- The Use of Preset & Default Licence Options;
- The Process leading to Licence Adoption.

4.6.2.1 Non-Commercial Use

The second ranked licence by popularity for Creative Commons works for both scientific publications and taxonomic data is the non-commercial use licence (CC-BY-NC). The Creative Commons CC-BY-NC licence specifies that:

“NonCommercial means not primarily intended for or directed towards commercial advantage or monetary compensation.”

A review of online public debates about the adoption of this licence by GBIF and the contributing iNaturalist citizen science amateur naturalist community revealed considerable ambiguity around the meaning of this definition with respect to “commercial advantage or monetary compensation” and a view from some participants in the GBIF consultation that an explicit definition might work better. A 2009 study of provider and user understandings of the non-commercial licence in the United States commissioned by Creative Commons concluded the following:

“The empirical findings suggest that creators and users approach the question of noncommercial use similarly and that overall, online U.S. creators and users are more alike than different in their understanding of noncommercial use. Both creators and users generally consider uses that earn users money or involve online advertising to be commercial, while uses by organizations, by individuals, or for charitable purposes are less commercial but not decidedly noncommercial. Similarly, uses by for-profit companies are typically considered more commercial. Perceptions of the many use cases studied suggest that with the exception of uses that earn users money or involve advertising – at least until specific case scenarios are presented that disrupt those generalized views of commerciality – there is more uncertainty than clarity around whether specific uses of online content are commercial or noncommercial.” (Creative-Commons 2009)

The issue here is that while there appears to be a broad shared understanding of what non-commercial use might be between providers and users, this starts to break down when specific cases are discussed. Considerable ambiguity also emerged in online debates on non-commercial use during the GBIF consultation and in the citizen science iNaturalist Forum (Oldham & Kindness 2021b). Thus, in the case of participants from the taxonomy community, it was unclear to users if a website that gained some of its revenue from support from advertising could legitimately include non-commercial data. Another example would be a software tool that uses GBIF data and charges users a small fee to recover costs in maintaining the tool. Does the existence of this fee automatically make an activity commercial? In other cases when selecting a licence, users did not appreciate that the use of a non-commercial licence would restrict others from using material in a way they wished to encourage.

This brief summary of the uncertainties involved in the expression ‘non-commercial’ can be said to mirror the difficulties encountered in debates under the Convention on Biological Diversity and related policy arenas in distinguishing between non-commercial and commercial research. An important insight from discussions around non-commercial licences for any future discussion on dsi and licences is that it would be important to explicitly define what is within and outside of the scope of non-commercial activity or use alternative and unambiguous terminology.

4.6.2.2 Share-Alike

The CC-SA (share-alike) licence is a version of the “copyleft” licences on which free and open source software was founded (the General Public Licence or GPL).³⁵ Copyleft licences are often described as “viral” because they impose an obligation on the user to share modifications and derivatives of works on exactly the same terms as the original licence. Copyleft licences such as the General Public Licence (GPL, a licence family) remain popular with large segments of the software community because they encourage forms of collaborative behaviour and the creation of communities. However, the popularity and success of copyleft or share alike licences does not mean that they are suitable in all circumstances.

Thus, in the case of GBIF it is reasonable to say that almost all data downloads contain a mix of records from different data providers and in many cases each dataset will constitute a unique object. The viral nature of the CC-SA licence means that all records within that data download, even where they are available under public domain (CC0) or attribution (CC-BY) terms, could be interpreted as being subject to the share-alike licence. At the very least, the inclusion of CC-SA licences in a dataset creates significant potential uncertainty for users given that almost all GBIF downloads will contain data aggregated from multiple sources. In light of this, GBIF does not permit the inclusion of share alike licences in its datasets.

In the field of software, where licences are very well established, companies such as Google explicitly require staff to avoid incorporating code with share-alike provisions into internal company code.³⁶ It should be emphasised that this does not mean that share-alike licences should be rejected or ignored - they are a very valuable tool. Thus, entire communities of programmers have contributed to open source software initiatives, such as the free Linux operating system, precisely because other contributors are required to ‘share alike’ and because collaborative code projects are believed to result in robust and safe software (when compared with purely proprietary systems). Equally, successful business models have been built around free and open source software precisely because these licences do not prohibit the sale of software or services built using code under a “share alike” or copyleft licence. Rather, the point here is that considerable care is required in identifying the specific use cases where share alike or enforced sharing provisions are desirable (e.g. preventing free riding) and distinguishing cases where share alike could be harmful to the realisation of wider collective objectives (e.g. sharing aggregated data as in the GBIF case).

³⁵ The latest version of the General Public Licence is version 3: <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>

³⁶ Source: Google Open Source guidance for staff <https://opensource.google/docs/using/license/>

4.6.2.3 The Public Domain

When GBIF launched the open consultation process for the adoption of licences there was initially a strong drive from some members of the GBIF community for the blanket adoption of a single option: the public domain CC0 waiver (GBIF 2013). This appears to reflect an underlying belief within some sections of the wider scientific community, who are also often the most vocal on open access, that all data should be free of any rights or obligations of any type in the interest of science. In the GBIF case this was accompanied by arguments in favour of the elaboration of ‘community norms’ requiring attribution (in effect a code of conduct). It would be sensible to anticipate that arguments for the public domain will be advanced in the case of digital sequence information particularly in light of the discussion of INSDC policy presented above.³⁷

However, in the course of the GBIF consultation it rapidly became clear that a pure public domain approach simply would not work for all GBIF data publishers (collections) as a global network involving, as of April 2021, 1,663 organisations from 124 countries who share data with GBIF and a total of 2,154 registered and endorsed institutions in 143 countries. Specifically, it became clear that a single model would not work for the different contexts in which data provider organisations operate and the distinct business models that have been developed to support their work. In the course of debates on CC0 and the public domain within GBIF it also became clear that the topic of the public domain is complex when extended to the legal systems of different countries. In short, one size will not fit all and any attempt to impose a single solution will fail.³⁸ In response, GBIF adopted a compromise approach that permits the use of the CC-BY (attribution) and CC-NC (non-commercial) licences and the CC0 public domain waiver.

4.6.2.4 Preset & Default Licences

We have suggested above that the growing prominence of the liberal MIT licence for software repositories on GitHub may reflect a tendency for software developers who are new to licences to follow the lead set by others. GitHub does not seek to shape the choices that users make in licensing materials other than encouraging the sharing of code using licences. In contrast, some GBIF data providers working with citizen scientists and amateur naturalists either predetermine the type of licence or set defaults inside their systems. It is important to understand the potential implications of both preset and default licence options.

A preset licence is a situation where those contributing data are not offered a choice and the decision on a licence is made by the data aggregator and publisher. When we initiated our research the single dominant licence across all GBIF data was the public domain waiver (CC0). Further investigation revealed that the use of the public domain waiver was mainly confined to bird observations in the eBird project dataset. The eBird

³⁷ INSDC Policy: <http://www.insdc.org/policy.html>

³⁸ An additional complicating factor encountered during the GBIF consultation is that in some countries (e.g. Canada and the UK) there are specific national licensing systems that governmental institutions are normally required to use. The provisions of those licences may only map approximately to CC licences. This may require a compromise for the use of a CC licence for specific purposes.

project is a pioneering project run by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology in the United States that mobilises bird observation data from citizen scientists/amateur naturalists.³⁹ Until April 2020 the eBird project dataset was submitted exclusively under the public domain CC0 waiver (accounting for 705,008,469 species occurrence records as of 15 March 2021). The licence relating to eBird data changed after April 27 2021 when a data refresh switched to the use of the CC-BY licence (currently 872,206,403 species occurrence records).⁴⁰ As this suggests, the use of a single preset licence and changes to that licence may have significant implications for user responsibilities - in this case users are now required to attribute the data to the Cornell Lab under the CC-BY licence - and for the use of licence data in statistical indicators.

Our second example involves a situation where those contributing data are offered a range of choices but the service uses a default licence. iNaturalist is a citizen science project that began life in 2008 as a collaborative project between masters students at UC Berkeley. From 2014 onwards iNaturalist has evolved into a joint initiative with the California Academy of Sciences and the National Geographical Society and provides research quality data to GBIF. As of February 2021, iNaturalist had 3,509,829 total users who had uploaded 66 million observations to the iNaturalist platform. As of September 2021 there were 33,786,723 'iNaturalist Research-grade Observations' on GBIF across all kingdoms.

The default licence that was presented to iNaturalist users for species observations at the time of our research was the non-commercial CC-BY-NC. All iNaturalist research grade observation data is made available through GBIF as CC-BY-NC. We reviewed debates on the use of licences on the iNaturalist public iNatForum at <https://forum.inaturalist.org/> by searching for references to creative commons licences (Oldham and Kindness 2021b). Our review suggests that many citizen science users simply accept this default. However, the discussions in the iNatForum revealed concerns within the community that users were not aware of the restrictions the non-commercial licence would place on the ability of others to reuse data. Some users were surprised by the restrictions that were imposed on wider use and a small number of contributors had sought to mobilise to persuade others to use more liberal licences (including at least one YouTube video on how to do so).⁴¹ To date the use of default licences has not generated significant controversy in the iNaturalist community and it appears that the vast majority of users have been content to simply accept the default as offered.

As this brief discussion reveals, the use of default licences merits careful consideration but can also be a very powerful tool in promoting sharing under specific terms and conditions. The promotion of specific licences as defaults is also proving important in

³⁹ See the Cornell Lab of Ornithology terms of use for further details: <https://www.birds.cornell.edu/home/terms-of-use/>

⁴⁰ The reasons for the switch are presently unknown. However, we would observe that the April 2021 data refresh added 167 million new observation records. The original CC0 eBird data remains available at the present time on the GBIF Microsoft Azure Planetary Computer snapshot.

⁴¹ See for example the 2019 video by Andra Waagmeester at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zFnJJDTYbjs>. Last accessed 12 October 2021.

the case of funding agencies attempts to address the costs of open access through cOAlition S and its Plan S. In this case, cOAlition S is promoting the use of specific licences to achieve policy objectives. This becomes clearer when we consider the relevant components of Plan S.

“Rights and licensing: The author or the author’s institution shall retain their copyright. Licenses to publish that are granted to a publisher must allow the author/institution to make either the Version of Record (VoR), the Author’s Accepted Manuscript (AAM), or both versions available under an open license (as defined below) via an Open Access repository, immediately upon publication.

Where possible, cOAlition S members will ensure by way of funding contracts or agreements that the authors or their institutions retain copyright as well as the rights that are necessary to make a version (either the VoR, the AAM, or both) immediately available under an open license (as defined below). To this end, cOAlition S will develop or adopt a model ‘License to Publish’ for their grantees.

The public must be granted a worldwide, royalty-free, non-exclusive, irrevocable license to share (i.e., copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (i.e., remix, transform, and build upon the material) the article for any purpose, including commercial, provided proper attribution is given to the author. cOAlition S recommends using Creative Commons licenses (CC) and requires the use of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) 4.0 license by default. The following exceptions apply:

- cOAlition S will, as secondary alternatives, accept the use of the CC BY-SA 4.0 license, and use of the public domain dedication, CC0.
- cOAlition S members may approve the use of the CC BY-ND license for individual articles, provided that this is explicitly requested and justified by the grantee.
- Third-party content included in a publication (for example images or graphics) is not affected by these requirements.

Collaborative research: cOAlitions S recognises that funders may face the challenge of scholarly papers published in collaboration with authors funded by non-cOAlition S members, or by authors with mixed affiliations. cOAlition S commits to actively engage with major research funders world-wide in order to foster alignment with the Plan S guidelines among collaborating authors.”⁴²

In our discussion of licences for biology journal articles above we observed that the second ranked licence was non-commercial and no-derivative works (NC-BY-NC-ND). Plan S appears to completely exclude the possible use of non-commercial licences (CC-BY-NC) and requires that use of CC-BY-ND (no derivatives) is “explicitly requested and justified by the grantee.” As we have suggested above, this is likely to reflect the use by publishers of the restrictive CC-BY-NC-ND (non-commercial, no derivatives) licence as a requirement or default rather than author choices.

⁴² Plan S: Guidance on the Implementation of Plan S. <https://www.coalition-s.org/guidance-on-the-implementation-of-plan-s/>

As this brief discussion makes clear, the use of default licences constitutes a powerful policy lever with impacts that can be quantified and monitored over time. Where necessary these measures can also be adjusted. In this paper we argue that use of a limited set of default licences could be mandated by governments and funding bodies for dsi in recognition that most users will simply accept the defaults. However, as we have seen above, this would not obviate the need for careful discussion on the use of defaults because of the scale of the impact on wider user communities in this domain.

4.6.2.5 The Licence Process

Open source software and Creative Commons licences also provide important insights into the *process* through which licences could be adopted, adapted or developed for dsi. This typically involves the definition of criteria (such as the Open Source Definition) that any proposed licence must meet, such as that they must be non-discriminatory.⁴³ This is followed by the elaboration of individual licences and a process of public consultation with a community before a licence or set of licences is adopted.

Following deployment, licences typically go through a periodic review and update process that leads to the issuance of new versions of a licence. These versions typically involve adaptations to address issues that were not previously considered or new issues such as patent and *sui generis* database rights. Following the practice in software communities, licence versions are normally numbered (e.g. the GPL2 and GPL3 or for Creative Commons CC-BY 3.0 and CC-BY 4.0). An important feature of licence versions is that they remain valid and may continue to be used within particular communities over long periods, although users will typically switch to newer versions. In this regard it is important to note that licences set the framework for a relationship between those issuing the licence and the user of the licenced material. Where a user community is content with existing licence provisions, they are likely to stay with that licence version in the absence of other incentives. What might be called legacy therefore needs to be considered in developing and implementing a licence system for dsi.

GBIF's experience is also important in illustrating what may happen in circumstances where licences are not available. Parties to the Nagoya Protocol are at liberty to include digital sequence information in the terms and conditions of Mutually Agreed Terms (ABS contracts) and it is entirely logical, in the absence of other available measures, that they will do so. The outcome of this approach will be the potential proliferation of widely differing and conflicting approaches and limitations on the use of dsi (Bagley et al. 2019). This was precisely the situation that confronted GBIF.

GBIF moved to adopt standard licences because of issues created for users by a system where publishers were at liberty to set their own terms and conditions. Analysis of 11,974 datasets containing just over 415 million species occurrence records in 2013 revealed 716 distinct licences as well as cases where no licensing information was provided (Desmet 2013). The diversity of often impenetrable licences within even small datasets made it very difficult for potential users to comply with the terms of use and virtually impossible to comply when working with millions or hundreds of millions of records. Agreement by GBIF members to adopt a small set of standard licences has

⁴³ See the Open Source Definition: <https://opensource.org/osd>

radically simplified and clarified the terms of use for all users. GBIF also implemented the use of digital object identifiers (DOIs) for each of its datasets and each individual download created by a user. This approach allows data publishers to identify the use of their data in publications (for reports to funding bodies and stakeholders). The combination of agreement on standard licences with a technical innovation to facilitate enhanced reporting succeeded in resolving key areas of friction affecting this community of data providers and users.

In connection with the adoption or development of licences, based on existing experience we would anticipate a draft outline process as follows:

- Agreement on a set of principles;
- Definition (e.g. what is to be licenced, what are the elements of a valid licence);
- Licence adoption, adaptation & development (e.g. can existing licences simply be adopted, what adaptations may be required for the subject matter, what new developments might be required);
- Consultation (with communities of providers and users including IPLCs);
- Live testing;
- Implementation;
- Evaluation (evidence based analysis and reporting), and;
- Periodic review (versioning to reflect experience and accommodate new developments).

Outside of the costs of the definition and consultation process, the main cost (as above) would be technological in establishing and maintaining a small software platform that serves licences and makes it easy for licences to be integrated into systems in machine readable format using Application Programming Interfaces. Given that GBIF is similar (in terms of number of accessions and global scale) to digital sequence information databases, we would anticipate that further discussion could assist with clarifying costs. We would also assume that any software platform could be hosted by an existing organisation with the necessary IT and programming capacity. We would also note that the writing and maintenance of software code is commonly a collaborative activity between entities using the code. Platforms such as GitHub exist to facilitate these collaborations (for example, the CBD Secretariat, GBIF and other relevant organisations already share their code on GitHub and invite collaboration).

4.6.2.6 System Costs

In considering the potential cost of the introduction of licences for dsi, the budget of the non-profit Creative Commons organisation may provide useful insights. In 2019, the latest year available, income was reported as US\$2,979,903 and outgoings as US\$4,259,101 with the main items of expenditure listed as technology (US\$1,264,204), Administration (US\$977,397) with Culture and Communications, Education, Fundraising and International affiliates accounting for +US\$400,000 and legal costs at

US\$285,872.⁴⁴ It should be emphasised that there is no suggestion that a separate organisation should be established for standard licences for digital sequence information. Rather, we would see GBIF as a more appropriate model for licence adoption and implementation. We were not able to establish the precise costs of introducing the licences at GBIF but in discussion with the GBIF Secretariat it appears reasonable to argue that costs were mainly incurred in the form of staff costs rather than meetings or infrastructure. As such, in our view, the Creative Commons example would represent an upper limit for costs.

4.6.2.7 The Limits of Track & Trace

In connection with debates on monitoring of dsi it appears to be tempting to consider licences purely as part of some form of “track and trace” approach to digital sequence information (Scholz et al. 2020). In our view, this framing is misplaced. In reality it is more accurate to consider licences as part of making digital sequence information *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable* (FAIR) in the context of policies directed towards the pursuit of open science (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Licences are important in terms of making data Accessible because they are readable by humans and machines and are also relevant to making data Interoperable, because they clarify what data can legitimately be mixed together. However, what we wish to highlight here is the Reusable aspect of the FAIR principles. The reason for this is that licences specify the basic terms and conditions of reuse. That is, licences *enable* reuse in conditions that would otherwise be uncertain. It is for this precise reason that funding bodies, such as Coalition S, the EU, UNESCO and others, are increasingly making reference to the use of open licences.

The adoption of licences by GBIF was part of a process that made the data submitted by multiple providers around the world available in a way that provided security to both users and providers. As noted above, because taxonomic datasets may contain data from potentially hundreds of different publishers, GBIF introduced document identifiers (DOIs) for dataset downloads created by users that could be cited in publications and other outputs. At the time of writing this is a relatively recent innovation. There were approximately 5,232 publications that cited GBIF data with 736 citing a GBIF DOI in the period to the end of 2020.⁴⁵ The introduction of citeable identifiers has also recently allowed the analysis and evaluation of 4,000 publications that use GBIF data in order to inform the scientific, policy and funding community about international patterns in the use of biodiversity data (Heberling et al. 2021). As such, licences combined with citations contribute to what might be called enhanced transparency and reporting for a set of resources.

The ability to cite datasets using standard digital identifiers is also an important innovation because it allows reporting to be automated by periodically carrying out automated searches of publication databases for GBIF identifiers and does not rely on users manually reporting publications. This initiative is particularly important for GBIF

⁴⁴ The 2019 financials suggest that the organisation operates at a loss until we factor in a US\$10,000,000 multi-year grant in the 2016 audited accounts.

⁴⁵ We thank Kyle Copas at GBIF for this data. A dynamic list of publications that cite GBIF is also available from the GBIF website: <https://bit.ly/3C2qRTq>

publishers who are required to demonstrate the relevance and impact of their work to their funders and other stakeholders. It is at least conceivable that DSI data providers could introduce a similar approach for downloaded datasets with the dual purpose of providing evidence of use for data providers in reporting to their funders and enhancing transparency on the use of sequence data for Parties to biodiversity related instruments and processes.

A further insight from the process of consultation leading to the adoption of licences by GBIF is publisher recognition of the limits of terms and conditions they may seek to impose. GBIF publishers were at liberty to seek to impose complex terms and conditions on potential users. However, in practice, it was widely recognised that the only way to truly control data was not to release it at all. The use of licences, as with the previous terms and conditions, was also imperfect in this regard except that it made the terms and conditions easier to understand and corresponding use of the data easier.

Debates around licencing during the GBIF consultation and in the iNaturalist community reveal what can be described as a *controllability of the world* problem when it comes to data. That is, what a user does is only controllable to a certain degree and the pursuit of compliance would require considerable effort and resources to both identify and then pursue remedies for non-compliance. Licences specify the basic terms and conditions of use, facilitate sharing and help make data findable and reusable. Licences will not assist parties seeking to pursue the use of molecules originating from their jurisdiction into commercial products that we might characterise as *hard track and trace*. However, as with GBIF, a licence system will help to radically improve transparency and reporting for digital sequence information to provider parties because indicators can readily be developed on the use of licences to a fine level of detail. Licences represent a flexible compromise between the existing situation, where there is no ready way of knowing what is happening with DSI, and a hard track and trace system.

4.6.2.8 Conclusion

This section has provided an extended discussion on existing models for sharing genetic sequence data and the growing use of open licences for software, scientific publications and taxonomic data including the metadata for sequences.

We are now in a position to make a number of observations about data sharing models and open licences that parties to the various instruments and processes considering digital sequence information may wish to consider.

The public domain sharing model that emerged during the Human Genome Project during the mid-1990s was a response to the intense interest in the commercial potential of genome sequencing. The public domain or “unrestricted access” model allows for anonymous access to data with no rights or responsibilities on the part of users to data providers. This model appears to be particularly favoured by scientists who use digital sequence information precisely because it is easy to access at scale without terms and conditions and as such is ‘frictionless.’ The value of this model to some sections of the scientific community and its merits in providing free access to data at scale should not be underestimated. The popularity of this data sharing model must be balanced against the lack of incentives provided by this model to actually share data. The benefits to data providers appear to be confined to an altruistic contribution to

science in the abstract. We may also observe that the public domain model has been characterised by a lack of effort to provide empirical demonstration of the benefits of the model including basic indicators on use etc. We in no way doubt that there are benefits from this model: those benefits may be considerable. However, the lack of attention to methods to demonstrate benefits can readily lead to the impression that the case for public domain sharing is closer to a religious or ideological conviction rather than being grounded in empirically demonstrable scientific fact. One positive outcome of the debates on digital sequence information is increasing attention to empirical analysis of the origins of genetic sequence data and the demonstration of benefits such as international research collaborations. Nevertheless, nearly twenty years on from the completion of the Human Genome Project, it is telling that it took a substantive threat to this data sharing model to initiate these efforts.

The tensions that have emerged between the INSDC and GISAID models demonstrate that whatever the merits of the public domain sharing model it does not work for everyone. At a time of a global pandemic an alternative model of a “closed commons” predicated on requirements for attribution and “best efforts” in collaboration has proven demonstrably more successful in promoting data sharing than the unrestricted public domain model. This ‘closed commons’ model is demonstrably popular with researchers in both developing and developed countries.

As we have sought to demonstrate in this paper, all models for data sharing have strengths and weaknesses. An important weakness of the GISAID model from the perspective of open access to sequence data is that the terms of use prohibit the disclosure of the sequence data in publications and other sources with the exception of the accession numbers. The GISAID model restricts access to the sequence data itself to those who are willing to accept its terms and conditions and thus become members of that particular closed data commons.

The proposal advanced in this paper seeks to overcome the weaknesses of what could be described as the ‘free for all’ INSDC model and the ‘closed commons’ of the GISAID model. This could be achieved by using GBIF as a working model for an ‘open commons’. As we have seen, in 2013 GBIF initiated an inclusive consultation involving governments, data publishers and individuals in the GBIF network that led to the adoption of a set of three Creative Commons licences: CC-BY, CC-BY-NC and the public domain waiver CC0. At the same time the GBIF network rejected licensing models that were perceived to not work well for that community, notably the share-alike CC-BY-SA and the highly restrictive CC-BY-NC-ND for non-commercial purposes with no derivative works.

GBIF is a global international network made up of governments, organisations and individuals distributed in both developed and developing countries. In September 2021, based on earlier work by EMBL-EBI, a new INSDC sequences dataset containing metadata for taxonomic records linked to sequences was deposited with GBIF under a CC-BY licence.⁴⁶ GBIF’s experience may therefore serve as a useful working model for other processes.

⁴⁶ Geographically Tagged INSDC Sequences: <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/ad43e954-dd79-4986-ae34-9ccd8bf568>

The key feature of the GBIF process was recognition of the diversity of circumstances and interests of members of the GBIF network and a shared willingness to identify a set of choices that would work for everyone within the network. Those choices ultimately came down to the three licences discussed above. In contrast with GISAID, the outcome of the GBIF process is an 'open commons' where data may be freely shared. The boundaries of the 'open commons' are defined by the three licences used for the taxonomic data and linked to the underlying data publisher and user agreements. Participants in the GBIF open commons agree to abide by the rules set by those licences focusing on attribution and the purposes of the use of data.

It is our argument that GBIF provides a useful model for potential approaches to the sharing of digital sequence information under the CBD and related instruments and processes. Specifically, an opportunity exists for parties to these instruments and processes to define an 'open commons' for digital sequence information that recognises the diversity of rights and interests of participants globally. The key to creating a functioning open commons on a global scale would be to agree to restrict the number of choices for sharing sequence data.

Recent research has demonstrated that the majority of digital sequence information that contains country information originates from northern developed countries and China (Scholz et al. 2021). At the same time, developing countries are revealed to be significant users of genetic sequence data originating elsewhere. This speaks to the growing internationalisation of the biosciences: a trend that is likely to increase with the spread of technologies such as next generation sequencing around the world (see below). However, the GISAID example graphically demonstrates that researchers will choose not to share unless they believe the conditions are right. If GISAID did not exist it appears unlikely that researchers around the world would have been willing to share COVID-19 data on such a scale during the pandemic. This 'absent' data would not have been visible as such but the lack of submissions could have had very real consequences for the ability of countries globally to respond to the pandemic. A similar issue emerged during the GBIF consultation where an initial drive from some participants that all data should be subject to the public domain waiver (CCO) was abandoned when it became clear that some participants in the network would not share their data under those conditions.

Viewed globally, the challenge for parties could be described as creating the enabling conditions to facilitate the sharing of digital sequence information in the wider interests of science, society, the environment and human welfare. In our view, this will involve offering data providers more than one choice on the grounds that one choice is unlikely to meet everyone's needs. At the same time, the number of choices will need to be restricted or the system will simply not function.

Determining what those restricted choices should be in deciding on open licences would undoubtedly be a subject of intense discussion. However, the empirical evidence from the three domains discussed above is in our view compelling. When offered a choice, providers and users will gravitate towards the simplest licences and will naturally avoid complex licence provisions. We can also take guidance from deliberations in the GBIF network on issues such as clearly defining any non-commercial use licence while in a more restricted sense the experience of cOAlition S on licence choices, such as avoiding

non-commercial and no-derivative works style licences could also inform deliberations on licence choices.

In our view a willingness to enable choices to facilitate sharing is likely to be central to finding a global solution on digital sequence information under the CBD and across instruments. The promise of such an approach is that it will create the foundation for an open commons to enhance data sharing that is bounded by the rules determined by parties to those instruments and processes.

A central concern in debates on digital sequence information is benefit-sharing. In our view the establishment of an open commons or system for digital sequence information must return demonstrable benefits to the participants in such a system. However, given the scale and complexity of sharing sequence data on a global scale, any benefit-sharing system will need to be indirect.

We discuss measures to generate revenue for benefit-sharing in the sections to follow. We close this discussion on the option to use open licences by focusing on the need to create a bridge between licenced materials and benefit sharing in constructing a global system.

In the discussion above we have focused on the need to enable a limited set of choices for data providers to promote data sharing. This is the problem that licences solve: choice in making data available. The second problem that licences solve, as in the discussion of the original concept of bounded openness below, is the creation of a bounded space for the benefit-sharing system. Those inside the bounded space defined by the open licences are entitled to receive benefits from the benefit-sharing system discussed below. Those outside that space are not.

In theory, it would be possible to define the bounded space for the benefit-sharing system with a single licence provision that, at its simplest, might say:

“This accession is licensed under the global benefit-sharing system established under [participating instruments] and must be deposited in a database that participates in the benefit-sharing system. Deposit of this sequence outside the benefit sharing system is a breach of the terms of this licence.”

We are not concerned here with the precise construction of the license provision but communicating the general idea. If participating parties required those depositing sequences to do so in a participating database with one of the standard licences the effect would be to create a bounded data commons. Over time the number of unlicensed sequences outside the system would decrease, and the number of sequence accessions inside the system would increase.

In this proposal the link to benefit-sharing is established if parties require participating databases and the life science infrastructure to charge users small fees for the use of the infrastructure (see below). An agreed portion of revenue generated would contribute to the sustainability of the infrastructure and a portion would be committed to the global fund for investment in biodiversity discussed below.

It is important to recognise that it is the sovereign right of states not to participate in the system under this proposal. States that did not participate in the system would not be entitled to a share of benefits under the distributed global fund considered below.

However, as we see below, the aim in combining open licences with benefit-sharing is to create a system that states, the life science infrastructure and the private sector will want to join.

5 From Open Access to Open Science

The developments in the fields of genomics, software, scientific publications and taxonomic data that we have considered above form part of a wider convergence of multiple movements around the concept of *open science*.

The term open science is relatively recent and can be traced, among other potential options, to a 1985 article by Daryl Chubin entitled “Open Science and Closed Science: Tradeoffs in a Democracy” (Chubin 1985). The concept of open science has been widely promoted in recent years, including by the European Union and the OECD, but until recently has lacked clarity in definition (Vicente-Saez and Martínez-Fuentes 2018; Salmi 2015; Gomez-Diaz and Recio 2020; OECD 2015). In this discussion we focus on two recent international policy developments that are bringing increasing clarity to open science. The first of these is the recently adopted UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science and the second is the OECD Recommendation of the Council on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data (EASD) (UNESCO 2021; OECD 2021).

In 2019 the UNESCO General Conference decided to elaborate a draft recommendation on open science. The elaboration of the draft recommendation builds on UNESCO’s previous work in standard setting, notably the 2017 UNESCO Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers which updated its 1974 recommendation on the Status of Researchers. The recommendation was adopted by UNESCO member states at its General Conference on the 23rd of November 2021 (Document 41/C22). Article 6 of the recommendation defines open science as follows:

“For the purpose of this Recommendation, **open science** is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.”

This definition and the use of the term ‘construct’ reflects the reality that open science encompasses a variety of overlapping and converging movements directed towards openness as set out in Figure 11.⁴⁷

⁴⁷ For a presentation on the then UNESCO draft recommendation by Ana Persic (UNESCO) see the ABS Initiative webinar entitled *Interplay between open science, access to data, terms and conditions of databanks, and options for tracing the use of DSI*. 13th October 2021, available at https://youtu.be/F_iSEW9mKRA. Presentation starts at 26:00.

Figure 11: Elements of Open Science, Ana Persic (UNESCO), image courtesy of Robbie Ian Morrison

The material elements of open science (open data, open access publications etc.) are reflected in the concept of open scientific knowledge as defined in Article 7. We focus here on the shared elements of open scientific knowledge rather than the elaborations of each element under Article 7.

“Open scientific knowledge refers to open access to scientific publications, research data, metadata, open educational resources, software, and source code and hardware that are available in the public domain or under copyright and licensed under an open licence that allows access, re-use, repurpose, adaptation and distribution under specific conditions, provided to all actors immediately or as quickly as possible regardless of location, nationality, race, age, gender, income, socio-economic circumstances, career stage, discipline, language, religion, disability, ethnicity or migratory status or any other grounds, and free of charge. It also refers to the possibility of opening research methodologies and evaluation processes.”

As we can see, the foundation for the different elements of open science includes materials that are either in the public domain or made available under an open licence. However, in common with other recent recommendations, there is recognition that openness cannot be absolute but may be conditioned in various ways and for various reasons that may change over time.

“Access to scientific knowledge should be as open as possible. Access restrictions need to be proportionate and justified. They are only justifiable on the basis of the protection of human rights, national security, confidentiality, the right to privacy and respect for human subjects of study, legal process and public order, the protection of intellectual property rights, personal information, sacred and secret indigenous knowledge, and rare, threatened or endangered species. Some data or code that is not openly available, accessible and reusable may nonetheless be shared among specific users according to defined access criteria made by local, national or regional pertinent governing instances. In cases where data cannot be openly accessible, it is important to develop tools and protocols for pseudonymizing and anonymizing data, as well as systems for mediated access, so that as much data as possible can be

shared as appropriate. The need for justified restrictions may also change over time, allowing the data to be made accessible or restricting access to data at a later point.”

Article 8’s reference to “as open as possible” is in our view probably derived from the expression “as open as possible and as closed as necessary” that is linked to the explanation of the FAIR principles in the European Union Horizon 2020 Program Guidelines on FAIR Data (Landi et al. 2020; Wilkinson et al. 2016). That is, a balance will need to be struck in many cases in deciding on whether, and to what extent, data should be open or closed. We can also note that Article 8 recognises that data may be shared between specific users under defined access criteria. GISAID would be an example of this type of approach where licence terms are used to create a closed commons that is accessible to anyone who accepts the terms of the licence. We can also observe the recognition of indigenous peoples rights in the reference to secret indigenous knowledge. This recognition is elaborated in greater detail in Article 11.

“Open dialogue with other knowledge systems refers to the dialogue between different knowledge holders, that recognizes the richness of diverse knowledge systems and epistemologies and diversity of knowledge producers in line with the 2001 UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity. It aims to promote the inclusion of knowledge from traditionally marginalized scholars and enhance inter-relationships and complementarities between diverse epistemologies, adherence to international human rights norms and standards, respect for knowledge sovereignty and governance, and the recognition of rights of knowledge holders to receive a fair and equitable share of benefits that may arise from the utilization of their knowledge. In particular, building the links with indigenous knowledge systems needs to be done in line with the 2007 United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples and principles for Indigenous Data Governance, such as, for example, the CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics) data principles. Such efforts acknowledge the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities to govern and make decisions on the custodianship, ownership and administration of data on traditional knowledge and on their lands and resources.”

Article 11 gives particular emphasis to the knowledge systems of indigenous peoples and local communities (in the language of CBD discussions) and is grounded in the 2007 United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. The emphasis that is placed on indigenous data governance reflects growing attention by indigenous scholars and activists to the governance of digital data (Tahu Kukutai 2016; Carroll et al. 2020; Caron et al. 2020; Liggins, Hudson, and Anderson 2021). In 2018 a group of indigenous scholars developed the CARE principles as a complement to the FAIR principles discussed above (Carroll et al. 2020). The purpose of the CARE principles is described as follows on the website for this initiative:

“The current movement toward open data and open science does not fully engage with Indigenous Peoples rights and interests. Existing principles within the open data movement (e.g. FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) primarily focus on characteristics of data that will facilitate increased data sharing among entities while ignoring power differentials and

historical contexts. The emphasis on greater data sharing alone creates a tension for Indigenous Peoples who are also asserting greater control over the application and use of Indigenous data and Indigenous Knowledge for collective benefit.

This includes the right to create value from Indigenous data in ways that are grounded in Indigenous worldviews and realise opportunities within the knowledge economy. The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance are people and purpose-oriented, reflecting the crucial role of data in advancing Indigenous innovation and self-determination. These principles complement the existing FAIR principles encouraging open and other data movements to consider both people and purpose in their advocacy and pursuits.”⁴⁸

The important point here for our purposes is that the UNESCO recommendation seeks to explicitly recognise the wider range of rights and interests involved in the construction of open science as part of what can be described as an inclusive vision.

The UNESCO recommendation also includes a range of provisions that relate to topics such as sustainability, infrastructure and funding that we will consider in further detail below. We now turn to a second important development at the OECD that focuses on data sharing.

On the 6th of October 2021 the Council of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) adopted *The Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of data (EASD)* (OECD 2021). The OECD is an international organisation consisting of 38 member states.

The EASD recommendation builds on earlier work by OECD on topics including Access to Research Data from Public Funding, Enhanced Access and More Effective Use of Public Sector Information, work on Digital Government Strategies and Health Data Governance (OECD 2021).

The EASD recommendation arose from recognition of the need for “more coherent data governance frameworks” with the growth of data access and sharing across sectors and countries (OECD 2021). The aim of the recommendation is set out as follows:

“The Recommendation aims to set out general principles and policy guidance on how governments can maximise the benefits of enhancing data access and sharing arrangements while protecting individuals’ and organisations’ rights and taking into account other legitimate interests and objectives.”

The recommendation is divided into three sections that address the following issues:

- Reinforcing Trust across the data ecosystem;
- Stimulating investment, incentivising data access and sharing;
- Effective and responsible data access, sharing and use across society.

⁴⁸ Source: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>, last accessed 12 October 2021.

The EASD recommendation merits detailed review and we focus here only on key elements of relevance to discussions on digital sequence information.

The EASD recommendation meshes with the UNESCO recommendation in connection with an emphasis on inclusiveness and trust. Specifically, EASD focuses on the importance of increasing “...the trustworthiness of the data ecosystem.” Of particular importance here is a specific recommendation to:

“Promote inclusive representation of and engage relevant stakeholders in the data ecosystem – including vulnerable, underrepresented, or marginalised groups – in open and inclusive consultation processes during the design, implementation, and monitoring of data governance frameworks related to data access and sharing to reinforce trust.” (OECD 2021 1.III(a), original emphasis);

The process of promoting trust across the data ecosystem is accompanied by specific recommendations to “empower individuals, social groups, and organisations” through mechanisms “...such as trusted third parties that increase their agency and control over data they have contributed or that relate to them...” (OECD 2021 1.III(d)). This is combined with a call to:

“Enhance transparency of data access and sharing arrangements to encourage the adoption of responsible data governance practices throughout the data value cycle that meet applicable, recognised, and widely accepted technical, organisational, and legal standards and obligations, including codes of conduct, ethical principles and privacy and data protection regulation...” (OECD 2021 1.III(d), original emphasis)

Promoting trust in the data ecosystem is seen as requiring a “whole of government approach” and national data strategies that promote “coherent, flexible and scalable data governance frameworks.” Furthermore, the EASD places particular emphasis on technology neutrality and flexibility by calling on adherents to the recommendation to:

“Adopt technology-neutral and agile legal and regulatory environments that promote responsible data access and sharing and enable regulatory innovation, while providing the necessary legal certainty and protection with the engagement of all relevant independent enforcement authorities, oversight bodies, and stakeholder groups.” (OECD 2021 1.IV(d), original emphasis)

The promotion of technology neutrality for data sharing is of particular relevance in connection with debates on the potential application of encryption technologies such as block chain to digital sequence information. At the same time, the emphasis on technology neutrality and agility recognises the danger of overly rigid approaches to data sharing and governance that are not capable of operating at scale (Morgera, Switzer, and Geelhoed 2020; Oldham 2020; Scholz et al. 2020).

In a direct echo of the UNESCO recommendation the EASD also focuses on the need to balance considerations around the closed and open nature of data.

“Encourage data access and sharing arrangements that ensure that data are as open as possible to maximise their benefits and as closed as necessary to protect legitimate public and private interests, including

interests related to national security, law enforcement, privacy and personal data protection, and intellectual property rights as well as ethical values and norms such as fairness, human dignity, autonomy, self-determination, and the protection against undue bias and discrimination between individuals or social groups” (OECD 2021 1.V(a));

The promotion of trust is explicitly linked to three additional measures:

- Taking “...**necessary and proportionate steps to protect these legitimate public and private interests as a condition for data access and sharing**”. This includes ensuring that stakeholders are aware of their rights and responsibilities in connection with data (OECD 2021 1.V(b), original emphasis);
- Ensuring that stakeholders are held accountable for the quality of data and implementation of risk management measures including security in the data cycle (OECD 2021 1.V(c), original emphasis);

Of particular relevance, and again echoing the UNESCO recommendation, is a call to:

“Foster the adoption of conditioned data access and sharing arrangements with the use of technological and organisational environments and methods, including data access control mechanisms and privacy enhancing technologies, through which data can be accessed and shared in a safe and secure way between approved users, combined with legally binding and enforceable obligations to protect the rights and interests of data subjects and other stakeholders.” (OECD 2021 1.V(d), original emphasis).

As both the UNESCO recommendation and the EASD recommendation make clear, while the emphasis is placed on promoting and facilitating data sharing this is balanced against recognition of other factors that legitimately shape data sharing.

The EASD recommendation is also of particular importance in providing specific recommendations on what it calls cross border data access and sharing. That is precisely the situation that is being debated in connection with digital sequence information. Three specific recommendations are provided on the topic of cross border data access and sharing in OECD 2021 3.VII:

- a) **“Assess, and to the extent possible minimise, restrictions to cross-border data access and sharing**, in particular for purposes of global public interest, taking into account the need to ensure respect for fundamental rights and vital interests, including the protection of privacy and intellectual property rights and the right to access public information;
- b) **Ensure that measures that condition cross-border data access and sharing are non-discriminatory, transparent, necessary, and proportionate to the level of risk**, taking into account, among others, the sensitivity of the data, the purpose and context of data access, sharing, and use, and the extent to which measures are in place to enforce accountability irrespective of the jurisdiction in which the data is stored;
- c) **Promote continued dialogue and international co-operation on ways to foster data access and sharing across jurisdictions** – including through

the implementation of trust-enhancing measures as set out above – as well as the interoperability and mutual recognition of data access and sharing arrangements, taking into account applicable legal requirements and global standards.”

The three recommendations in connection with cross-border data access and sharing are directly linked to the promotion of trust in data ecosystems in Section 1 of the EASD recommendation. In considering these three recommendations, we might observe that they could make a useful contribution to the debates on digital sequence information under the CBD and related processes involved in defining what could be described as global standards on digital sequence information.

In our view, these three elements are complementary with the provisions on international cooperation in the UNESCO recommendation and can be linked to issues around infrastructure, capacity building and funding that are the focus of the remainder of this paper.

As a starting point in moving into these discussions, Article 18(g) of the UNESCO recommendation calls for:

“North-South, North-South-South and South-South collaborations to optimize infrastructure use and joint strategies for shared, multinational, regional and national open science platforms, including through the promotion of research collaborations, sharing of open science infrastructures, technical assistance, transfer and coproduction of technology related to open science and exchange of good practices under mutually agreed terms. Such initiatives are a mechanism to provide coordinated support for open science covering: access to open science services and research infrastructures (including storage, stewardship and data commons), alignment of policies, educational programmes and technical standards. With a number of initiatives under way in different regions, it is important that they should interoperate from the perspective of policy, practices and technical specifications. It will also be important to invest in funding programmes to enable scientists to create and use such platforms, particularly in low- and middle-income countries.” (Article 18(g))

The UNESCO recommendation contains a number of elements on the topics of sustainability, infrastructure, funding and capacity building that receive a complementary, but somewhat sharper, treatment in the EASD recommendation from the OECD (see below).

In connection with sustainability Article 14(f) of the UNESCO recommendation says:

“**Sustainability:** to be as efficient and impactful as possible, open science should build on long-term practices, services, infrastructures and funding models that ensure the equal participation of scientific producers from less privileged institutions and countries. Open science infrastructures should be organized and financed upon an essentially not-for-profit and long-term vision, which enhance open science practices and guarantee permanent and unrestricted access to all, to the largest extent possible.”

In recognition of what might be described as a history of negative practices, the UNESCO recommendation makes a highly conditioned call for public private-partnerships in Article 17(i) as follows:

“Fostering equitable public-private partnerships for open science and engaging the private sector in open science, provided that there is appropriate certification and regulation to prevent vendor lock-in, predatory behaviour and unfair and/or inequitable extraction of profit from publicly funded scientific activities. Given the public interest in open science and the role of public funding, Member States should ensure that the market for services, relating to science and open science, functions in the global and public interest and without market dominance on the part of any commercial entity.”

Elsewhere in Article 18 the UNESCO recommendation recognises that investment is required in open science infrastructure.

“Open science both requires and merits systematic and long-term strategic investment in science technology and innovation, with emphasis on investment in technical and digital infrastructures and related services, including their long-term maintenance. These investments should include both financial and human resources. Considering science as a global public good, open science services should be viewed as essential research infrastructures, governed and owned by the community and funded collectively by governments, funders and institutions reflecting the diverse interests and needs of the research community and society. Member States are encouraged to promote non-commercial open science infrastructures and ensure adequate investment in the following...”

Among other provisions, Article 18 envisions that member states will “make an effort to contribute at least 1% of national gross domestic product (GDP) dedicated to research and development, as a guide” (Article 18(a)). Support for non-commercial infrastructure, including computing and digital public infrastructure, should be directed towards long term stewardship and community control over research products and preferably built on open source software stacks (Article 18(d)). It is also envisioned that: “These open infrastructures could be supported by direct funding and through an earmarked percentage of each funded grant” (Article 18(d)).

Finally, on funding, the UNESCO recommendation makes a recommendation with striking similarities to the debates on multilateral approaches to benefit-sharing in connection with dsi in Article 22(c) by calling for:

“Establishing regional and international funding mechanisms for promoting and strengthening open science and identifying those mechanisms, including partnerships, which can support international, regional and national efforts.”

With respect to infrastructure, sustainability and funding, the OECD EASD recommendation more directly recognises the wider issues of markets, business models and public-private partnerships. Section 2 VII of the OECD EASD recommendation focuses on the promotion of investments in data sharing and the fair distribution of benefits:

a) Foster competitive markets for data through sound competition policy and regulation that addresses possible exploitation of market dominance and other appropriate measures, including enforcement and redress mechanisms that increase stakeholders' agency and control over data and ensure an adequate level of consumer, intellectual property, and privacy and personal data protection;

b) Promote, where appropriate, self- or co-regulation mechanisms – including voluntary guidance, codes of conduct and templates for data access and sharing agreements – that provide legal flexibility while ensuring that all relevant stakeholders have certainty as to applicable laws and regulations;

c) Support long-term investments in data access and sharing arrangements to ensure their sustainability, including in open data arrangements. Adherents should consider a combination of various structured financing and revenue models to support these arrangements where appropriate;

d) Promote appropriate incentive mechanisms that enable the fair distribution of the benefits of data access and sharing arrangements and ensure that stakeholders are enabled, encouraged, recognised, and rewarded for engaging in data access and sharing arrangements;

e) Support the development and upscaling of new business models and application areas for data access and sharing through a mix of policies for innovation that take into account the context of data access, sharing and use, and the various roles, responsibilities and rights, technologies, and business models of all relevant stakeholders in the data ecosystem.”

As we might reasonably expect, the OECD recommendation is more explicitly directed towards markets, incentives and business models than the UNESCO recommendation on open science which places particular emphasis on funding non-profit and non-commercial infrastructure. However, while noting these variations, we can observe that the recommendations are complementary.

In our view elements of both recommendations could prove to be useful in building a set of agreed principles and framework to inform the sharing of digital sequence information under the CBD and related instruments and processes. We now turn to a brief consideration of the economics of information as the basis for practical exploration of how the use of open licences could be linked to revenue generation for biodiversity and the biodiversity and life science infrastructure.

6 The Economics of Information

In existing research on digital sequence information, increasing reference has been made to the need to consider the economics of information arising from the work of economist Joseph Vogel and legal expert Manuel Ruiz Muller (e.g. Vogel 1994, 2011; Muller 2015). In common with other work on the economics of information their work has rightly highlighted the issue of the non-rivalrous (can be consumed without affecting others) and non-excludable (in the absence of intellectual property rights) characteristics of natural information (dsi). They propose an approach to digital sequence information inspired by a concept coined by political scientist Christopher May as *bounded openness* (May 2015). It will be useful for future discussions to briefly unpack this concept here.

Christopher May originally used the term bounded openness in work on intellectual property rights and the economics of information in the global political economy (May 2015, 2011). In particular, he was concerned with exploring the rise in demand for openness in multiple fields in response to the increased strengthening and expansion of intellectual property rights instruments during the late 1990s. For example, from this perspective, the growing demand that sequences or taxonomic data be placed in the public domain, and thus out of the immediate reach of intellectual property rights, could be seen as a demand for a particular form of openness.

In using the expression *bounded openness*, what May appears to have in mind is a *flexible space* between the extremes of enclosure represented by intellectual property rights and complete openness of information. He uses the example of Wikipedia to explain this idea. Wikipedia is an example of openness where the intention is to maintain an open resource. However, absolute openness for Wikipedia pages needs to be constrained to varying degrees because of “ideologically driven ‘vandalism’ of contentious pages” (May 2011). Based on this example he argues that:

“Openness is not the same as leaderlessness or disorganised collaboration; rather it is more about the philosophical intent of those involved, especially where the position (openness) cannot be taken to its logical conclusion if the advantages are to be maintained.” (May 2011)

He goes on to explain that the danger of absolute openness is that confidence in the authority of information is destroyed, or, put in other terms, that confidence in the authority of Wikipedia is destroyed. Building on this he argues that:

“...rather than an either/or proposition, we can see a more fluid set of possibilities, reflecting pragmatic choices between property and openness, within the socio-economic relations of what is often referred to as our (increasingly global) information society” (May 2011).

In our view, what is attractive about May’s articulation of the idea of bounded openness for the present debate on digital sequence information is its emphasis on flexibility and pragmatic choices, rather than ideological commitments either to intellectual property rights or the public domain. Furthermore, this suggests that there may not be a single solution to the particular issue at hand, as some participants in the dsi debate appear determined to assert, but rather a more flexible set of pragmatic arrangements or options that can be deployed to address the issue.

The concept of bounded openness has entered the debate on digital sequence information (natural information) through the work of economist Joseph Vogel as part of the evolution of an argument that was originally described in terms of a *genetic information commons* (Vogel 1994). In essence, in both its original and more recent formulations, this is a proposal to link disclosure of the origin of genetic resources in patent applications with the payment of a previously agreed standard royalty rate for commercial use to return benefits to a Global Multilateral Benefit-Sharing Mechanism (GBSM) (Vogel 1994, 2011; Muller 2015; Vogel et al. 2017). This forms part of approaches to access and benefit-sharing, including those adopted by Brazil, that focus on benefit-sharing at the point of commercialisation. As we have previously argued, approaches to benefit-sharing at the point of commercialisation merit fuller consideration as part of a framework approach to promoting investments in biodiversity (Oldham 2020).

However, another dimension to the economics of digital sequence information or natural information is to consider its nature as a type of asset. We can usefully explore the properties of this type of asset by contrasting it with digital currencies such as Bitcoin. As discussed in the earlier work, digital currency consists in essence of an encrypted digital signature that has no intrinsic value other than the value attributed to it by those who engage in trade in currencies (Oldham 2020). It is literally money from nothing. In contrast, a genome has multiple intrinsic values. However, a distinctive feature of genomes as a type of asset is that those values, including economic value, can only be realised where genomes are compared and contrasted with other genomes. Genomics and the other omics are, in the simplest of terms, exercises in compare and contrast conducted at scale. Put in other words, the value of a genome as an asset can only be realised where it is shared. Whereas digital currencies as a type of asset depend on the use of encryption to exclude others as the basis for the realisation of value, the value of genomes is realised in the opposite way, through sharing. In this, genomes also differ from gold as a form of asset in that gold is typically used as a store of value and a hedge against economic uncertainties. Indeed, we may observe that the tendency of the biodiversity community to treat genetic resources as a form of gold (green gold, blue gold etc.) is profoundly unhelpful. Treating digital sequence information as gold mischaracterises the nature of the asset and how value can be realised from this type of asset.

These brief reflections on the values of digital sequence information as a type of asset also assist us in understanding the emphasis that the scientific community places on open access to sequence data and the motivations behind investments in the ever expanding growth in sequence data. These reflections can also assist us with thinking about the position of countries as asset holders. Viewed from this perspective, countries could be said to hold rights (as sovereigns) over a set of assets in the form of genomes. However, the multiple values of those assets for the economy and wider human welfare *can only be realised* where they are made available for combination with other assets of the same of type.

An interesting feature of debates on the Bermuda Principles is the emergence of the concept of a genome or genomic commons. As genomics data and related data has expanded, recognition of the means for the realisation of value for these types of assets is finding expression in the concept of a *data commons*. The rise of digital sequence information, along with the explosion in other forms of digital data, is also leading to

recognition that the publicly funded infrastructure faces pressure through exponential growth and that value is best realised through the combination of data that is presently located in silos. Of direct relevance to dsi, in 2015 the US National Institutes of Health launched a set of pilot projects on a data commons to explore the possibility of a sustainable business model.

“Physically speaking, the commons will be collections of public and private resources (including cloud resources) for storing data and computing with those data. To be commons-compliant, such resources must abide by two simple rules. First, each research object in the commons — for example, data, software, narratives or papers — must be uniquely identified, shareable (taking into account privacy issues), and resolvable to its source by using a common identifier. Second, each research object must be defined by a minimal amount of metadata, as defined by the community.” (Bourne, Lorsch, and Green 2015)

The concept of the data commons is then combined with a new experimental business model:

“We also are studying the notion of computing credits, in which a grant recipient is given credits instead of funding to pay for computational time. A principal investigator would be able to spend those credits at any commons-compliant resource. Researchers whose work involves extensive computation on small amounts of data may spend their credits at a different commons-compliant resource to investigators who do minimal computing on large amounts of data.

This model is very different from the situation today. It shifts the initial burden of hardware, data and software maintenance from awardees and their institutions to third parties, notably cloud service providers. The funding model also has the effect of paying only for services used, and aims to create competition in the marketplace, so this approach could result in more data science per dollar.” (Bourne, Lorsch, and Green 2015)

As we will see below, following the completion of the commons pilots the NIH has scaled up the approach across its operations, including the Sequence Read Archive, through the Big Data to Knowledge programme and the recent STRIDES programme which has established partnerships with cloud service providers.⁴⁹ These approaches have also informed the ongoing development and implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). We explore the nature of cloud computing and the economics of cloud computing in more detail below.

In closing this discussion on the economics of information, our approach is informed by a Sustainable Social-Ecological Systems (SES) perspective, which is concerned with the governance of common pool resources on multiple scales and extends to knowledge as a commons (Oldham 2020). Viewed from that perspective, licences set the basic terms and conditions for the construction of a commons that enables and promotes the

⁴⁹ See BD2K at <https://bit.ly/3zGT4wV> and the STRIDES programme at <https://datascience.nih.gov/strides>

realisation of the values of digital sequence information as an asset. Licences are an enabling element of the FAIR principles that will allow digital sequence information to become reusable and interoperable with other types of data as part of a wider data commons. The FAIR principles and the use of licences are already embedded in the policies of many countries and regions including in European Union Directive 2019/1024 on open data (e.g. Article 8 on standard licences).

The use of licences does not in and of itself address the question of benefit-sharing, but creates the enabling conditions for a solution. Our approach assumes that any measures on digital sequence information must return tangible monetary benefits to biodiversity.

A central problem in debates on digital sequence information and benefit-sharing is *benefit-sharing for what?* Is benefit-sharing to be understood as a set of financial transfers from the bank accounts of ‘user’ countries to the bank accounts of ‘provider’ countries for any purpose whatsoever? Or is benefit-sharing better reframed as the promotion of tangible and quantifiable investments in biodiversity as the global asset on which all economies and human societies depend?

This matters because, as the recent Dasgupta Review *The Economics of Biodiversity* has emphasised, the current crisis in biodiversity arises from the failure of existing economic models to include biodiversity as natural capital (Dasgupta 2021). In the context of debates on digital sequence information this failure is observable in arguments that any change to existing approaches will “stifle” research and innovation or that rent transfers should be made from user countries to provider countries for the use of digital sequence information. None of these arguments take biodiversity into account as an asset, as natural capital, and thus reproduces the reasoning that created the crisis in the first place. As Dasgupta observes:

“We may have increasingly queried the absence of Nature from official conceptions of economic possibilities, but the worry has been left for Sundays. On week-days, our thinking has remained as usual.” (Dasgupta 2021, 4)

Following this same reasoning, we might respond to arguments about the stifling of research and innovation where used as an excuse to avoid action with the blunt observation that there will be no research and no innovation on a dead planet.

The question therefore becomes how to avoid the pitfalls of existing arguments and place biodiversity at the forefront of the debate as the object of benefits? One element of a wider solution in our view is to tie licensing to a requirement to deposit sequence data in databases that charge users fees for the use of the infrastructure. If parties participating in multilateral arrangements on digital sequence information require users to deposit sequences in databases that charge fees for the use of the infrastructure, a means will be found to construct a mechanism that returns value for investment in biodiversity. Fees based on the principle of use are readily understandable by public and private users as proportionate and fair. As we will see, the implementation of such an approach would require a willingness on the part of public funding bodies to make adjustments to their approach, for private users to be willing to contribute and for public and private cloud service providers to cooperate in identifying cost effective and efficient ways to implement the approach. While challenging, the outcome would be an approach that takes biodiversity into account as natural capital and returns value to biodiversity at scale.

7 Cloud Computing & DSI

Cloud computing involves the storage of data and use of computing capacity housed in remote data centres rather than on an individual user's computer or local facilities. Taken together these data centres form world wide networks with varying degrees of integration and communication between them.

Cloud computing is commonly described in terms of a set of three services that are offered to users:

- infrastructure as a service (hardware),
- platforms as a service (framework applications), and;
- software as a service (user end products).

In the period since the early 2000s cloud computing has become a multi-billion dollar industry with estimated user spending of US\$242 billion worldwide in 2019 and predicted spending of US\$362 billion by 2022.⁵⁰

“The cloud” can appear remote and difficult to grasp. In practice, most readers of this paper will use it every day, to upload or download photographs or video or to share files using services such as Apple iCloud, Google Photos, Google Drive, Microsoft OneDrive, Dropbox and a host of over services. When we purchase goods or services online we will normally be buying from a company that hosts their website on rented computer infrastructure situated in a data centre for which they pay fees. Applications on our mobile phones communicate regularly with remote servers at the expense of our battery life and mobile data budgets unless we switch them off. If at any point the cloud appears confusing it can be useful to look at your mobile phone and ask what applications are consuming your battery life or data budget (and switch off those you do not use). While contemplating the applications on the phone you might also remember the online subscriptions with services that you started as a free trial (for how much was that again?) and have forgotten to cancel (and cancel those as well). In short, you probably already know what the cloud is without calling it that. Over the last decade the cloud has become part of the fabric of the everyday lives of hundreds of millions, if not billions, of people around the world.

The key feature of cloud services, and the key reason for the size of user spending, is that we as consumers or as companies pay subscription fees for services such as iCloud, Google Photos or a host of other services. These services are deliberately priced at levels, pegged to where we live using tools such as purchasing power parities, that we are willing to pay as long as they do not cause financial discomfort (as we will stop paying at that point). In the case of online storage for photos, video or files, these services are typically offered with a basic free tier and staged paid tiers for additional storage with a price point of approximately US\$9.99 per month for 2 terabytes of data across most offerings. Users are often provided with access to software as a service, such as Google documents, as part of these free or paid services.

⁵⁰ Statista 2021, citing Gartner: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/273818/global-revenue-generated-with-cloud-computing-since-2009/>

The cloud services that we as consumers routinely encounter are the tip of a much larger iceberg in the digital economy. The key feature of those services, whether they be hardware, framework applications or software, is that they are normally *rented* from a service provider rather than purchased outright. For companies and researchers the cloud offers major economic savings because it *abstracts away* the complexities and costs of the purchase, maintenance and upgrade of expensive equipment and associated software and small army of technical maintenance staff needed to maintain all of that, in favour of *rental* of services with different pricing models. This is one reason why companies are the main segment of users of cloud services: the business case for the use of cloud services is compelling.

As cloud services have expanded they have increasingly moved into “big data” areas such as the life sciences. Thus, many companies offer specialist and preconfigured platforms in the life sciences (e.g. Microsoft Genomics, Google Cloud Life Sciences and Genomics in the Cloud from Amazon Web Services).⁵¹ Major actors in the cloud computing market such as Amazon, Microsoft and Google have all established partnerships with companies that provide specialist platforms for the life sciences in areas such as pharmaceuticals. Increasingly, these services have expanded to include artificial intelligence applications, such as machine learning for image recognition or the large scale classification of texts such as patient records or the scientific and patent literature. These services are then added to the paid subscription or rental offerings. As such, looking beyond our everyday experience as consumers, the cloud is best understood as a network involving multiple public and private actors and as a marketplace for specialist services.

In the preceding discussion we focused on the importance of the economics of information in assisting us with understanding the nature and characteristics of the object of policy attention: in this case of genomes as a particular and distinctive type of asset. Sticking with economics we can also interrogate the business and pricing models that have been developed for cloud computing or cloud service markets (Wu, Buyya, and Ramamohanarao 2019). That is, the economics of cloud services as they are experienced by companies and organisations such as research organisations (Wu, Buyya, and Ramamohanarao 2019). These pricing models can be divided into three basic groups:

- a) storage;
- b) compute (processing of data), and;
- c) network egress (moving data around, e.g. downloading to a computer or mobile phone).

Companies typically offer a relatively generous free tier of services that are designed to convert users to paying customers. For paid services users are charged in units of the specific service. In contrast with normal consumer experience, these charges are normally levied by the second, the minute or hour of usage or can be advance purchased

⁵¹ a) Microsoft Genomics: <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-gb/services/genomics/> ; b) Google Life Sciences <https://cloud.google.com/life-sciences> ; c) Amazon Genomics in the Cloud <https://aws.amazon.com/health/genomics/>

(reserved) at discounted rates for set periods (e.g. a year). For example, the user of a commonly used database (MySQL, Postgres, Mongo Db etc.) would pay in specific price units for that resource while a user of an Apache Spark cluster for large scale parallel processing would pay in price units of that service. Specialised services offered on those platforms such as life science analytics or artificial intelligence tools would attract a different price unit. Each service has a price and where users are using multiple services at the same time they will pay in the units for each service.

A key advantage for users of these services is that payment ceases when a user stops using the service. A key obstacle for users is that it can be difficult to know in advance how much the use of a service or set of services will actually cost. To assist users in overcoming this obstacle, all the major companies offer online calculators that allow users to work out what these costs are likely to be and often provide worked examples for users to test.⁵² Importantly, users are able to set budget ceilings and alerts to control expenditure. The free tiers offered by these companies are also important in familiarising new users with costs. The free tiers are generally expressed as a monetary credit (e.g. US\$240) and this creates a safe buffer for users to gain experience in how the costs will work out before spending their own money.⁵³

The emergence of cloud computing is proving extremely important in the case of the life sciences because of the exponential growth and scale of genomics data (Oldham 2020). The use of cloud computing benefits from economies of scale, because multiple users can use the same resource without diminishing it, while the implementation of the FAIR principles helps overcome problems in mobilising data from different sources for analysis.

The European Union and the United States, among others, have responded to the increasing challenges of the digital economy by promoting a major shift towards developing and integrating cloud infrastructure and services. In the European Union this takes the form of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as an offering for 1.7 million researchers and 70 million professionals.⁵⁴ The European Open Science Cloud involves public sector and private sector service providers who advertise their services via the cloud portal.⁵⁵ Prototyping for the European Open Science Cloud was initiated under the Horizon 2020 programme with 320 million Euros in funding.⁵⁶ Work on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) should be seen in the wider context of the

⁵² Microsoft Genomics provides a calculator based on the number of gigabases processed <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-gb/pricing/details/genomics/>

⁵³ In addition to assistance with calculating costs, for the life sciences most major companies provide services that comply with regulations relating to privacy, security and data sovereignty in specific jurisdictions.

⁵⁴ Source: <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

⁵⁵ See: <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

⁵⁶ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

European Data Strategy⁵⁷ for a single market in data and the recently declared Europe's Digital Decade.⁵⁸

In the United States the shift to the cloud is being led by major research funders, notably the National Institutes of Health (see above). The 2018 *NIH Strategic Plan for Data Science* is informed by expectations that the volume of sequence data will exceed that of the other major sources of data combined (astronomy, YouTube and Twitter) by 2025 (NIH 2018).

The significance of these developments for digital sequence information is that the storage and processing of this data will increasingly take place in the cloud and will involve a mixture of public and private sector service providers. Thus, in 2019 the US National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) under the NIH announced that it had initiated the transfer of 26 petabytes of sequence data from the Sequence Read Archive or SRA (which stores Next Generation Sequence data) onto the cloud servers of Amazon Web Services and Google Cloud (NLM 2019).

The NIH has approached cloud service provision through the creation of the STRIDES Initiative to provide "...cost-effective access to industry-leading partners to help advance biomedical research."⁵⁹ The STRIDES Initiative has contracted two intermediary companies to manage the provision of services from Amazon and Google.⁶⁰ This involves a system where NIH institutions and grant holders establish cloud service accounts through the intermediaries and research funding is transformed into credits or vouchers to purchase cloud storage and compute time at discounted rates. In this model the sequence data itself remains openly accessible free of charge, however the processing, storage of results and movement of data by grant holders is paid for through public research funding. For the private sector, the emphasis on implementation of the FAIR Principles in the wider NIH strategy means that they will benefit from using large scale data in the cloud that is FAIR compliant. However, as far as we are aware, private sector users will pay for the use of cloud services and any data transfers at the normal commercial rates.

In the European Union, the arrangements with respect to sequence data held by EMBL-EBI in relation to the EOSC remains unclear to the authors.⁶¹ However, the available evidence suggests that the development of the wider EOSC system will involve a mix of public and private services and that the costs of cloud services to researchers will be reimbursed through research budgets. Private sector users will pay commercial rates.

⁵⁷ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en

⁵⁸ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_21_983

⁵⁹ See: <https://datascience.nih.gov/strides>

⁶⁰ For further information see the NIH STRIDES Initiative: <https://datascience.nih.gov/strides>

⁶¹ EMBL and the European Life Science Infrastructure for Biological Information (ELIXIR) are signatories to the 2017 European Open Science Cloud Declaration. https://eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_declaration.pdf

We would emphasise that as a new and large scale initiative, further investigation and clarification of planning for EOSC and its emerging marketplace will be needed.⁶²

In considering these developments, it appears reasonable to argue that we are witnessing an important emerging transition point from the existing and formerly dominant model of funding for the life science infrastructure to a mixed model. In the existing model the life science infrastructure is funded through a combination of structural funds (e.g. for facilities), research grant based funding and, to a limited degree, provision of private services to clients (OECD 2017). The emerging mixed model will combine public and private services and free, discounted and commercial rate services.

The emerging model will also present challenges for the existing infrastructure. In Europe the life science infrastructure, including sequence databases, can be grouped under the European Life Science Infrastructure for Biological Information (ELIXIR). ELIXIR is an intergovernmental organisation consisting of 22 member countries and one observer that brings together life science infrastructure from 222 organisations including EMBL-EBI. ELIXIR is organised around a Hub (based in Cambridge, UK) and national nodes in member countries. As such ELIXIR can be described as a distributed infrastructure. ELIXIR offers a set of Platforms (e.g. Tools, Data, Compute) to public and private sector researchers.⁶³

The ELIXIR 2019 *long term sustainability plan* highlights the considerable uncertainties that confront an infrastructure that depends on a combination of national and infrastructure grants and competitive research grants (Martin, Smith, and ELIXIR Partners 2019). While the actual annual cost of the distributed infrastructure is difficult to precisely quantify, the sustainability plan suggests it is in excess of 100 million Euros a year. ELIXIR highlights that the global life science infrastructure, consisting of over 1,600 databases, typically relies on “...short-term, fixed duration research grants. As a consequence of this, very few bioinformatics resources have secure, long term funding.” In light of this, ELIXIR members have been seeking to identify more “fit for purpose funding models,” such as the use of some form of access fee. However, they note that this type of fee could only be considered if the funding agency for that resource does not require that the data remain open and free for all users. As ELIXIR point out, this would run counter to the entire movement against putting knowledge and data behind paywalls (see above). As external observers of the challenges that ELIXIR is seeking to navigate, we may note that there appears to be expectation on the part of funders that data be made openly accessible free of charge potentially *for eternity* without any detailed consideration or commitment by the funders to meeting those long term costs. This appears to reflect a lack of strategic thinking arising from the dominance of a short term research grant model that ELIXIR and policy makers are increasingly seeking to address.

⁶² For further detail see the *Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*, February 2021. https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC-SRIA-V1.0_15Feb2021.pdf

⁶³ See: ELIXIR <https://elixir-europe.org/>

Members of ELIXIR are increasingly seeking to explore sustainable business models through practical analysis. To date this work has been led by UniProt. UniProt is the main open access database for protein information from sequencing projects and is operated by the UniProt Consortium (consisting of European bioinformatics institutes and the National Biomedical Research Foundation at Georgetown University in the US). In an important contribution, Gabella, Gurnix and Appel at UniProt have explored the potential application of different business models to meeting UniProt maintenance costs (approximately Euro 15 million a year) (Gabella, Durinx, and Appel 2017). While noting that a variety of models, such as access fees and subscriptions, could meet these costs, their preferred approach to ensuring that all data remains open access is that all research proposals should include infrastructure costs in a budgeted data plan (formally speaking a data management plan) at somewhere between 2.5% and 5% of the project budget. Purely for the purpose of illustration, for a project budget of 100,000 Euro that would imply a contribution of 2,500 to 5,000 rising to 12,500 to 25,000 for a 500,000 Euro budget and between 25,000 and 50,000 at 1 million Euro. Those numbers would then be divided by project duration (e.g. three years). It would of course be possible to project potential revenue for UniProt based on actual grant figures for UniProt users (assuming the users are known) as the basis for a longer term projection of likely revenue.

In considering the dilemma confronting the funding model for the life science infrastructure, it is important to note that the Horizon 2020 programme introduced a pilot Data Management Plan approach that includes a requirement to specify how data will be made FAIR, licence provisions for reuse, and how data will be managed after the duration of the project. The costs associated with making data FAIR and the costs of data management were eligible costs for reimbursement under the Horizon 2020 pilots.⁶⁴ This approach has been extended under the new Horizon Europe programme which formally incorporates the promotion of open science into Article 17 of the Model Grant Agreement. The November 2021 draft Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement states that: “Costs for research output management (e.g. management of research data) are eligible if the eligibility conditions are fulfilled, including open access to peer-reviewed publications..., research data and other outputs” (Article 6.2.C.3, 4.1.4).⁶⁵ In addition, research infrastructure actions under Horizon Europe involving transnational or virtual access to research infrastructure now use simplified unit costs (sometimes called access units) for the calculation of reimbursable costs.⁶⁶ Reimbursement of such costs appears to be consistent with EU Directive 2019/1024 on open data and the reuse of public sector information.

⁶⁴ See Article 6 and Article 6.2.D.3 of the Horizon 2020 Grant Agreement and see also the Data Management Plan (DMP) template developed for this purpose. <https://bit.ly/3FTn02h>

⁶⁵ European Commission. EU Grants, AGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement, EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027. Pre-Draft (HE) incl. update for All Programmes, 30 November 2021. <https://bit.ly/3NnLE8U>. See also the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template that is to be completed to conform with Article 17 of the Model Grant Agreement <https://bit.ly/37Vbl1t>.

⁶⁶ European Commission. Decision authorising the use of unit costs for the costs of providing transnational and virtual access in Research Infrastructures actions under the Horizon Europe Programme (2021-2027) and the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2021-2025). Ref.Ares(2022)3456777 - 05/05/2022. <https://bit.ly/3wzZwWF>

As this suggests, part of the answer to the issues confronting the life science infrastructure, at least in the EU and other European countries, may be partly resolved through provision for reimbursement in research funding systems. However, in our view, this is unlikely to fully resolve these issues. Furthermore, as authors based at the NIH have argued, this will not resolve the issue that while the infrastructure is funded through national and, for the EU, regional resources, the users are increasingly international as outlined in the study on DNA databases prepared for the Secretariat by Rohden et al. 2019 (Bourne, Lorsch, and Green 2015). This may suggest the desirability of finding what the NIH researchers call “... more equitable funding models” (Bourne, Lorsch, and Green 2015). In the context of exponential growth in sequence data and growing demands on the infrastructure, including its future development, this point merits further consideration.

The challenge therefore is to find a way forward that simultaneously contributes to addressing the funding challenges confronting the life science infrastructure in addressing growth and sustainability *and* in generating monetary benefits for investment in biodiversity. As argued in the earlier paper, it is our view that this challenge will best be met under a flexible framework that involves *multiple revenue streams* (Oldham 2020). Those revenue streams could include membership fees, subscriptions, micro-levies, biodiversity tokens, biodiversity bonds, royalty rates against patents, charges for commercial users and a range of other possible options (Scholz et al. 2020). The important point here is that any potential revenue stream should be modelled and, drawing on the important experience of the Plant Treaty, that Parties avoid the pitfall of relying purely on one largely untested revenue generation model.

It is our argument that cloud based fees could form an important revenue generating stream to support the infrastructure and generate monetary benefits for DSI. We would emphasise that the revenue generated by these fees would not bridge the biodiversity funding gap estimated at between US\$103 – US\$178 billion (low) to US\$599 - US\$823 billion (high) per annum.⁶⁷ However, this approach could provide a regular source of revenue that is significant, transparent, proportionate and fair.

7.1 A Cloud Computing Revenue Model

The basic elements of a cloud funding model for digital sequence information are as follows:

1. Participating governments would require the deposit of openly licenced sequence data in databases that participate in the cloud system;
2. Data would remain openly and freely accessible;
3. Databases participating in the system would levy charges based on the use of the infrastructure;
4. All users would contribute under this system with no exceptions.

⁶⁷ Second Report of the Panel of Experts on Resource Mobilization: Final Report. CBD/SBI/3/5/Add.2/Rev.1, 8 December 2021.

5. Accommodation would be made for the differing means available to users around the world (e.g. using purchasing power parity rates) and the creation of voucher or credit schemes or similar measures;
6. Revenue would be collected by participating databases and include partnerships with private sector cloud service providers;
7. Revenue generated would be held nationally/regionally as part of a distributed global fund;
8. A proportion of revenue generated would be allocated to support the infrastructure and a proportion would be allocated to investments in biodiversity as agreed between participating parties to the system;
9. Investments in biodiversity will be made in accordance with a roadmap to be agreed between participating parties to the system.

This approach would transform the emerging global life science infrastructure into a form of social enterprise. The purpose of that enterprise would be to generate revenue to support the infrastructure and funds to invest in biodiversity. Put in other terms, the infrastructure becomes the ground that supports a commons for the benefit of wider human societies and biodiversity.

A major advantage of such an approach in economic terms is that a return to biodiversity is *embedded* in the design of the system and central to its purpose. However, this proposal raises many questions. We will now seek to address some of these questions. We will start by considering the importance of modelling costs and benefits.

The International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (the Plant Treaty) is often seen as a potential model for a benefit-sharing mechanism. While the pioneering work of the Treaty is to be applauded, in 2010 the Treaty conducted a research project to examine the effectiveness of the Treaty benefit-sharing mechanism that was followed by more in depth consideration of potential options to improve the system (Moeller and Stannard 2013).⁶⁸ In summary, the original studies found that expectations of even modest benefits, notably from the private sector, could not be expected for many years. In part, benefits would remain modest because the provisions of the Standard Material Transfer Agreement (SMTA) would lead rational actors to avoid the use of SMTA materials altogether or to free ride.⁶⁹ On the basis of the follow on studies, member states have increasingly turned to discussion of subscription based models (Aubry 2019).

The Plant Treaty continues to be an important example of a benefit-sharing mechanism but demonstrates the difficulties confronting parties and stakeholders in assessing options for revenue generation. What appeared at that time to be reasonable provisions

⁶⁸ The results of the research project, in which Oldham participated, are contained in Moeller and Stannard (2013). Background study 1 by Moeller and Stannard summarises the outcomes of the later work and can be accessed at: <http://www.fao.org/publications/card/ar/c/7dfe8195-42ee-42b3-9644-3eda66fbcaed/>

⁶⁹ See in particular Study 2 and Study 3 in Moeller and Stannard (2013). Subsequent studies focused on modelling options based on these outcomes.

in the SMTA to generate revenue under the Treaty proved, some years later, to be very unlikely to realise the objective in terms of private sector contributions.

Exercises in modelling involve a combination of data, assumptions, constraints and projections under different conditions. This paper does not seek to engage in a formal modelling exercise but instead to initiate a discussion on what such an exercise might involve. As such, what follows is intended as a basis for further discussion.

In the case of cloud based fees, the basic proposition is that a proportion of fees to be paid for the use of computing services would be returned to some form of benefit-sharing mechanism for investment. We have seen above that cloud computing involves pricing models that relate to:

- a) Storage
- b) Compute (processing)
- c) Network egress (moving data around)

Of these three points, storage is the easiest to make predictions about. The reason for this is that compute is entirely dependent on the service that a user chooses - which may vary significantly - and egress also depends in part on choices that users make. We will therefore use storage as the basis for the experiment presented below.

A second major variable for a modelling exercise is data on the number of users. As we will see below, one limitation of the existing publicly funded life science infrastructure is that information on the number of users is remarkably difficult to obtain. Existing figures have what may be described as a “thumb in the air” quality because user numbers do not appear to be a standard reporting requirement. Furthermore, it would be useful to understand the number of users across institutions and by type of organisation (e.g. public or private sector) although approximate numbers could be extrapolated from metadata about deposits of sequences or patent data involving sequences (Oldham 2020).

A third major variable relates to what is included and excluded from this approach as constraints on a modelling exercise. For example, given that all genetic sequence data is stored effectively in the same place, should the pricing apply to all digital sequence information? Alternatively, should efforts be made to limit the application of fees to only that sequence data considered to fall inside some definition of dsi (e.g. only ‘non-human’ sequences). In addition, should charges be levelled only against sequences that have a compliant licence or all sequences? As this makes clear, a range of assumptions are available in modelling data as are a range of constraints in developing projections on questions of revenue or cost.

In making these observations, it is important to emphasise that when dealing with systems on a global scale, and when seeking to design systems that will be able to scale in future, simplicity is key. Thus, from one standpoint it may appear preferable to restrict any biodiversity fees to ‘non-human’ sequence data. However, in practice this could prove to be inefficient and impractical to implement in global systems and limit the return to the infrastructure and biodiversity in ways that are neither necessary or desirable from a policy perspective.

In many respects, in seeking to calculate potential costs and revenue for any of the options proposed for dsi we are confronted by a cold start problem (Oldham 2020). We lack the desirable quantity and quality of input data to make accurate predictions. However, in the case of cloud based fees, and the micro-levy (through Unitaid), we possess data that can be used as proxies to help to make a start with this type of exercise for dsi.

In the case of the cloud, we have two readily available sources of data. First, in connection with storage, we know from consumer products what cloud storage products cost. Using this data as a guide we can apply varying levels of charges (from low to high) using available data on the number of users from a range of sources in the public literature on dsi while bearing in mind that these may have a best efforts guesstimate level of quality. Second, we can begin to look at the cloud cost calculators and worked examples that are being created by genomics researchers and companies for research in the cloud.

7.1.1 A Subscription Based Model

Our initial and crude experiment takes data on the number of users of the life science infrastructure from three sources: ELIXIR (2.8 million users), the NIH strategic plan focusing on NCBI (approximately 4.5 million users), and estimates from the study prepared for the CBD Secretariat by Rohden et al. 2019 (Rohden et al. 2019). The Rohden et al. study cites a range of estimates: for GenBank (5.8 million users), a median value from the range for the INSDC (which covers GenBank, EBI, and DDBJ) and what can be described as a global user guesstimate of 500 million (Rohden et al. 2019). Here we would note that ELIXIR's user count is based on distinct IP (internet protocol) addresses which they acknowledge is problematic, the data from NIH comes from a figure in their strategic plan but there appears to be no public data, and the figures provided in the database study are likely estimates that have similar problems. These issues should be borne in mind.

We then choose a range of values ranging from low to high at .10, .25, and 50 cents and a high value of US\$1 dollar as a daily fee payable by a user. Here we would note that 2 terabytes of consumer cloud storage costs around US\$9.99 per month with services such as Apple and Dropbox or 0.33 cents per day (365 days and around US\$119 a year). 2 terabytes would be sufficient to store a significant number of genomes across different classes of organism and is therefore a helpful reference point. The daily price points are then multiplied by 20 working days to arrive at a projected monthly value and from there to a yearly per person value. The range of yearly per person values is US\$24, US\$60, US\$120 and a maximum of US\$240. The daily, monthly, per year and five year values are then calculated by multiplying the price points by the number of users. The full results of this exercise are presented in Annex 2. A summary is presented in Figure 12 below. For reasons of space, a summary of the table is shown below displaying only the lowest and highest values.

A Flat Rate Subscription Model for DSI						
dsi user number assumption	user count per year	daily pp	yearly pp ¹	yearly revenue	year five	
Flat Rate: 10 cents a day						
ELIXIR 2019	2,867,265	0.1	24	68,814,360	344,071,800	
NCBI 2018	4,500,000	0.1	24	108,000,000	540,000,000	
GenBank (Rohden et al 2019)	5,800,000	0.1	24	139,200,000	696,000,000	
INSDC median (Rohden et al 2019)	12,500,000	0.1	24	300,000,000	1,500,000,000	
Global (Rohden et al 2019)	500,000,000	0.1	24	12,000,000,000	60,000,000,000	
Flat Rate: 1 dollar a day						
ELIXIR 2019	2,867,265	1.0	240	688,143,600	3,440,718,000	
NCBI 2018	4,500,000	1.0	240	1,080,000,000	5,400,000,000	
GenBank (Rohden et al 2019)	5,800,000	1.0	240	1,392,000,000	6,960,000,000	
INSDC median (Rohden et al 2019)	12,500,000	1.0	240	3,000,000,000	15,000,000,000	
Global (Rohden et al 2019)	500,000,000	1.0	240	120,000,000,000	600,000,000,000	

¹ Based on 240 working days per year

Figure 12: Projections of Cloud Based Revenue at 10 cents and 1 dollar per user

Figure 12 reveals that in this exploratory storage example, the potential revenue from the lowest and highest price points is a function of the number of users. Even at the lowest price point (10 cents a working day) the numbers are not trivial. In practice, even where the number of users were fixed, this type of calculation would need to take regional and national differences into account to scale fees in an equitable way (e.g. using purchasing power parities). This type of calculation also does not take into account the impact of discounts that may be applied where a user pays up front for a year. Other factors that would influence calculations are that users may not be evenly distributed across a given year.

The main contribution of this exercise is that it illustrates the impact of scale on potential revenue at different price points. This is also helpful because it reveals the potential impact of a form of subscription model for cloud services (in this case for storage) compared with other models. Thus, the rate of US\$24 per year or US\$240 at the highest price point per user would be barely noticeable for most researchers particularly where adjusted or discounted for researchers in a range of economic circumstances. This feature of consumer cloud storage models is one of the reasons that they are so popular. Thus, Apple had a reported 170 million users of paid iCloud subscription storage services in 2018. The linkage with computer equipment and infrastructure (in the form of integration with operating systems such as Windows or desktop and phone applications) is also a reason that these services have been a success.

This exploratory example is intended to ground the reader in their own lived experience. It allows us to ask the question, would you object to paying US\$24 a year or US\$240 a year if you were a researcher in a life science field as a contribution to biodiversity? Scaling this up, in the public sector we could ask universities and other public research organisations or their funding agencies whether they would object. For

the private sector in the life sciences, which appears to lack any obvious mechanism to contribute to biodiversity as a global asset, we might ask exactly the same question. As the difference between being asked to pay US\$24 or US\$240 suggests, the answer to that question (willingness to pay) will be highly dependent on the answer to the question: *what is this for?*

In the discussion on open access above we have seen that the business models for scientific publication have been dominated by transfers of public money to journal publishers at a cost to the openness of science and lost benefits to society. Those business models are coming under coordinated attack from funding bodies in order to drive costs down. The proposal for cloud based fees is deliberately not seeking to replicate those problems. Rather, there is presently no means through which research and development can return quantifiable monetary benefits to the infrastructure or to biodiversity. The present proposal addresses that gap by embedding a return to biodiversity into the system.

Within this context, notably for funding agencies, the question of what funds from cloud based fees would be used for as part of a mechanism is likely to be a central question. The answer in the present proposal is investment in the life science infrastructure and biodiversity on the assumption that a significant volume of that investment would be invested in biodiversity research and innovation as part of an agreed road map between participants in the system.

Existing approaches to digital sequence information appear to envision a global fund that would be located somewhere with Parties making transfers to the fund. The creation of a centralised fund raises major questions about the cost of a new institution and the potential remoteness of such a fund from the front lines of the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.

The present proposal envisions that databases and private sector providers around the world would play the central role in collecting cloud based fees predicated on use of the infrastructure rather than contributions by Parties. This lends itself to what could be called a distributed fund, where revenue would be held nationally/regionally by the participating Party to the system. This approach would take advantage of the existing administrative infrastructure and accounting standards. The nationally/regionally held funds would collectively constitute the overall “fund.” Disbursements from the distributed fund would be made in accordance with the activities agreed between participating Parties in the shared road map, such as investments in biodiversity in developing countries. Such disbursements could then be made through existing partner agencies and in accordance with standard accounting and reporting procedures. While clearly meriting further discussion, the aim would be to fit within existing structures, procedures and practices, avoid the creation of new institutions and minimise transaction costs.

A key focus of discussion in debates on digital sequence information is the importance of private sector contributions. This is predicated on the principle that those who seek to benefit from the commercial exploitation of biodiversity should materially contribute to its conservation and sustainable use. In this proposal there are two distinct potential roles for the private sector.

The first role for the private sector involves cloud service companies. As we seen above, the United States has established contracts for the provision of cloud services to grant holders that will be provided by Google and Amazon Web Services. We might envision a role for cloud service providers both in advising on the implementation of the system outlined above and as direct participants in the generation of biodiversity revenue from users of their services in relevant areas. Establishing whether cloud service providers would be willing, and in what form, to participate in the system outlined above would require direct engagement with the companies. However, in the context of increasing attention to the environmental impacts of large data centres and the pursuit of the circular economy in the European Union and elsewhere, a foundation could be created for constructive engagement (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017).

The second role for the private sector in this system is as users of cloud services. The available market data suggests that the major users of cloud services are in the private sector. This arises because of the major savings represented by cloud services for many companies. Under the proposal outlined above, private companies who use the life science infrastructure would pay at commercial rates based on the principle of use. A proportion of the revenue generated would then go towards investments in the infrastructure and in biodiversity. This approach has the advantage that it would be transparent to companies while the principle of payment on the basis of use is widely understood as fair. Engagement with companies as users under this system could be extended to a role in promoting nature based solutions through investments from the distributed fund in projects for Small and Medium Size Enterprises (SMEs). An understanding that a portion of funds generated would be reinvested in the promotion of new biodiversity based businesses would probably be welcomed by the private sector.

7.1.2 Flat & Variable Rate Models

The discussion above is predicated on a form of *flat subscription rate* based on storage that could be adjusted to accommodate the economic situation of public and private sector researchers in various ways. This approach has been adopted because it is the easiest to explain and understand. However, in reality one of the purposes of cloud services is to be flexible to specific needs. This is reflected in a large range of services with different price levels. This means that cloud services are commonly used at *variable rates* per service that will be multiplied across potentially millions of users. For example, users can pay for services (storage, compute, etc.) on a “pay as you go” basis or by purchasing dedicated services for a set period at discounted rates. While these options are all quantifiable for the purpose of modelling it would be desirable to identify a set of common workflows that represent standard scientific practice and generate cost models for those workflows. At the time of writing we are not in a position to do this.

The issue of cost modelling for cloud services is also increasingly confronting researchers seeking to explore the advantages of the cloud or with the positive push to the cloud from initiatives such as NIH STRIDES Initiative. In response, researchers are beginning to build tools to predict these costs. In recent work, Krum and Hoffman 2020 have developed an online modelling tool that estimates the costs of storage (rather than analysis) for genome data and tests (Krumm and Hoffman 2020). Figure 13 displays the

results from an online costing tool created by Krum and Hoffman. The cost estimation tool can be accessed for experimentation at <https://ngscosts.info/>.

Figure 13: Modelling Cloud Storage Costs in Genomics

This tool aims to allow researchers to model cloud computing costs across multiple providers taking into account the different formats and sizes of genome data, the costs of different types of storage (hot and cold), the number of times the data will be accessed, the lifetime of the data and the number of tests performed. A fuller cost estimation tool would include a means to calculate the compute (processing) and egress (data movement) costs. The biodiversity component would be a calculable percentage of each of those elements (e.g. a small percentage). In some cases, cost modelling will involve unfamiliar terminology. For example Microsoft Genomics prices its processing for sequencing in terms of Gibabases (a gigabase is 1 billion bases) with compute costs at US\$1 for 5 gigabases rising to US\$10 for 100 gigabases.⁷⁰

As noted above, one way forward for any work on modelling would be to identify a set of common workflows using cloud services that could then be costed and tested under different scenarios. However, while our experiments in this paper have been crude, the essential point should by now be clear. In contrast with the Article Processing Charge (APC) model discussed above, the aim is to claim a fraction of cloud based costs that, distributed across millions of users and thousands of research organisations and companies worldwide, will not create a major burden for any single user, agency or company. By focusing on the allocation of the revenue received back to investments in the life science infrastructure and biodiversity, the cost to users is likely to be

⁷⁰ Source: Microsoft Genomics <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-gb/pricing/details/genomics/>

acceptable and potentially embraced by users as a contribution to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. This approach also represents a departure from the existing treatment of biodiversity as an optional extra by embedding biodiversity into the design of the system.

8 A Distributed Global Biodiversity Fund

In international environmental policy debates, proposals for some form of fund commonly rest on an assumption of financial transfers from participating governments to a remote fund located elsewhere. For example the Global Environmental Facility (GEF) has a Secretariat located in Washington in the United States, the Green Climate Fund has a Secretariat based in the Republic of Korea. Other funds are typically housed with the United Nations agencies responsible for a specific instrument.

Existing funds can generally be described as being based on a donor model. Under this model, donor countries make transfers to the fund for agreed purposes. Those funds are then disbursed through a range of implementing organisations. In contrast, this paper is proposing a social enterprise model. A social enterprise model refers to businesses that reinvest their income for the purposes for which they were established.

In existing debates on digital sequence information, the main revenue generating proposals advanced so far include: the 1 % levy on commercial sales of biobased products proposed by the Africa Group; a micro-levy proposed by members of the scientific community; the cloud services model proposed by the authors; a royalty rate linked to patents under the concept of bounded openness, and; general arguments for payments at the point of commercialisation.⁷¹ Setting the merits of any individual proposal to one side, to date little thought appears to have been given to how such revenue generating proposals would actually be organised and implemented. A 'global fund' is presented as a desired solution in abstract terms but how such a fund might best be organised and implemented has not been debated in detail (see Morgera, Switzer and Geelhoed 2020).

In broad terms, the dominant donor model is predicated on donations to a fund collected through general taxation in donor countries. In contrast, the proposals mentioned above all involve revenue generating measures. The introduction of new revenue generating measures will have very different requirements to the dominant donor model. In our view, those requirements will best be met through the implementation of measures on the national level accompanied by regional and global components.

The reasoning behind this becomes clearer when we start to ask basic questions of the revenue generating proposals advanced so far. This list is by no means exhaustive:

- How will percentage, pricing or fee levels be set?
- Who will set the levels?
- How will the revenue be collected?
- Who will collect the revenue?
- Where will revenue be stored?
- How will revenue be accounted for?
- Who will do the accounting?
- What is the taxable status of the revenue?
- How will revenue be disbursed?

⁷¹ For details of the Africa Group proposal see the Appendix to CBD/WG2020/3/L.3

- For what purposes will disbursements be made?
- To whom will be disbursements be made?
- How will expenditure be accounted for?
- To whom will expenditure be reported?
- How much will it cost to do all of the above relative to revenue generated?
- How might implementation costs best be minimised in order to maximise the amount available for investment in the purposes of the fund?

These questions are not intended to discourage the creation of a global fund. Rather, by focusing on basic questions of who, what, where, when, how and why we are able to consider how it is that a global fund might best be organized in practice. It is our argument that a distributed approach to the formation of a global fund will be the most practical and cost effective approach for the implementation of revenue generation measures and the disbursement of investments. We call this a distributed global fund. Under this proposal:

- Each participating party would take measures to implement its own social enterprise model for revenue generation to support the sustainability of its biodiversity and life science infrastructure and invest in biodiversity;
- Participating parties would cooperate on the regional level for the realisation of the agreed purposes of the distributed global fund (e.g. EU, African Union, ASEAN etc.);
- Participating parties would cooperate on the global level for the realisation of the agreed purposes of the distributed global fund (e.g. through the GEF).

This broad outline of implementation tiers (national, regional, global) for the global distributed fund can be further divided into two main components:

- Revenue generation
- Investment (disbursements)

We will briefly consider each in turn.

8.1 Revenue Generation

We have presented the argument for a new social enterprise model for funding the sustainability of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure and investments in biodiversity. We anticipate that this will require a phased approach in order to avoid disrupting the operations of the infrastructure and allow time for adjustment to the new model (Oldham 2020).

We are also conscious of the diverse circumstances of the existing and emerging biodiversity and life science infrastructure across different countries around the world. That infrastructure is presently mainly concentrated in Northern developed countries. However, as we will now see, that situation is changing.

The rise in technological capacity in genomics can be traced across the globe using the known locations of Next Generations Sequencing (NGS) machines as a proxy indicator (Oldham 2020). Next Generations Sequencing (NGS) machines are expensive high throughput sequencing machines that are capable of outputs in terabytes and petabytes of sequence. Such data must be stored, curated, processed and analysed somewhere. As

such, the known locations of NGS machines provides a useful proxy indicator for the emerging global distribution of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure.

The data presented below is taken from the Next Generation Sequencing blog called Enseqlopedia at <<http://enseqlopedia.com>> created by James Hadfield, the head of the Cancer Research UK genomics lab in Cambridge. The map provides data on the reported locations of over 1,500 next generation sequencing machines at over 840 centres worldwide. Information on the location of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) machines is based on self-reporting and as such, will be imperfect. However, the reported locations of these machines provide a useful proxy indicator for the emergent global distribution of the life science and biodiversity infrastructure.

Figure 14 displays the summary data for Europe, Asia and the Pacific. Figure 15 shows the known distribution of NGS machines in the Americas and Figure 16 shows a partial view of more precise locations for NGS machines in a small number of European countries.

Figure 14: Distribution of Next Generation Sequencing Machines in Europe, Asia and the Pacific

Figure 15: Distribution of Next Generation Sequencing Machines in the Americas

Figure 16: Distribution of Next Generation Sequencing Machines in a section of European Countries (partial view)

The data presented above on the distribution of NGS machines offers only a partial view of the global biodiversity and life science infrastructure. This is for two reasons. First, it only includes reported locations of NGS machines and is therefore likely to be an under-representation of total distribution. Second, there are other more commonly used sequencing technologies that are in widespread use that will not be visible on the map.

For example, the lack of NGS machines on the map for South America or parts of Africa does not mean they do not exist. More importantly, it does not necessarily mean that there is no life science capacity. Rather, that capacity is not visible to us at present. Bearing these factors in mind, these maps are useful because they demonstrate that while the biodiversity and life science infrastructure is presently concentrated in the north it is *increasingly global in scope*.

At every location where a NGS machine is located there will be a network of specialist support staff, databases, analytics tools, equipment and funding sources to which the machines are linked. These ‘nodes’ as we might call them will supply data to other components of the infrastructure and may pass data on to data aggregators such as INSDC, GISAID or private databases.

As we can see in Figure 16, the infrastructure produces digital data but is located in physical locations in the form of laboratories and data centres. For example, the high concentration of NGS sequencing machines in Cambridge in the UK will reflect activities in the University and related hospitals and the presence of EMBL-EBI. As such, each

country can be said to have its own biodiversity and life science infrastructure with its own funding arrangements. The biodiversity and life science infrastructure will be regionalised to varying degrees (e.g. EMBL, ELIXIR and EOSC in Europe) and international (e.g. INSDC).

The social enterprise model proposed in this paper would involve a transition from a purely publicly funded model for the infrastructure to a revenue generating model using fees based on use of the infrastructure. Given the global scale and diversity of the circumstances of the infrastructure, in our view it would make sense for the implementation of the social enterprise model to be handled on the national level.

To be more precise, we anticipate that participating governments would consult with the national public and private sector infrastructure on the arrangements to transition to a social enterprise model. This would include decisions on issues such as: what elements of the infrastructure would participate; services for which fees would be charged; the levels of fees; the timing of the transition; how revenue would be collected and accounted for and so on.

We also anticipate that while much of the infrastructure is publicly funded, many of the *users* of the outputs from the infrastructure will be private companies. In our view, companies could play a key role in consultations on the design and implementation of a national social enterprise model that is considered to be efficient, effective and fair.

As this brief sketch makes clear, there would a need for significant consultation on the design and implementation of a social enterprise model. That will commonly best be conducted on the national level.

As we have discussed above, in important respects the biodiversity and life science infrastructure is regional and global. The European Union enjoys the advantage of being able to coordinate and fund infrastructure across member states in accordance with framework programmes such as Horizon Europe. The situation is less clear in other world regions. However, we could reasonably expect that regional cooperation could play an important role in implementation of a social enterprise model. Given that one purpose of the social enterprise model is to promote the sustainability of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure, regional cooperation could be particularly important for developing shared strategies for the development of biodiversity and life science infrastructure (e.g. through the African Union in Africa or perhaps through ASEAN for South-East Asia).

International level cooperation is an important dimension of the present proposal and could be broken down into a number of component elements:

- a) Mutual agreement between governments interested in participating in the system on the basic rules for the system (e.g. such as, *inter alia*: a limited set of open licences, a shared roadmap for investments, progress reports and indicators, updates to measures etc.);
- b) Cooperation with the international elements of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure (e.g. INSDC, GBIF and others);
- c) Cooperation with private cloud service providers (Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Platform, Microsoft Azure, Digital Ocean and others);

d) Appropriate use of agencies and networks for disbursements of income (e.g. GEF and UN agencies, non-governmental organisations) (see below).

As this brief discussion of revenue generation makes clear, a shift from a donor model to a social enterprise model involves multiple elements on multiple levels. However, in our view, primary responsibility for planning and implementation would logically reside at the national level. We now turn to the disbursements side of the distributed global fund.

8.2 Investments

An important concept in this proposal is the creation of a shared roadmap to guide investments. The shared roadmap would establish mutually agreed priorities for investment between participating parties across the range of instruments and processes. We assume that the priorities will be directly linked to operational implementation of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. These priorities might include, *inter alia*:

- Priorities identified by participating parties from developing countries;
- Priorities for investment in the biodiversity and life science infrastructure;
- Priority areas for research from the scientific community and informed by the work of IPBES. This could potentially include areas that are either neglected by existing funding schemes and/or that require international research collaborations at larger scales (e.g. taxonomy, neglected diseases, neglected foods, indigenous peoples and local communities, research in the deep oceans etc.);
- Priorities identified by indigenous peoples and local communities.

The purpose of the shared roadmap is to create a set of mutually agreed priorities to guide investments by participating parties at different scales.

On the revenue generation side of this system individual participating parties would implement revenue generating measures. That revenue would generally be held nationally and made available for investment nationally and/or in partnerships with other participating parties in accordance with the shared roadmap.

We regard support for the biodiversity and life science infrastructure as integral to the system because *the infrastructure is the engine that allows for revenue generation from users* from the public and private sector under the cloud services model. If the infrastructure does not exist, or is unusable because of a lack of investment, it will not generate revenue. Equally, if all revenue generated is redirected to supporting the infrastructure and only a tiny fraction is allocated to biodiversity investment then the purpose of the social enterprise is defeated. The appropriate balance between these two portions will probably best be found on the national level but could also benefit from experience sharing and technical support between participating parties in the wider system. We now turn to the organisation of the component involving investments in biodiversity rather than the infrastructure.

Investments in biodiversity are required at different levels for different purposes. For simplicity, these can be broadly classified as:

- local (e.g. indigenous peoples and local communities);
- national (e.g. national and sub-national investments);

- regional (geographic or political, Amazon basin, East Africa, EU, African Union, ASEAN, etc.);
- international (global level investments, typically in research).

The key question that arises here is: what are the most efficient ways of organising investments on the different levels to minimise transaction costs and maximise positive outcomes for biodiversity?

In our view, the answer to this question is to use the existing administrative, technical and accounting infrastructure at the appropriate level. That will typically, but not exclusively, be the national level as we will now explain.

The system proposed in the previous work and this paper focuses on the generation of revenue from the use of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure. This revenue will be generated from public and private sector users of the infrastructure for investment under what we have called the shared roadmap. As we have argued above, the collection of revenue will best be achieved through national arrangements.

An important strength of the social enterprise model is that it directly engages with the private sector as users of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure in ways that will make sense to business. Payment for use is not a controversial concept for business as long as it is seen as broadly proportionate and fair. In this case, business would be asked to contribute to the global system based on use of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure. We would anticipate that each participating party would wish to engage in consultations with representatives of the private sector on the social enterprise scheme to ensure that it is understood to be broadly fair and proportionate. Specifically, while the social enterprise model is predicated on payment on the basis of use, its aim is to facilitate and promote use of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure, not prevent or stifle it. Pricing for the private sector must therefore be seen as reasonable by the private sector. The rapid adoption of cloud services by business suggests that cloud pricing models are understood by business.

The role of private sector users in the social enterprise model is not confined to payments. Social enterprises are businesses that reinvest their profits in the purposes for which they are established. That is not the same as a public sector model. We would therefore anticipate that members of the business community could provide important expertise in the transition to the new model.

Disbursements from what we might call a set of national funds making up the distributed global fund system could focus on specific biodiversity priorities for that country under the shared roadmap. For example, governments of countries that are a home to indigenous peoples and local communities (whether they are classed as developed or developing countries) may wish to prioritise biodiversity investments with indigenous peoples in their own country or in partnership with other countries. This is another advantage of a distributed approach where funds are primarily held nationally/regionally. It provides flexibility for governments, through duly established processes and procedures, to make disbursements in accordance with priorities agreed as part of the shared roadmap (e.g. biodiversity investments with indigenous peoples and local communities).

While each party participating in the system could enjoy flexibility in making biodiversity investments we anticipate that the bulk of investments would be made with partner countries who are participating in the system. In this approach, parties would be able to make requests to partners for investments in priority areas under the shared roadmap.

At this point an important efficiency gain from a distributed global fund is that existing national technical assistance agencies could use their processes and procedures for disbursement, accounting and reporting purposes. As such, no new administrative apparatus would be needed except, where necessary, the establishment or strengthening of a biodiversity programme within the national technical assistance agency.

It is also reasonable to assume that, considered globally, there could be regional elements to the disbursements of funds where participating parties believe it is more efficient to disburse funds in this way.

The above options are more likely to be desirable where activities under the shared roadmap are required on a larger scale e.g., investments in regional level activity. This approach may also be needed in circumstances where important beneficiary groups of the system (notably indigenous peoples and local communities) may be unable to apply for investments through the national route.

The same logic applies to the international dimension of disbursement. In some cases there may be a clear case for disbursement through the GEF and partner implementing agencies. The key considerations here are efficiency in disbursement and administration relative to the scale of the investment activity.

8.3 Conclusion

In this section we have presented an outline for a nationally focused distributed global biodiversity fund. Under this proposal:

- Each participating party will implement revenue generating measures using a social enterprise model. We have advanced the argument for the cloud services model but participating parties may wish to implement more than one revenue generating model in order to create multiple sources of revenue. Revenue will be collected, stored, administered and disbursed by that participating party.
- Participating parties will agree a shared roadmap setting out priorities for investments linked to implementation of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. Participating parties will establish partnerships to pursue implementation of those priorities at the appropriate level using the existing administrative, technical and reporting infrastructure.
- The concept of the shared roadmap setting out priorities for investment across instruments, would not, in our view, necessitate a new and expensive international instrument. Rather it serves as a mechanism for coordination and partnerships between participating parties in addressing shared priorities linked to implementation of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework.
- A cross instrument approach would lend itself to the possibility that the Conference/Meeting of the Parties or governing body of a participating instrument could serve as a meeting of participating parties in order to reduce

costs. If such meetings to review and update the roadmap were perhaps rotated across participating instruments, a means might be found to maintain a balance in the portfolio of priorities set out in the roadmap.

Finally, as discussed in the previous work, one challenge confronting governments who might be interested in pursuing such a proposal would be the “cold start” problem. That is, how to get started. In our view, in order to build confidence and trust between interested parties this would involve significant initial commitments to a “cold start fund” or “start up fund” as a demonstration of intent and to kick start the distributed global fund initiative.

The ideas presented here are clearly a very different way of conceptualising a global fund than has historically been the case and are likely to merit further discussion and reflection. We have sought to identify the most efficient and cost effective ways of organising a partnership in a social enterprise on a global scale that generates revenue for investments in biodiversity and the biodiversity and life science infrastructure. In our view, that goal will most efficiently be realised through the creation of a set of national funds with regional and international components that collectively constitute a distributed global biodiversity fund.

9 Conclusion

This paper has focused on examining the conditions for sharing digital sequence information on a global level in a way that recognises and respects the rights and interests of diverse participants and generates benefits for biodiversity. It has focused on resolving two problems in a mutually supportive way:

1. Creating a mechanism for financial returns to biodiversity from the use of digital sequence information for investment in the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity;
2. Addressing the growing demands on the biodiversity and life science infrastructure and its sustainability.

Drawing on experience in the use of open source licences and practical experience in the use of licences by organisations such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the paper proposes the adoption of standard open licences across instruments and processes that address digital sequence information. Under this proposal:

1. Participating parties would agree a set of principles focusing on the promotion of open access and open science in addressing digital sequence information. The principles could draw on the recommendations in the 2021 *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* and *OECD Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data* (EASD);
2. Drawing on the experience of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) as an intergovernmental network involving developed and developing countries, participating parties would adopt a small set of standard open licences for digital sequence information. Participating parties would require users to deposit licenced sequences in participating databases;
3. Digital sequence information would remain openly accessible free of charge;
4. Participating databases and service providers would charge users low level fees for the use of the infrastructure and services based on experience with cloud service pricing models (e.g. subscriptions, “pay as you go”);
5. Participating parties would receive fees that would be held nationally/regionally in a national/regional fund as part of a *distributed global biodiversity fund*;
6. Participating parties would, over time, introduce additional revenue generation measures on the national/regional level that may include *inter alia*: a bio-based product levy; a micro-levy (e.g. on reagents/sequencing machines); royalty fees linked to patent filings or other revenue generation measures.
7. A portion of revenue generated would support the sustainability of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure and a portion would be committed for investments in biodiversity;
8. Participating parties would establish a *shared roadmap* to set out priorities for investments in biodiversity at the required level for successful implementation (e.g. local, national, regional, international);
9. Participating parties would make disbursements for investment in accordance with the shared roadmap in partnership with other participating parties. Disbursements would be made and accounted for through existing agencies at the appropriate level. Priority in partnerships would be given to partnerships with developing country participants and indigenous peoples and local

communities at the forefront of the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity;

10. Key participants in the implementation of the proposal outlined above include: the private sector, as both service providers and users; research funding bodies, in identifying and coordinating research priorities under the shared roadmap; technical assistance agencies and non-governmental organisations in facilitating partnerships and administration of disbursements, and; indigenous peoples and local communities as the principal guardians of biodiversity.
11. No new legal instrument is anticipated under this proposal. Participating parties under instruments and processes participating in the above system would establish cost-effective measures for the establishment of the shared roadmap, experience sharing, reporting and periodic updating of the shared roadmap and other measures.

To assist in consideration and potential further elaboration of these points, a short 'version zero' of an outline proposal is annexed to this paper.

The system outlined in this paper is intended to stimulate further discussion on potential ways forward in addressing digital sequence information under the Convention on Biological Diversity and the range of related instruments and processes that are debating digital sequence information. The authors assume that it is likely that if this proposal is pursued further, the CBD would take a leading role in partnership with other biodiversity related instruments and processes addressing dsi. We anticipate that this would be reflected in any deliberations on the creation of a shared road map for biodiversity investments.

As we have sought to highlight at various points in this paper, it is important to build on and learn from existing experiences. This applies both to existing experiences in the use of licences and in particular to modelling revenue generation options. However, the promise of the options discussed in this paper is that it will be possible to overcome the treatment of a monetary return to biodiversity as an optional extra or purely aspirational goal. Agreement among participating Parties to embed a return to biodiversity in policy and practical measures on digital sequence information would represent a significant step forward in all our interests.

References

- Adams, Mark D., and J. Craig Venter. 1996. "Should Non-Peer-Reviewed Raw DNA Sequence Data Release Be Forced on the Scientific Community?" *Science (New York, N.Y.)* 274 (5287): 534–36. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.274.5287.534>.
- Anderson, Jane, and Maui Hudson. 2020. "The Biocultural Labels Initiative: Supporting Indigenous Rights in Data Derived from Genetic Resources." *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 4 (October). <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.4.59230>.
- Anonymous. 2021. [Online]. "Data Imperialism in a Pandemic: How to Make Things Fall Apart." *Independent Online (IOL) South Africa*. <https://www.iol.co.za/news/opinion/data-imperialism-in-a-pandemic-how-to-make-things-fall-apart-f707fe96-fc6f-4866-aa9f-7c0aaa1f97db>.
- Arita, Masanori, Ilene Karsch-Mizrachi, and Guy Cochrane. 2020. "The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration." *Nucleic Acids Research* 49 (D1): D121–24. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa967>.
- Aubry, Sylvain. 2019. "The Future of Digital Sequence Information for Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture." *Frontiers in Plant Science* 10 (August): 1046–. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.01046>.
- Bagley, Margo, Elizabeth Karger, Manuel Ruiz Muller, Frederic Perron-Welch, and Siva Thambisetty. 2019. "Fact-Finding Study on How Domestic Measures Address Benefit-Sharing Arising from Commercial and Non-Commercial Use of Digital Sequence Information on Genetic Resources and Address the Use of Digital Sequence Information on Genetic Resources for Research and Development." https://www.cbd.int/abs/DSI-peer/Study4_domestic_measures.pdf.
- Bergstrom, Theodore C., Paul N. Courant, R. Preston McAfee, and Michael A. Williams. 2014. "Evaluating Big Deal Journal Bundles." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 111 (26): 9425–30. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1403006111>.
- Bourne, Philip E., Jon R. Lorsch, and Eric D. Green. 2015. "Perspective: Sustaining the Big-Data Ecosystem." *Nature* 527 (7576): 16–17. <https://lens.org/123-930-933-291-120>.
- Boyle, James. 2003. "The Second Enclosure Movement and the Construction of the Public Domain." *Law and Contemporary Problems* 66 (1): 33–74. <https://lens.org/178-294-244-516-858>.
- Brunak, Søren, Antoine Danchin, Masahira Hattori, Haruki Nakamura, Kazuo Shinozaki, Tara C. Matisse, and Daphne Preuss. 2002. "Nucleotide Sequence Database Policies." *Science* 298 (5597): 1333–33. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.298.5597.1333b>.
- Caron, Nadine R., Meck Chongo, Maui Hudson, Laura Arbour, Wyeth W. Wasserman, Stephen P. Robertson, Solenne Correard, and Phillip Wilcox. 2020. "Indigenous Genomic Databases: Pragmatic Considerations and Cultural Contexts." *Frontiers in Public Health* 8 (April): 111–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00111>.

- Carroll, Stephanie Russo, Ibrahim Garba, Oscar L. Figueroa-Rodríguez, Jarita Holbrook, Raymond Lovett, S. A. Materechera, Mark A. Parsons, et al. 2020. "The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance." *Data Science Journal* 19 (1): 43–43.
<https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>.
- Chubin, Daryl E. 1985. "Open Science and Closed Science: Tradeoffs in a Democracy." *Science, Technology, & Human Values* 10 (2): 73–81.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/016224398501000211>.
- Contreras, Jorge L. 2011. "Bermuda's Legacy: Policy, Patents, and the Design of the Genome Commons." *Minnesota Journal of Law, Science & Technology* 12 (1): 61–61.
<https://lens.org/160-283-900-336-795>.
- Cook-Deegan, Robert. 1994. *The Gene Wars: Science, Politics, and the Human Genome*. W. W. Norton & Company. <https://lens.org/143-685-426-334-084>.
- Creative-Commons, Creative. 2009. "Defining 'Noncommercial': A Study of How the Online Population Understands 'Noncommercial Use'."
https://mirrors.creativecommons.org/defining-noncommercial/Defining_Noncommercial_fullreport.pdf.
- Dasgupta, Partha. 2021. "The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review."
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/final-report-the-economics-of-biodiversity-the-dasgupta-review>.
- Desmet, Peter. 2013. "Analyzing the Licenses of All 11,000+ GBIF Registered Datasets."
<http://peterdesmet.com/posts/analyzing-gbif-data-licenses.html>.
- Elbe, Stefan, and Gemma Buckland-Merrett. 2017. "Data, Disease and Diplomacy: GISAID's Innovative Contribution to Global Health." *Global Challenges* 1 (1): 33–46.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.1018>.
- Endang R Sedyaningsih, Triono Soendoro, Siti Isfandari. 2008. "'Towards Mutual Trust, Transparency and Equity in Virus Sharing Mechanism: The Avian Influenza Case of Indonesia'." *Annals of the Academy of Medicine Singapore* 37 (6): 482–88.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18618060/>.
- Gabella, Chiara, Christine Durinx, and Ron D. Appel. 2017. "Funding Knowledgebases: Towards a Sustainable Funding Model for the UniProt Use Case." *F1000Research* 6 (November): 2051–51. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.12989.2>.
- GBIF. 2013. "Standard Licences for GBIF-Mediated Data: Proposed Options for Action."
https://dev.gbif.org/issues/browse/GBIF-4/GBIF_Consultation_Standard_Data_Licences.pdf.
- . 2014. "Summary of Responses to GBIF Consultation: Licensing of Data Within the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)."
<https://www.gbif.org/document/6Z903VDErucikyqAuQSYwc/summary-of-consultation-responses-licensing-of-data-within-gbif>.
- . 2021. "GBIF Forecast: Increasing Chance of Clouds for Species Occurrence Data." <https://www.gbif.org/news/4Uyr7RpdcoevzLBGRqX7k/gbif-forecast-increasing-chance-of-clouds-for-species-occurrence-data>.

- Geissdoerfer, Martin, Paulo Savaget, Nancy Bocken, and Erik Jan Hultink. 2017. "The Circular Economy – a New Sustainability Paradigm?" *Journal of Cleaner Production* 143 (February): 757–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.048>.
- Goff, Stephen A., Darrell O. Ricke, Tien-Hung Lan, Gernot G. Presting, Ronglin Wang, Molly Dunn, Jane Glazebrook, et al. 2002. "A Draft Sequence of the Rice Genome (*Oryza Sativa* l. Ssp. Japonica): The Rice Genome." *Science* 296 (5565): 79–92. <https://lens.org/005-636-899-409-993>.
- Gomez-Diaz, Teresa, and Tomás Recio. 2020. "Towards an Open Science Definition as a Political and Legal Framework: On the Sharing and Dissemination of Research Outputs." <https://lens.org/081-211-958-110-303>.
- Heberling, J. Mason, Joseph T. Miller, Daniel Noesgaard, Scott B. Weingart, and Dmitry Schigel. 2021. "Data Integration Enables Global Biodiversity Synthesis." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 118 (6): e2018093118–. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2018093118>.
- Hess, Charlotte, and Elinor Ostrom. 2006. *Understanding Knowledge as a Commons*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/6980.001.0001>.
- Hilgartner, Stephen. 2017. *Reordering Life: Knowledge and Control in the Genomics Revolution*. Inside Technology. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press.
- Human Genome Program, U. S. Department of Energy. 1993. "NIH, DOE Guidelines Encourage Sharing of Data, Resources." *Human Genome News*. https://web.ornl.gov/sci/techresources/Human_Genome/publicat/hgn/v4n5/01tocont.shtml.
- Jones, Kathryn Maxson, Rachel A. Ankeny, and Robert Cook-Deegan. 2018. "The Bermuda Triangle: The Pragmatics, Policies, and Principles for Data Sharing in the History of the Human Genome Project." *Journal of the History of Biology* 51 (4): 693–805. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10739-018-9538-7>.
- Krumm, Niklas, and Noah G. Hoffman. 2020. "Practical Estimation of Cloud Storage Costs for Clinical Genomic Data." *Practical Laboratory Medicine* 21 (May): e00168–. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plabm.2020.e00168>.
- Landi, Annalisa, Mark Thompson, Viviana Giannuzzi, Fedele Bonifazi, Ignasi Labastida, Luiz Olavo Bonino da Silva Santos, and Marco Roos. 2020. "The 'A' of FAIR – As Open as Possible, as Closed as Necessary." *Data Intelligence* 2 (1-2): 47–55. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00027.
- Larivière, Vincent, Stefanie Haustein, and Philippe Mongeon. 2015. "The Oligopoly of Academic Publishers in the Digital Era." *PloS One* 10 (6): e0127502–. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0127502>.
- Leonelli, Sabina. 2016. *Data-Centric Biology: A Philosophical Study*. University of Chicago Press. <https://doi.org/doi:10.7208/9780226416502>.

———. 2020. “Learning from Data Journeys.” In, Leonelli, S and Tempini, M (eds.) *Data Journeys in the Sciences*, pp 1–24. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37177-7_1.

Liggins, Libby, Maui Hudson, and Jane Anderson. 2021. “Creating Space for Indigenous Perspectives on Access and Benefit-Sharing: Encouraging Researcher Use of the Local Contexts Notices.” *Molecular Ecology* 30 (11): 2477–82. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.15918>.

Marshall, Eliot. 2001. “Bermuda Rules: Community Spirit, with Teeth.” *Science (New York, N.Y.)* 291 (5507): 1192–92. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.291.5507.1192>.

Martin, Corinne, Andrew Smith, and Elixir Partners. 2019. “ELIXIR’s Long-Term Sustainability Plan (2019).” *F1000Research* 8 (September). <https://lens.org/172-342-127-846-466>.

Maxmen, Amy. 2021a. “One Million Coronavirus Sequences: Popular Genome Site Hits Mega Milestone.” *Nature* 593 (7857): 21–21. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-01069-w>.

———. 2021b. “Why Some Researchers Oppose Unrestricted Sharing of Coronavirus Genome Data.” *Nature* 593 (7858): 176–77. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-01194-6>.

May, Christopher. 2011. “Bounded Openness: The Future Political Economy of Knowledge Management.” *European Intellectual Property Review* 33 (8): 477–80.

———. 2015. *The Global Political Economy of Intellectual Property Rights, 2nd Ed.* Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203873816>.

Moeller, Nina Isabella, and Clive Stannard. 2013. “Identifying Benefit Flows: Studies on the Potential Monetary and Non-Monetary Benefits Arising from the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture.” <https://lens.org/174-306-616-776-600>.

Morgera, Elisa, Stephanie Switzer, and Miranda Geelhoed. 2020. “Study for the European Commission on ‘Possible Ways to Address Digital Sequence Information - Legal and Policy Aspects.’” https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/biodiversity/international/abs/pdf/Final_study_legal_and_policy_aspects.pdf.

Morrison, Heather. 2018. *Global OA APCs (APC) 2010–2017: Major Trends*. OpenEdition Press. <https://doi.org/10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2018.16>.

Muller, Manuel Ruiz. 2015. *Genetic Resources as Natural Information*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315754451>.

NIH. 2018. “NIH STRATEGIC PLAN FOR DATA SCIENCE.” https://datascience.nih.gov/sites/default/files/NIH_Strategic_Plan_for_Data_Science_Final_508.pdf.

NLM. 2019. “NLM Is Moving Its Sequence Read Archive (SRA) to the Cloud,” April. https://www.nlm.nih.gov/news/NLM_Moves_SRA_Cloud.html.

- Noorden, Richard Van. 2021. "Scientists Call for Fully Open Sharing of Coronavirus Genome Data." *Nature* 590 (7845): 195–96. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-00305-7>.
- OECD. 2015. "Making Open Science a Reality," no. 25. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>.
- . 2017. "Business Models for Sustainable Research Data Repositories." <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/302b12bb-en.pdf?expires=1627669169&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=02DC9C1CEEC765C9D3785F5684BE0086>.
- . 2021. "Recommendation of the Council on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data." <https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/en/instruments/OECD-LEGAL-0463#relatedInstruments>.
- Oldham, Paul. 2004. "Global Status and Trends in Intellectual Property Claims: Genomics, Proteomics and Biotechnology." *SSRN Electronic Journal*, January. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1331514>.
- Oldham Paul, Colin Barnes, Stephen Hall et al. 2014. "Valuing the Deep: Marine Genetic Resources in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction," http://randd.defra.gov.uk/Document.aspx?Document=12289_ValuingTheDeepDEFRAFinalVersionOne28092014.pdf.
- . 2020. "Digital Sequence Information - Technical Options." https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/biodiversity/international/abs/pdf/Final_Report_technical_aspects_of_DSI.pdf.
- Oldham, Paul, and Kindness, Jasmine. 2021a. "Exploring Trends in Licences for Open Access Publications." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6560921>.
- Oldham, Paul, and Kindness, Jasmine. 2021b. "Sharing Digital Biodiversity Data: Insights from The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6560895>.
- Ostrom, Elinor. 2009. "A General Framework for Analyzing Sustainability of Social-Ecological Systems." *Science* 325 (5939): 419–22. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1172133>.
- Piwowar, Heather A., Jason Priem, Vincent Larivière, Juan Pablo Alperin, Lisa Matthias, Bree Norlander, Ashley Farley, Jevin D. West, and Stefanie Haustein. 2018. "The State of OA: A Large-Scale Analysis of the Prevalence and Impact of Open Access Articles." *PeerJ* 6 (February): e4375–. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4375>.
- Rohden, Fabian, Sixing Huang, Gabriele Dröge, Amber Hartman Scholz, Katharine Barker, Walter G. Berendsohn, Jonathan A. Coddington, et al. 2019. "Combined Study on DSI in Public and Private Databases and DSI Traceability." <https://www.cbd.int/abs/DSI-peer/Study-Traceability-databases.pdf>.
- Salmi, Jamil. 2015. "Study on Open Science Impact, Implications and Policy Options." <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b0906f2d-8907-11e5-b8b7-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>.

- Scholz, A. H., U. Hillebrand, J. Freitag, I. Cancio, C. dos S. Ribeiro, G. Haringhuizen, P. Oldham, et al. 2020. "FINDING COMPROMISE ON ABS & DSI IN THE CBD: REQUIREMENTS & POLICY IDEAS FROM a SCIENTIFIC PERSPECTIVE." <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35180.80001>.
- Scholz, Amber Hartman, Matthias Lange, Pia Habekost, Paul Oldham, Ibon Cancio, Guy Cochrane, and Jens Freitag. 2021. "Myth-Busting the Provider-User Relationship for Digital Sequence Information." *bioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.02.454535>.
- Stephens, Zachary D., Skylar Y. Lee, Faraz Faghri, Roy H. Campbell, ChengXiang Zhai, Miles Efron, Ravishankar K. Iyer, Michael C. Schatz, Saurabh Sinha, and Gene E. Robinson. 2015. "Big Data: Astronomical or Genomical?" *PLoS Biology* 13 (7): e1002195–null. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002195>.
- Stuart, Lawson, Meghreblian Ben, and Brook Michelle. 2014. "Journal Subscription Costs - FOIs to UK Universities." <https://lens.org/169-440-700-578-806>.
- Suber, Peter. 2012. *Open Access*. The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9286.001.0001>.
- Sulston, John, and Sydney Brenner. 1974. "THE DNA OF CAENORHABDITIS ELEGANS." *Genetics* 77 (1): 95–104. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/77.1.95>.
- Swanson, Timothy. 1995. *Intellectual Property Rights and Biodiversity Conservation: Diversity and Sustainability: Evolution, Information and Institutions*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511623417.002>.
- Tahu Kukutai, John Taylor. 2016. *Indigenous Data Sovereignty: Towards an Agenda*. ANU Press. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.22459/CAEPR38.11.2016>.
- Tenopir, Carol, and Donald W. King. 1997. "Trends in Scientific Scholarly Journal Publishing in the United States." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 28 (3): 135–70. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp-028-03-135>.
- UNESCO. 2021. "UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science." <https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>.
- Vicente-Saez, Ruben, and Clara Martínez-Fuentes. 2018. "Open Science Now: A Systematic Literature Review for an Integrated Definition." *Journal of Business Research* 88: 428–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.12.043>.
- Vogel, Joseph Henry. 1994. *Genes for Sale: Privatization as a Conservation Policy*. <https://www.amazon.com/Genes-Sale-Privatization-Conservation-Policy/dp/0195089103>; <https://lens.org/136-569-370-077-119>.
- . 2011. "The Economics of Information, Studiously Ignored in the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and Benefit Sharing." <https://doaj.org/article/8b4506731fcc43babb9470166a463c86>; <https://lens.org/002-249-937-400-078>.
- Vogel, Joseph Henry, Klaus Angerer, Manuel Ruiz Muller, and Omar Oduardo-Sierra. 2017. "Bounded Openness as the Modality for the Global Multilateral Benefit-Sharing

Mechanism of the Nagoya Protocol.” In *Routledge Handbook of Biodiversity and the Law*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315530857-26>.

Warner, Simeon. 2001. “Open Archives Initiative Protocol Development and Implementation at arXiv.” <https://lens.org/012-626-562-668-409>.

Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. “Scientific Data - the FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3 (1): 160018–18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

Wu, Caesar, Rajkumar Buyya, and Kotagiri Ramamohanarao. 2019. “Cloud Pricing Models: Taxonomy, Survey, and Interdisciplinary Challenges.” *ACM Computing Surveys* 52 (6): 108–36. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3342103>.

Annex 1: Version Zero Proposal

This paper proposes a cross-instrument system for sharing digital sequence information (DSI) and benefit-sharing in the form of a distributed global biodiversity fund, under the Convention on Biological Diversity and related instruments addressing DSI. The proposed system will be open to all United Nations member states (hereafter, participating parties). Key partners in the proposed system include: the biodiversity and life science infrastructure; the private sector; research funding bodies and IPBES; technical assistance and conservation organisations, and; indigenous peoples and local communities.

Under this proposal:

1. Participating parties agree a shared set of principles including a commitment to open access and open science based on the *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* and *OECD Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data* (EASD);
2. Participating parties mandate the use of a small set of open standard licences for DSI. Participating parties require data providers to deposit licenced sequence data with databases and infrastructure participating in the wider system;
3. Participating parties introduce measures for revenue generation linked to digital sequence information and the life science and biodiversity infrastructure;
4. Each participating party establishes a fund that will form part of a distributed global biodiversity fund;
5. Participating parties establish a shared roadmap setting out priorities for investment in biodiversity in partnership with other participating parties. The roadmap supports implementation of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework;
6. Disbursement of investments from the distributed global biodiversity fund will be made in accordance with the priorities established in the shared roadmap. Disbursements are made through existing administrative infrastructure in collaboration with technical assistance agencies at the relevant level for the proposed activities;
7. Participants. Identification of key stakeholders and participants in the proposed system.

The main elements of the proposed system are further described in outline form below as a basis for potential further discussion.

1. PRINCIPLES

- 1.1 A shared commitment to the implementation of the objectives of participating instruments and processes;⁷²
- 1.2 A shared commitment to open access and the pursuit of open science under the 2021 *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* in the implementation of the participating instruments and processes;
- 1.3 A shared commitment to enhancing access to and sharing of data taking into account the recommendations set out in *The Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data (EASD)* adopted by the Council of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in October 2021;
- 1.4 Recognition that biodiversity is not free and has to be paid for. Everyone, proportionate to their means, must contribute;
- 1.5 Recognition that a quantifiable financial return to nature must be embedded in policy responses;⁷³
- 1.6 Recognition of the priorities of developing countries;
- 1.7 Recognition of the rights and priorities of indigenous peoples and local communities;
- 1.8 [to be further elaborated...]

2. OPEN LICENCES

2.1 Licences

A system of standard open electronic licences will be agreed for digital sequence information. Open licences for digital sequence information will support implementation of the FAIR principles⁷⁴ and be:

- simple
- interoperable
- machine readable
- findable
- available in multiple languages
- compatible, as appropriate, with existing licences
- without prejudice to existing intellectual property rights

⁷² The term 'processes' refers to policy processes addressing dsi and genetic resources that are not legal instruments as such. Animal genetic resources under the FAO Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture is an example.

⁷³ Dasgupta, P (2021) *The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review*. London: UK Treasury.

⁷⁴ Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. "Scientific Data - the FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship." *Scientific Data* 3 (1): 160018–18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

Participating parties agree to adopt a limited and clearly defined set of interoperable open licences. Open licences may be limited to the following categories:⁷⁵

- Attribution. Any use permitted provided that attribution of source is given;
- Non-Commercial. Attribution of source and use for non-commercial purposes;⁷⁶
- Waiver of Rights. All rights, including the right of attribution, over digital sequence information are explicitly and irrevocably waived.

2.2 Use of Licences

2.2.1 The use of standard licences will be mandated by the participating parties in the system. The system will be flexible enough to accommodate the needs of participating parties at the time the system is introduced:

- a) Parties to the Nagoya Protocol requiring PIC or MAT for digital sequence information under national legislation specify a suitable standard licence in Mutually Agreed Terms (an ABS contract) with the user;⁷⁷
- b) Parties who do not require PIC or MAT for digital sequence information mandate the use of one or more standard licences as the default.

2.2.2 Participating parties will require all users to deposit sequences in databases and related infrastructure that participate in the distributed global biodiversity fund.

2.3 Licence platform

2.3.1 A cost effective electronic server platform will be created to host standard licence templates and guidance;

2.3.2 The server platform will be hosted by one or more participating institutions in the system to reduce costs;

2.3.3 Data providers will be able to generate licences for use in their systems using an Application Programming Interface (API or web service);

2.3.4 All software code for licence generation will be publicly available under a permissive open source licence to allow for easy incorporation into systems;

2.3.5 Agreed changes to licences over time will be addressed using versions (version 1, version 2 etc.). Versions will be visible in the supporting platform.

⁷⁵ The three licences listed are those used by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility since 2016 as agreed in 2014 by the Governing Board consisting of participants from developed and developing countries. Over 2 billion taxonomic records are listed under these licences including millions of metadata records for sequences from the INSDC and the International Barcode of Life Project (IBOL).

⁷⁶ Non-commercial use is a widely used expression but is subject to multiple and conflicting interpretations. Participating parties may wish to explicitly define activities constituting commercial or non-commercial use, use alternative terminology or drop the option.

⁷⁷ This is intended to address circumstances where Parties to the Nagoya Protocol have included PIC and MAT requirements for digital sequence information.

2.4 Database Terms and Conditions

2.4.1 Databases and related infrastructure participating in the system will adopt standard terms and conditions for data providers and users that are consistent with the open licences used under the system;

2.4.2 Databases and related infrastructure will adopt such additional terms and conditions as may be required from time to time for effective operation of the system.

3. REVENUE GENERATING MEASURES

Participating parties agree to take measures to generate revenue linked to digital sequence information and the biodiversity and life science infrastructure. Participating parties are encouraged to introduce additional innovative revenue generating measures beyond the initial starter model set out below with the aim of maximising investments for biodiversity over the long term.

Participating parties seek to establish partnerships with the private sector in the design of business models for revenue generation, as providers of services (e.g. cloud computing services technology), and as users of digital sequence information and the associated biodiversity and life science infrastructure.

Participating parties may identify one or more revenue generating measures as starter models to initiate revenue generation.

3.1 Cold Start/Start Up Fund

3.1.1 Participating parties agree to make financial commitments to a temporary fund to support participants with initiating revenue generating measures.

3.2 Cloud Infrastructure Measures (proposed starter model)

3.2.1 Parties to the licensing system agree to require digital sequence information to be deposited with databases and life science and biodiversity infrastructure that participates in the distributed global biodiversity fund;

3.2.2 Digital sequence information will be openly accessible free of charge;

3.2.3 Participating databases and related infrastructure will charge users fees for the use of the infrastructure;

3.2.4 Fees will be transparent to parties and users and based on the principle of use.

3.2.5 Participating parties agree that no user is exempt from fees, but fees will be proportionate to means;

3.2.6 Fees for users from developing countries will be discounted in accordance with criteria to be agreed between participating parties, such as Purchasing Power Parties (PPPs) and/or the use of electronic voucher schemes.⁷⁸

⁷⁸ Voucher schemes have been widely introduced by cloud computing companies to provide researchers with access to infrastructure services they would not otherwise be able to afford (e.g., large scale parallel computing and analysis). Some of these schemes are explicitly linked to environmental purposes such as the Microsoft Planetary Computer providing important opportunities for potential partnerships.

3.2.7 Existing cloud computing pricing models will be applied and include:

- i) Pay as you go;
- ii) Subscription;
- iii) Other.

3.2.8 Participating parties invite funding agencies to reimburse publicly funded researcher costs for use of the infrastructure in line with policies to reimburse open access related costs.

3.3 Other Revenue Generating Measures⁷⁹

Participating parties are encouraged to identify, model, pilot and implement additional innovative business models for revenue generation. Such models may include, inter alia:

- Levies (e.g. on bio-based products);
- Micro-Levies (e.g. on reagents/sequencing machines);
- Membership Fees (e.g. Plant Treaty proposals);
- Royalty rates linked to patent filings (bounded openness);
- Other innovative revenue generation models (e.g. biodiversity tokens, bonds etc.).

4. A DISTRIBUTED GLOBAL BIODIVERSITY FUND

4.1 Participating parties agree to establish a benefit-sharing mechanism for investments in biodiversity and to support the sustainability of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure related to digital sequence information;

4.2 The benefit-sharing mechanism will take a distributed form operated by each participating party on the national and, where appropriate, regional level⁸⁰;

4.3 The individual funds established by participating parties shall collectively constitute the distributed global biodiversity fund;

4.3 Each participating party will collect fees arising from the income generation measures identified above in accordance with their existing procedures and accounting practices;

⁷⁹ Models in the list below are drawn from the proposal by the Africa Group for a levy on sales of biobased projects and the outcomes of various studies including WILDSI, Oldham, Morgera et al., debates under the Plant Treaty, Vogel and Muller among others.

⁸⁰ The regional level in the context of this proposal refers to the European Union and the African Union among others.

4.4 Each participating party will disburse funds for investment in partnership with other participating parties through existing technical assistance and related organisations with the aim of minimising transaction, accounting and reporting costs;

4.5 Disbursements for investments by participating parties will be targeted at the level appropriate to the proposed activity (e.g. local, national, regional, international) using existing administrative infrastructure and procedures. Particular attention will be paid to implementing effective measures for supporting investments with indigenous peoples and local communities who are at the forefront of the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity;

4.6 Participating parties agree to make disbursements in accordance with the shared roadmap setting out agreed priorities for the distributed global biodiversity fund.

5. A SHARED ROADMAP

5.1 Participating parties agree to establish a shared roadmap setting out mutually agreed priorities for investment from the distributed global biodiversity fund. The shared road map will support implementation of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework;

5.2 Priorities for investment under the shared roadmap will include:

5.2.1 Investments in biodiversity;

5.2.2 Supporting the sustainability of the biodiversity and life science infrastructure among participating parties;

5.2.3 Capacity building;

5.2.4 Indigenous peoples and local communities;

5.2.5 Supporting pilot experiments between participating parties with innovative models for revenue generation.

5.3 Priorities for investment under the shared roadmap will be identified at the appropriate level (local, national, regional, international etc.);

5.4 Participating parties agree to take measures to improve the transparency of information on the use of digital sequence information licenced under the system as part of the creation of a trusted system. Participating parties agree that track and trace measures, including encryption technologies such as block chain, are not required in the trusted system;

5.5 Participating parties agree on suitable indicators to measure progress in implementation of priorities under the shared roadmap as part of the trusted system. Wherever possible indicators will be drawn from existing indicators in order to avoid duplication of effort and minimize costs.

5.6 Participating parties are encouraged to share experiences and lessons learned in the implementation of the national biodiversity funds under the distributed global biodiversity fund;

5.7 The shared roadmap will be periodically updated in accordance with a timetable agreed between participating parties and in consultation with all participating instruments and processes;

5.8 The Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity shall serve as the periodic meeting of participating parties and instruments for review of implementation of the shared roadmap;

5.8 *alt* In order to maximise the participation of all participating instruments and processes and ensure coherence in policy implementation, the periodic meeting of participating parties will rotate between the Conference of the Parties / Meeting of the Governing Body, as appropriate, of participating instruments and processes.

6. PARTICIPANTS

The design and implementation of the system described above will require expertise and participation from a range of different stakeholders and rights holders (hereafter, participants).

6.1 The participation of the private sector will be central to the implementation of the proposal outlined above in four main areas:

- a) As partners in service provision (e.g. cloud computing and infrastructure provision);
- b) As paying users (e.g. of infrastructure linked to digital sequence information);
- c) In providing expertise to advise on the design of innovative business models for income generation and the review of business plans for national funds and sustainability of the national infrastructure;
- d) In implementing nature based solutions.

6.2 National and regional research funding bodies have a central role to play:

- a) In supporting the infrastructure it funds in making the transition from a short term research project based funding model to a social enterprise model;
- b) In ensuring that publicly funded researchers are aware of the need to deposit and use licenced sequence data and the aims of the wider system;
- c) In ensuring the cost effective collection of funds originating from public sector research for allocation to the distributed global fund;

- d) In identifying research priorities for the shared roadmap between participating parties;⁸¹
- e) In coordinating research collaborations between participating parties for cost effective implementation of projects and programs to address the research priorities in the shared roadmap;
- f) In identifying innovative ways forward in supporting research activities that are vital for advancing knowledge and understanding of biodiversity but receive very limited support relative to their wider significance (e.g. taxonomy, the deep oceans, neglected foods, neglected diseases, indigenous peoples and local communities)

6.3 Technical Assistance Agencies and non-governmental organisations have a central role to play in:

- a) Assisting participating parties with identifying partners for implementation of priorities under the shared roadmap (match making);
- b) Working with participating parties on planning and budgeting for programmes and projects to address priorities in the shared roadmap at the appropriate level;
- c) Assisting participating parties with implementation of programmes and projects;
- d) Reporting in accordance with standard procedures to the participating party/parties involved in making disbursements from the distributed global fund.

6.4 Indigenous peoples and local communities are at the forefront of the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity and are rights holders under international law. They are key target beneficiaries of the distributed global biodiversity fund. Participating parties agree to work with indigenous peoples and local communities to identify their priorities for investment for inclusion in the shared roadmap.

⁸¹ IPBES has an important role to play in the identification of research priorities and its role could be more clearly reflected in this proposal.

Annex 2: Storage Based Projections for Potential Cloud Based Revenue

DSI cloud subscription based revenue projection based on existing user counts at 10, 25 or 50 cents a day or 1 dollar price point (US\$ dollars).

pp = per person, 1 month = 20 working days. Note workings assume *all users* pay a flat Dropbox/Google Photos style cloud subscription fee regardless of access, dsi or usage type.

dsi user number assumption	user count per year	daily pp	monthly pp	yearly pp	revenue per day	monthly revenue	yearly revenue	year five
ELIXIR 2019	2,867,265	0.1	2	24	286,727	5,734,530	68,814,360	344,071,800
	2,867,265	0.25	5	60	716,816	14,336,325	172,035,900	860,179,500
	2,867,265	0.5	10	120	1,433,633	28,672,650	344,071,800	1,720,359,000
	2,867,265	1	20	240	2,867,265	57,345,300	688,143,600	3,440,718,000
NCBI 2018	4,500,000	0.1	2	24	450,000	9,000,000	108,000,000	540,000,000
	4,500,000	0.25	5	60	1,125,000	22,500,000	270,000,000	1,350,000,000
	4,500,000	0.5	10	120	2,250,000	45,000,000	540,000,000	2,700,000,000
	4,500,000	1	20	240	4,500,000	90,000,000	1,080,000,000	5,400,000,000
GenBank (Rohden et al 2019)	5,800,000	0.1	2	24	580,000	11,600,000	139,200,000	696,000,000
	5,800,000	0.25	5	60	1,450,000	29,000,000	348,000,000	1,740,000,000
	5,800,000	0.5	10	120	2,900,000	58,000,000	696,000,000	3,480,000,000
	5,800,000	1	20	240	5,800,000	116,000,000	1,392,000,000	6,960,000,000
INSDC median (Rohden et al 2019)	12,500,000	0.1	2	24	1,250,000	25,000,000	300,000,000	1,500,000,000
	12,500,000	0.25	5	60	3,125,000	62,500,000	750,000,000	3,750,000,000
	12,500,000	0.5	10	120	6,250,000	125,000,000	1,500,000,000	7,500,000,000
	12,500,000	1	20	240	12,500,000	250,000,000	3,000,000,000	15,000,000,000
Global (Rohden et al 2019)	500,000,000	0.1	2	24	50,000,000	1,000,000,000	12,000,000,000	60,000,000,000
	500,000,000	0.25	5	60	125,000,000	2,500,000,000	30,000,000,000	150,000,000,000
	500,000,000	0.5	10	120	250,000,000	5,000,000,000	60,000,000,000	300,000,000,000
	500,000,000	1	20	240	500,000,000	10,000,000,000	120,000,000,000	600,000,000,000